

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4355–4488

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0040

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a target called Allison Mine located northwest of the butte Texoli. Illuminated by sunlight from the upper right, this is MAHLI focus merge product 4444MH0001710001601324R00, created onboard the instrument from a focus stack acquired on Sol 4443.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 4355th and 4488th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 4355 and 4488.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4355–4488*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 39 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 05 November 2024 through 22 March 2025.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 4355 through 4488 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4355 – 4488						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Traversing west towards Rustic Canyon near Texoli	05 Nov 24	4355	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Epidote Peak and the target Millys Foot Path. The focus stack images were also merged.
	10 Nov 24	4359	9	74	0	On Sol 4357, MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3506 (data from Sols 4139-4306) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. On Sol 4359, MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Forester Pass and the targets Mahogany Creek and Buttress Tree.
	11 Nov 24	4360	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4359 were merged.
	19 Nov 24	4368	9	66	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Calaveras and Murphys.
	20 Nov 24	4369	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4368 were merged.
	21 Nov 24	4370	12	112	0	MAHLI acquired an 8-position L-shaped mosaic on the target Lee Vining. MAHLI also imaged the target Buttermilk.
	22 Nov 24	4371	0	0	11	Focus stack images from Sol 4370 were merged.
	23 Nov 24	4372	7	62	0	MAHLI imaged the target Mount Tallac and the DRT-brushed target Cienega Mirth.
	25 Nov 24	4374	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4372 were merged.
Traversing west towards Rustic Canyon near Texoli	03 Dec 24	4382	11	54	4	MAHLI imaged the target Coronet Lake. MAHLI also imaged the target Excelsior Mountain, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.
	05 Dec 24	4384	9	84	8	MAHLI imaged the targets Placerville and Three Brothers. The focus stack images were also merged.
	07 Dec 24	4386	11	71	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Icehouse Canyon and the DRT-brushed target Sunland.
	08 Dec 24	4387	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4386 were merged.
	10 Dec 24	4389	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Cerro Negro and the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Dec 24	4393	9	66	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the DRT-brushed targets Triunfo Canyon and Calabasas Peak.
	15 Dec 24	4394	0	0	6	MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3507 through 4751 (data from Sols 4307-4355) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. Focus stack images from Sol 4393 were merged.
Traversing west towards Rustic Canyon near Texoli	07 Jan 25	4416	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Snow Creek and the DRT-brushed target Winter Creek.
	08 Jan 25	4417	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4416 were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4355 – 4488						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Traversing west towards Rustic Canyon near Texoli	16 Jan 25	4425	6	52	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Rancho_Potrero and the target Fawnskin. The focus stack images were also merged.
	19 Jan 25/ 20 Jan 25	4428	11	76	0	MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHLI also imaged the target Magic Mountain and the DRT-brushed target Idlehour.
	20 Jan 25	4429	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4428 were merged.
At Rustic Canyon near Texoli	23 Jan 25	4431	7	62	0	MAHLI imaged the target Pleasant_View_Ridge and the DRT-brushed target Bee_Rock.
	23 Jan 25/ 24 Jan 25	4432	20	20	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4431 were merged. MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
Transversing southwest around Texoli	26 Jan 25	4434	9	74	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Little_Jimmy, Acton and Wildhorse.
	27 Jan 25	4435	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4434 were merged.
	29 Jan 25	4437	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Desert_View and the focus stack images were merged.
	31 Jan 25	4439	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Deer_Springs and the focus stack images were merged.
Transversing southwest around Texoli	02 Feb 25	4441	8	40	0	MAHLI imaged the target Coldwater_Canyon, which included a run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface.
	03 Feb 25	4442	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 4441 were merged.
	04 Feb 25	4443	11	78	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target San_Rafael_Hills and the target Allison_Mine.
	05 Feb 25	4444	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4443 were merged.
	06 Feb 25	4445	11	63	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Zuma_Canyon and the DRT-brushed target Bear_Canyon.
	07 Feb 25	4446	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4445 were merged.
	08 Feb 25	4447	8	56	0	MAHLI imaged the target Bridge_To_Nowhere, which included a 2x1 mosaic, and the DRT-brushed target Aliso_Canyon.
	10 Feb 25	4449	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4447 were merged.
	13 Feb 25	4452	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Catalina_Island and the focus stack images were merged.
	16 Feb 25	4455	19	134	0	MAHLI imaged the target Skyline_Trail and the DRT-brushed target Lake_Arrowhead. MAHLI also imaged the target Strawberry_Peak, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface.
	17 Feb 25	4456	0	0	12	Focus stack images from Sol 4455 were merged.
	19 Feb 25	4458	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Wheeler_Gorge and Chumash_Trail.
	20 Feb 25	4459	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4458 were merged.
	22 Feb 25	4461	13	59	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the targets Wellman_Divide and Salton_Sea.
	23 Feb 25	4462	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4461 were merged.
25 Feb 25	4464	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Matilija_Poppy and the focus stack images were merged.	
27 Feb 25	4466	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Trippet_Ranch and the focus stack images were merged.	
Transversing southwest around Texoli	05 Mar 25	4471	4	40	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Ramona_Trail and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4355 – 4488						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Transversing southwest around Texoli	11 Mar 25	4477	7	65	0	MAHLI imaged the target Angeles_Crest and acquired a 4x1 mosaic on the target Millard_Canyon.
	12 Mar 25	4478	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4477 were merged.
	13 Mar 25	4479	10	100	0	MAHLI imaged the target Stunt_Ranch and the target Pacifico_Mountain, which includes a 3x1 mosaic.
	14 Mar 25	4480	0	0	10	Focus stack images from Sol 4479 were merged.
	15 Mar 25	4481	14	140	0	MAHLI acquired a 5x1 mosaic on the target Yerba_Buena_Ridge. MAHLI also imaged the targets South_Fork and Sepulveda_Pass.
	17 Mar 25	4483	0	0	14	Focus stack images from Sol 4481 were merged.
	20 Mar 25	4486	21	202	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Palm_Grove and acquired a 8x2 mosaic on the target Duna_Vista.
	21 Mar 25	4487	0	0	20	Focus stack images from Sol 4486 were merged.
	22 Mar 25	4488	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Solstice_Canyon and the target Black_Oak.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, etc.). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 4355–4488 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 4355, 4359, 4368, 4370, 4372, 4382, 4384, 4386, 4389, 4393, 4416, 4425, 4428, 4431, 4432, 4434, 4437, 4439, 4441, 4443, 4445, 4447, 4452, 4455, 4458, 4461, 4464, 4466, 4471, 4477, 4479, 4481, 4486, 4488.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{\text{uncertainty}} = (p_{\text{far}} + p_{\text{near}})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

SOL 4355 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Epidote_Peak – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4355MH0001900011404689C00	4689	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4355MH0001680011404691C00	4691	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4355MH0002270001104750R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4355MH0002270001104751S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4355MH0001680011304701C00	4701	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4355MH0002270001104748R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4355MH0002270001104749S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4355MH0007430011304711C00	4711	15168	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4355MH0002270001104746R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4355MH0002270001104747S00	

target named Millys_Foot_Path

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4355MH0001900011304721C00	4721	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4355MH0002240011304723C00	4723	14059	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4355MH0002270001104744R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4355MH0002270001104745S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4355MH0002240011304733C00	4733	14083	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4355MH0002270001104742R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4355MH0002270001104743S00	

SOL 4359 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Forester_Pass – after DRT**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4359MH000190001160002C00	2	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4359MH000336001160004C00	4	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600087R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600088S00
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4359MH000336001160004C00	14	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600085R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600086S00
mhlI00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4359MH0008480011600024C00	24	15020	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600083R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600084S00

target named **Mahogany_Creek**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4359MH0001900011600034C00	34	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6	
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4359MH0003360011600036C00	36	14198	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600081R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600082S00
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4359MH0003360011600046C00	46	14204	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600079R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600080S00

target named **Buttress_Tree**

mhlI00892	INTERMEDIATE-RES STEREO-1 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 13 cm													
	4359MH0008920011600056C00	56	13414	13.3	11.4	-0.5	0.5	53.7	1.7	1608	1198	8.6	6.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600077R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600078S00	
mhlI00892	INTERMEDIATE-RES STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 13 cm													
	4359MH0008920011600066C00	66	13430	13.0	11.1	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	1608	1198	8.5	6.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4360MH0001710001600075R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4360MH0001710001600076S00	

SOL 4368 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Calaveras – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW STEREO-1 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4368MH000190001160090C00	90	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4368MH000336001160092C00	92	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600165R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600166S00		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4368MH0003360011600102C00	102	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600163R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600164S00		
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4368MH0008640011600112C00	112	15115	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600161R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600162S00		
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4368MH0001900011600122C00	122	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	

target named Murphys – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4368MH0001900011600124C00	124	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4368MH0003360011600126C00	126	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600159R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600160S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4368MH0003360011600136C00	136	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600157R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600158S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4368MH0008480011600146C00	146	15101	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4369MH0001630001600155R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4369MH0001630001600156S00	

SOL 4370 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Lee_Vining** – an 8-position L-shaped mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
POSITION 1 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00854	4370MH0008540011600168C00		168	13098	22.3	20.4	-1.3	1.4	85.4	4.7	1608	1198	13.7	10.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600299R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600300S00														
POSITION 2 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00854	4370MH0008540011600178C00		178	13114	21.6	19.7	-1.2	1.3	83.0	4.4	1608	1198	13.3	9.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600297R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600298S00														
POSITION 3 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00854	4370MH0008540011600188C00		188	13135	20.8	18.9	-1.1	1.2	80.0	4.1	1608	1198	12.9	9.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600295R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600296S00														
POSITION 4 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00854	4370MH0008540011600198C00		198	13150	20.2	18.3	-1.1	1.1	78.0	3.8	1608	1198	12.5	9.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600293R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600294S00														
POSITION 5 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00854	4370MH0008540011600208C00		208	13164	19.7	17.8	-1.0	1.1	76.2	3.7	1608	1198	12.2	9.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600291R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600292S00														
POSITION 6 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00846	4370MH0008460011600218C00		218	13164	19.7	17.8	-1.0	1.1	76.2	3.7	1608	1198	12.2	9.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600289R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600290S00														
POSITION 7 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00846	4370MH0008460011600228C00		228	13158	19.9	18.0	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.7	1608	1198	12.4	9.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600287R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600288S00														
POSITION 8 OF 8 INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm														
mhli00846	4370MH0008460011600238C00		238	13155	20.0	18.1	-1.0	1.1	77.3	3.8	1608	1198	12.4	9.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600285R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600286S00														

target named **Buttermilk**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm														
mhli00190	4370MH0001900011600248C00		248	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
APXS RASTER SPOT 3														
mhli00224	4370MH0002240011600250C00		250	13940	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600283R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600284S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
mhli00224	4370MH0002240011600260C00		260	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600281R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600282S00														
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm														
APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
mhli00224	4370MH0002240011600270C00		270	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600279R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4371MH0004490001600280S00														

SOL 4372 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Mount_Tallac**

mhl100291	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm													
	4372MH0002910011600302C00	302	13503	11.8	9.9	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600373R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600374S00	
mhl100291	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm													
	4372MH0002910011600312C00	312	13503	11.8	9.9	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600371R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600372S00	

target named **Cienega_Mirth – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4372MH0001900011600322C00	322	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4372MH0003360011600324C00	324	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600369R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600370S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4372MH0003360011600334C00	334	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600367R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600368S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4372MH0008480011600344C00	344	15162	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600365R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600366S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4372MH0003360011600354C00	354	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4374MH0001630001600363R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4374MH0001630001600364S00	

SOL 4382 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Coronet_Lake**

mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4382MH0008650011600376C00	376	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600435R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600436S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4382MH0002240011600386C00	386	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600433R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600434S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4382MH0002240011600396C00	396	13964	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600431R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600432S00					
mhl100838	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm											
	4382MH0008380011600406C00	406	15012	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600429R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4382MH0001530001600430S00					

target named **Excelsior_Mountain**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4382MH0001900011600416C00	416	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7

target named **Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode**

mhl100866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4382MH0008660011600418C00	418	14147	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
mhl100867	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 4 cm											
	4382MH0008670011600420C00	420	14145	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
mhl100868	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 3 cm											
	4382MH0008680011600422C00	422	14360	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100869	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm											
	4382MH0008690011600424C00	424	14659	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
mhl100870	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm											
	4382MH0008700011600426C00	426	14840	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3
mhl100871	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm											
	4382MH0008710011600428C00	428	15070	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0

SOL 4384 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Placerville**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0007060011600438C00	438	13048	24.8	22.9	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.3
mhlI00852	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm									
	4384MH0008520011600441C00	441	13635	10.0	8.1	-0.3	0.3	42.3	1.0	1608	1198	6.8	5.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600535R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600536S00					

target named **Three_Brothers**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00855	CONTEXT STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0008550011600452C00	452	12965	30.1	28.2	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	1608	1198	18.1	13.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600533R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600534S00					
mhlI00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4384MH0001520011600462C00	462	13812	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.7	1608	1198	5.8	4.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600531R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600532S00					
mhlI00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4384MH0001520011600472C00	472	13478	12.2	10.3	-0.4	0.4	49.8	1.5	1608	1198	8.0	6.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600529R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600530S00					
mhlI00855	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0008550011600482C00	482	12962	30.3	28.4	-2.3	2.6	113.6	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600527R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600528S00					
mhlI00855	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0008550011600492C00	492	12964	30.1	28.2	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600525R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600526S00					
mhlI00855	CONTEXT STEREO-4 – ROTATED OFFSET			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0008550011600502C00	502	12968	29.8	27.9	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	1608	1198	18.0	13.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600523R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600524S00					
mhlI00855	CONTEXT STEREO-5 – ROTATED OFFSET			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4384MH0008550011600512C00	512	12965	30.1	28.2	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	1608	1198	18.1	13.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600521R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4384MH0008930001600522S00					

SOL 4386 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target

NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.

mhl100371	BAR TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4386MH0003710011600538C00	538	14375	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100372	CENT TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4386MH0003720011600540C00	540	14370	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE – 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET												
	4386MH0003740011600542C00	542	12961	30.4	28.5	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6
	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS												
	4386MH0003740021600543C00	543	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)

APXS calibration target

NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).

mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4386MH0003730011600545C00	545	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named Icehouse_Canyon

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW												
	4386MH0008760011600547C00	547	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600618R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600619S00						
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1												
	4386MH0001520011600557C00	557	14189	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600616R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600617S00						
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2												
	4386MH0001520011600567C00	567	14204	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600614R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600615S00						

target named Sunland – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW												
	4386MH0001900011600577C00	577	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1												
	4386MH0003360011600579C00	579	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600612R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600613S00						
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2												
	4386MH0003360011600589C00	589	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600610R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600611S00						
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW												
	4386MH0008480011600599C00	599	14918	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600608R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4387MH0001630001600609S00						

UPDATED: 11_December_2024

SOL 4389 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Cerro_Negro															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4389MH0001900011600621C00	621	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4389MH0001680011600623C00	623	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4389MH0001930001600656R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4389MH0001930001600657S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4389MH0001680011600633C00	633	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4389MH0001930001600654R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4389MH0001930001600655S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm												
	4389MH0007430011600643C00	643	15097	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4389MH0001930001600652R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4389MH0001930001600653S00

SOL 4393 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4393MH0000950011600659C00	659	13265	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8

target named <u>Triunfo_Canyon</u> - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4393MH0001900011600661C00	661	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4393MH0001680011600663C00	663	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600734R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600735S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4393MH0001680011600673C00	673	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600732R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600733S00	
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4393MH0008640011600683C00	683	15088	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600730R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600731S00	

target named <u>Calababas_Peak</u> - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4393MH0001900011600693C00	693	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4393MH0003360011600695C00	695	14032	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600728R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600729S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4393MH0003360011600705C00	705	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600726R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600727S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4393MH0008480011600715C00	715	15207	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600724R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4394MH0001630001600725S00	

SOL 4416 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Snow_Creek**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4416MH0001900011600737C00	737	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4416MH0003360011600739C00	739	13970	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4417MH0002270001600798R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4417MH0002270001600799S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4416MH0003360011600749C00	749	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4417MH0002270001600796R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4417MH0002270001600797S00	

target named **Winter_Creek - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4416MH0001900011600759C00	759	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4416MH0003360011600761C00	761	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4417MH0002270001600794R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4417MH0002270001600795S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4416MH0003360011600771C00	771	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4417MH0002270001600792R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4417MH0002270001600793S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4416MH0008480011600781C00	781	15058	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4417MH0002270001600790R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4417MH0002270001600791S00	

SOL 4425 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Rancho_Potrero - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4425MH0001900011600801C00	801	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4425MH0001680011600803C00	803	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600860R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4425MH0002270001600861S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4425MH0001680011600813C00	813	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600858R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4425MH0002270001600859S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4425MH0007430011600823C00	823	15212	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600856R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4425MH0002270001600857S00

target named **Fawnskin**

mhl100894	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm													
	4425MH0008940011600833C00	833	13156	20.0	18.1	-1.0	1.1	77.2	3.8	1608	1198	12.4	9.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600854R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4425MH0002270001600855S00	
mhl100894	CONTEXT STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm													
	4425MH0008940011600843C00	843	13161	19.8	17.9	-1.0	1.1	76.5	3.7	1608	1198	12.3	9.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600852R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4425MH0002270001600853S00	

SOL 4428 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120001600862C00	862	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120011600863C00	863	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120021600864C00	864	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120031600865C00	865	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0007120041600866C00	866	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530001600867C00	867	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530011600868C00	868	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530021600869C00	869	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530031600870C00	870	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0004530041600871C00	871	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0004530051600872C00	872	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530001600873C00	873	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530011600874C00	874	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530021600875C00	875	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0004530031600876C00	876	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT - ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0004530041600877C00	877	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0004530051600878C00	878	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

NOTE: WHERE THE MOTOR COUNT IS GIVEN IN BLUE FONT, THE DUST COVER WAS CLOSED DURING THE IMAGING; PLEASE USE CAUTION IN INTERPRETING THE RANGE AND SCALE INFORMATION, AS THE RESULTS ARE LESS CERTAIN.

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS - ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120001600879C00	879	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120011600880C00	880	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120021600881C00	881	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT - ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION - MANUAL FOCUS												
	4428MH0007120031600882C00	882	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
INFINITY FOCUS - MANUAL FOCUS													
4428MH0007120041600883C00	883	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

Continued on Next Page..

target named Magic_Mountain													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4428MH0001900011600885C00	885	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4428MH0001680011600887C00	887	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600946R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4429MH0002270001600947500					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4428MH0001680011600897C00	897	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600944R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4429MH0002270001600945500					

target named Idlehour - after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	4428MH0001900011600907C00	907	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4428MH0003360011600909C00	909	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600942R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4429MH0002270001600943S00					
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	4428MH0003360011600919C00	919	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600940R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4429MH0002270001600941S00					
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm											
	4428MH0008480011600929C00	929	15167	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600938R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4429MH0002270001600939S00					

SOL 4431 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Pleasant_View_Ridge

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4431MH0008760011600949C00	949	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601020R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601021S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4431MH0003060011600959C00	959	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601018R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601019S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4431MH0003060011600969C00	969	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601016R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601017S00	

target named Bee_Rock – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4431MH0001900011600979C00	979	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601014R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601015S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4431MH0003360011600981C00	981	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601012R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601013S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4431MH0003360011600991C00	991	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601012R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601013S00	
mhl100873	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	4431MH0008730011601001C00	1001	14694	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601010R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							4432MH0001630001601011S00	

SOL 4432 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 4432)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4432MH0007690011601022E01	1022	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4432MH0007700011601023E01	1023	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4432MH0007710011601024E01	1024	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4432MH0007720011601025E01	1025	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 4432)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4432MH0007690011601026E01	1026	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4432MH0007700011601027E01	1027	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4432MH0007710011601028E01	1028	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4432MH0007720011601029E01	1029	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 4432)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4432MH0007690011601030E01	1030	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4432MH0007700011601031E01	1031	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4432MH0007710011601032E01	1032	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4432MH0007720011601033E01	1033	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 4432)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4432MH0007690011601034E01	1034	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4432MH0007700011601035E01	1035	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4432MH0007710011601036E01	1036	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4432MH0007720011601037E01	1037	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

Continued on Next Page..

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 4432)													
mhl00769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4432MH0007690011601038E01	1038	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~-612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4432MH0007700011601039E01	1039	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~-408	~-137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4432MH0007710011601040E01	1040	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~-489	~-210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4432MH0007720011601041E01	1041	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~-450	~-175	1608	1198	~72	~54

SOL 4434 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Little_Jimmy**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4434MH0001900011601043C00	1043	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001820011601045C00	1045	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601128R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601129S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001820011601055C00	1055	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601126R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601127S00	

target named **Acton**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4434MH0001900011601065C00	1065	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001730011601067C00	1067	14110	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601124R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601125S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001730011601077C00	1077	14115	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601122R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601123S00	

target named **Wildhorse**

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4434MH0008760011601087C00	1087	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601120R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601121S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001520011601097C00	1097	14101	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601118R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601119S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4434MH0001520011601107C00	1107	14090	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4435MH0001710001601116R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4435MH0001710001601117S00	

UPDATED: 29_January_2025

SOL 4437 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Desert_View															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4437MH0001900011601131C00	1131	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4437MH0001680011601133C00	1133	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4437MH0001930001601166R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4437MH0001930001601167S00
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4437MH0001680011601143C00	1143	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4437MH0001930001601164R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4437MH0001930001601165S00
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	4437MH0007430011601153C00	1153	15213	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4437MH0001930001601162R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4437MH0001930001601163S00

UPDATED: 31_January_2025

SOL 4439 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Deer_Springs															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4439MH0001900011601169C00	1169	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4439MH0001680011601171C00	1171	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4439MH0002650001601192R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4439MH0002650001601193S00
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4439MH0001680011601181C00	1181	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4439MH0002650001601190R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4439MH0002650001601191S00

SOL 4441 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Coldwater_Canyon

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4441MH0001900011601195C00	1195	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4441MH0003360011601197C00	1197	14149	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4442MH0001930001601238R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4442MH0001930001601239S00
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4441MH0003360011601207C00	1207	14160	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4442MH0001930001601236R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4442MH0001930001601237S00

target named Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode

mhl00866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4441MH0008660011601217C00	1217	14146	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
mhl00867	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 4 cm									
	4441MH0008670011601219C00	1219	14156	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
mhl00868	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 3 cm									
	4441MH0008680011601221C00	1221	14368	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl00869	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm									
	4441MH0008690011601223C00	1223	14668	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5

target named Coldwater_Canyon

mhl00873	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm										
	4441MH0008730011601225C00	1225	14666	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4442MH0001930001601234R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4442MH0001930001601235S00

SOL 4443 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **San_Rafael_Hills** – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4443MH0001900011601241C00	1241	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100168	MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0001680011601243C00	1243	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601320R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601331S00	
mhl100168	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0001680011601253C00	1253	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601328R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601329S00	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0007050011601263C00	1263	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0007050011601265C00	1265	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0007050011601267C00	1267	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4443MH0007430011601269C00	1269	15085	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601326R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601327S00	

target named **Allison_Mine**

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4443MH0008760011601279C00	1279	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601324R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601325S00	
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0003080011601289C00	1289	14068	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601322R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601323S00	
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4443MH0003080011601299C00	1299	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601320R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601321S00	
mhl100176	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm											
	4443MH0001760011601309C00	1309	14842	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4444MH0001710001601318R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4444MH0001710001601319S00	

SOL 4445 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target														
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.														
mhl100371	BAR TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4445MH0003710011601333C00	1333	14372	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100372	CENT TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	4445MH0003720011601335C00	1335	14367	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE – 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET													
	4445MH0003740011601337C00	1337	12962	30.3	28.4	-2.3	2.6	113.6	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6	
	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS													
	4445MH0003740021601338C00	1338	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4445MH0003730011601340C00	1340	13945	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named Zuma_Canyon													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4445MH0001900011601342C00	1342	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4445MH0001680011601344C00	1344	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601403R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601404S00				
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4445MH0001680011601354C00	1354	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601401R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601402S00				

target named Bear_Canyon – after DRT													
mhl100172	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm										
	4445MH0001720011601364C00	1364	13109	21.8	19.9	-1.2	1.3	83.7	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.0
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4445MH0003360011601366C00	1366	13906	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601399R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601400S00				
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4445MH0003360011601376C00	1376	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601397R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601398S00				
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4445MH0008480011601386C00	1386	15050	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601395R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601396S00				

SOL 4447 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Bridge_To_Nowhere** – a 2 x 1 mosaic from 25 cm standoff

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
POSITION 1 OF 2													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00190	4447MH0001900011601406C00	1406	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00168	4447MH0001680011601408C00	1408	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601469R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601470S00													
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00168	4447MH0001680011601418C00	1418	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601467R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601468S00													
POSITION 2 OF 2													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00190	4447MH0001900011601428C00	1428	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6

target named **Aliso_Canyon** – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
CONTEXT VIEW													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
mhli00190	4447MH0001900011601430C00	1430	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00168	4447MH0001680011601432C00	1432	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601465R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601466S00													
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
mhli00168	4447MH0001680011601442C00	1442	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601463R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601464S00													
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
mhli00302	4447MH0003020011601452C00	1452	14697	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601461R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4449MH0002270001601462S00													

UPDATED: 14_February_2025

SOL 4452 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Catalina_Island</i> – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4452MH0001900011601472C00	1472	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4452MH0001680011601474C00	1474	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4452MH0001930001601507R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4452MH0001930001601508S00
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4452MH0001680011601484C00	1484	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4452MH0001930001601505R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4452MH0001930001601506S00
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4452MH0007430011601494C00	1494	15228	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4452MH0001930001601503R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4452MH0001930001601504S00

SOL 4455 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Skyline_Trail															
mhl100876	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4455MH0008760011601510C00	1510	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601665R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601666S00	
mhl100876	CONTEXT STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4455MH0008760011601520C00	1520	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601663R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601664S00	
mhl100166	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0001660011601530C00	1530	14120	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601661R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601662S00	
mhl100166	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0001660011601540C00	1540	14112	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601659R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601660S00	

target named Lake_Arrowhead – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4455MH0001900011601550C00	1550	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601657R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601658S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0003360011601562C00	1552	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601657R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601658S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0003360011601562C00	1562	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601655R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601656S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4455MH0008480011601572C00	1572	15050	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601653R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601654S00	

target named Strawberry_Peak															
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4455MH0003590011601582C00	1582	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601651R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601652S00	
mhl100359	CONTEXT STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4455MH0003590011601592C00	1592	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601649R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601650S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0001820011601602C00	1602	14109	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601647R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601648S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4455MH0001820011601612C00	1612	14112	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601645R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601646S00	

target named Strawberry_Peak – MAHLI proximity mode													
mhl100866	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4455MH0008660011601622C00	1622	14128	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
mhl100867	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 4 cm											
	4455MH0008670011601624C00	1624	14129	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
mhl100868	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 3 cm											
	4455MH0008680011601626C00	1626	14312	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0
mhl100869	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm											
	4455MH0008690011601628C00	1628	14630	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
mhl100870	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm											
	4455MH0008700011601630C00	1630	14813	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3
mhl100871	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4455MH0008710011601632C00	1632	15029	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1

target named Strawberry_Peak															
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	4455MH0007430011601634C00	1634	15037	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4456MH0004580001601643R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4456MH0004580001601644S00	

SOL 4458 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Wheeler_Gorge** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4459MH0001900011601668C00	1668	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4459MH0003360011601670C00	1670	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601741R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601742S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4459MH0003360011601680C00	1680	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601739R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601740S00
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm											
	4459MH0008480011601690C00	1690	14841	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601737R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601738S00

target named **Chumash_Trail** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4459MH0001900011601700C00	1700	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4459MH0003360011601702C00	1702	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601735R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601736S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4459MH0003360011601712C00	1712	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601733R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601734S00
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4459MH0008480011601722C00	1722	15171	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4459MH0001630001601731R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4459MH0001630001601732S00

SOL 4461 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.													
mhl100371	BAR TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4461MH0003710011601744C00	1744	14374	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100372	CENT TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4461MH0003720011601746C00	1746	14369	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE - 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET												
	4461MH0003740011601748C00	1748	12962	30.3	28.4	-2.3	2.6	113.6	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS												
	4461MH0003740021601749C00	1749	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4461MH0003730011601751C00	1751	13946	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named Wellman Divide - quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW												
	4461MH0001900011601753C00	1753	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhl100299	MED RES - STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1												
	4461MH0002990011601755C00	1755	14179	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601808R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601809S00			
mhl100299	MED RES - STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2												
	4461MH0002990011601765C00	1765	14192	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601806R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601807S00			
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3												
	4461MH0007050011601775C00	1775	14180	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4												
	4461MH0007050011601777C00	1777	14169	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
mhl100705	MED RES - RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5												
	4461MH0007050011601779C00	1779	14179	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3

target named Salton Sea													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW												
	4461MH0001900011601781C00	1781	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1												
	4461MH0003360011601783C00	1783	14159	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601804R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601805S00			
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2												
	4461MH0003360011601793C00	1793	14164	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601802R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4462MH0001530001601803S00			

SOL 4464 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Matilija_Poppy															
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4464MH0003590011601811C00	1811	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4464MH0001930001601844R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4464MH0001930001601845S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4464MH0001820011601821C00	1821	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4464MH0001930001601842R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4464MH0001930001601843S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4464MH0001820011601831C00	1831	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4464MH0001930001601840R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4464MH0001930001601841S00	

SOL 4466 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Trippet_Ranch – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4466MH0001900011601847C00	1847	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4466MH0003360011601849C00	1849	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4466MH0001930001601882R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4466MH0001930001601883S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4466MH0003360011601859C00	1859	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4466MH0001930001601880R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4466MH0001930001601881S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4466MH0008640011601869C00	1869	15107	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4466MH0001930001601878R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4466MH0001930001601879S00

UPDATED: 05_March_2025

SOL 4471 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ramona_Trail – after DRT															
mhl00876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4471MH0008760011601885C00	1885	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601930R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4471MH0001530001601931S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4471MH0001680011601895C00	1895	14050	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601928R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4471MH0001530001601929S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4471MH0001680011601905C00	1905	14052	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601926R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4471MH0001530001601927S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4471MH0008640011601915C00	1915	15009	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601924R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4471MH0001530001601925S00	

SOL 4477 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Angeles_Crest

mhl00706	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4477MH0007060011601933C00	1933	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhl00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4477MH0008340011601936C00	1936	14155	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001602007R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001602008S00
mhl00834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4477MH0008340011601947C00	1947	14163	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001602005R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001602006S00

target named Millard_Canyon – a 4 x 1 mosaic

mhl00877	POSITION 1 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4477MH0008770011601958C00	1958	13208	18.2	16.3	-0.9	0.9	71.0	3.1	1608	1198	11.4	8.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001602003R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001602004S00	
mhl00877	POSITION 2 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4477MH0008770011601968C00	1968	13243	17.2	15.3	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	1608	1198	10.8	8.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001602001R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001602002S00	
mhl00877	POSITION 3 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4477MH0008770011601978C00	1978	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001601999R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001602000S00	
mhl00877	POSITION 4 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm											
	4477MH0008770011601988C00	1988	13273	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001601997R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4478MH0007890001601998S00	

SOL 4479 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Stunt_Ranch													
mhl100855	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4479MH0008550011602010C00	2010	12996	27.9	26.0	-1.9	2.2	105.0	7.3	1608	1198	16.9	12.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602127R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602128S00					
mhl100297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4479MH0002970011602020C00	2020	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602125R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602126S00					
mhl100297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4479MH0002970011602030C00	2030	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602123R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602124S00					
mhl100649	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4479MH0006490011602040C00	2040	15099	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602121R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602122S00					
mhl100855	CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4479MH0008550011602050C00	2050	13001	27.5	25.6	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	1608	1198	16.7	12.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602119R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602120S00					
mhl100855	CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4479MH0008550011602060C00	2060	12995	27.9	26.0	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	1608	1198	16.9	12.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602117R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602118S00					

target named Pacifico_Mountain – a 3 x 1 mosaic from 8 cm standoff													
mhl100895	POSITION 1 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 8 cm											
	4479MH0008950011602070C00	2070	13682	9.5	7.6	-0.3	0.3	40.4	0.9	1608	1198	6.5	4.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602115R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602116S00					
mhl100895	POSITION 2 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 8 cm											
	4479MH0008950011602080C00	2080	13629	10.1	8.2	-0.3	0.3	42.5	1.1	1608	1198	6.8	5.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602113R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602114S00					
mhl100895	POSITION 3 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 8 cm											
	4479MH0008950011602090C00	2090	13608	10.4	8.5	-0.3	0.3	43.4	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602111R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602112S00					
mhl100855	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4479MH0008550011602100C00	2100	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602109R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4480MH0003690001602110S00					

SOL 4481 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Yerba Buena Ridge** – a 5 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)		
POSITION 1 OF 5												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 20 cm											
4481MH0008460011602130C00	2130	13339	14.8	12.9	-0.6	0.6	59.0	2.1	1608	1198	9.5	7.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602295R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602296S00	
POSITION 2 OF 5												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 20 cm											
4481MH0008460011602140C00	2140	13252	16.9	15.0	-0.8	0.8	66.5	2.7	1608	1198	10.7	8.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602293R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602294S00	
POSITION 3 OF 5												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 20 cm											
4481MH0008460011602150C00	2150	13120	21.4	19.5	-1.2	1.3	82.1	4.3	1608	1198	13.2	9.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602291R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602292S00	
POSITION 4 OF 5												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 20 cm											
4481MH0008460011602160C00	2160	13094	22.5	20.6	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	1608	1198	13.8	10.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602289R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602290S00	
POSITION 5 OF 5												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 20 cm											
4481MH0008460011602170C00	2170	13095	22.4	20.5	-1.3	1.4	85.9	4.7	1608	1198	13.8	10.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602287R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602288S00	

target named **South Fork**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)		
CONTEXT VIEW												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 25 cm											
4481MH0008550011602180C00	2180	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602285R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602286S00	
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 5 cm											
4481MH0003080011602190C00	2190	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602283R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602284S00	
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 5 cm											
4481MH0003080011602200C00	2200	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602281R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602282S00	
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 15 mm											
4481MH0007960011602210C00	2210	14878	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602279R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602280S00	

target named **Sepulveda Pass**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)		
CONTEXT STEREO-2 – ROTATED OFFSET												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 25 cm											
4481MH0008550011602220C00	2220	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602277R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602278S00	
CONTEXT STEREO-3 – ROTATED OFFSET												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 25 cm											
4481MH0008550011602230C00	2230	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602275R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602276S00	
CONTEXT STEREO-1												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 25 cm											
4481MH0008550011602240C00	2240	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602273R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602274S00	
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 5 cm											
4481MH0006730011602250C00	2250	14100	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602271R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602272S00	
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2												
INTENDED STANDOFF	– 5 cm											
4481MH0006730011602260C00	2260	14157	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602269R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4483MH0007280001602270S00	

SOL 4486 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)			
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
target named Palm_Grove – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4486MH0001900011602298C00	2298	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4486MH0001680011602300C00	2300	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH00008970001602537R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4487MH00008970001602538S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4486MH0001680011602310C00	2310	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH00008970001602535R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4487MH00008970001602536S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4486MH0001680011602320C00	2320	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH00008970001602533R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4487MH00008970001602534S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4486MH0008640011602330C00	2330	14903	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH00008970001602531R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4487MH00008970001602532S00	

Continued on Next Page..

target named **Duna_Vista** - a 8 x 2 mosaic

mhl100896	POSITION 1 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602340C00	2340	13304	15.6	13.7	-0.7	0.7	61.8	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602529R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 2 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602350C00	2350	13315	15.3	13.4	-0.6	0.6	60.9	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602527R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 3 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602360C00	2360	13313	15.4	13.5	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	1608	1198	9.8	7.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602525R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 4 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602370C00	2370	13301	15.7	13.8	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	1608	1198	10.0	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602523R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 5 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602380C00	2380	13301	15.7	13.8	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	1608	1198	10.0	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602521R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 6 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602390C00	2390	13310	15.4	13.5	-0.6	0.7	61.3	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602519R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 7 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602400C00	2400	13305	15.6	13.7	-0.7	0.7	61.7	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602517R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 8 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602410C00	2410	13293	15.9	14.0	-0.7	0.7	62.7	2.4	1608	1198	10.1	7.5
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602515R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 9 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602420C00	2420	13286	16.0	14.1	-0.7	0.7	63.3	2.5	1608	1198	10.2	7.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602513R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 10 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602430C00	2430	13301	15.7	13.8	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	1608	1198	10.0	7.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602511R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 11 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602440C00	2440	13288	16.0	14.1	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	1608	1198	10.2	7.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602509R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 12 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602450C00	2450	13273	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602507R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 13 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602460C00	2460	13265	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602505R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 14 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602470C00	2470	13277	16.3	14.4	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	1608	1198	10.3	7.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602503R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 15 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602480C00	2480	13268	16.5	14.6	-0.7	0.7	64.9	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.8
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602501R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					
mhl100896	POSITION 16 OF 16	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm											
	4486MH0008960011602490C00	2490	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4487MH0001630001602499R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					

SOL 4488 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Solstice_Canyon - after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	4489MH0001900011602540C00	2540	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4489MH0003360011602542C00	2542	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602623R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602624S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4489MH0003360011602552C00	2552	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602619R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602625S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4489MH0003360011602562C00	2562	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602619R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602620S00	
mhl00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4489MH0008480011602572C00	2572	14874	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602617R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602618S00	

target named Black_Oak

mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	4489MH0003590011602582C00	2582	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602615R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602616S00	
mhl00166	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4489MH0001660011602592C00	2592	14342	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602613R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602614S00	
mhl00166	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4489MH0001660011602602C00	2602	14357	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4489MH0001710001602611R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4489MH0001710001602612S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 4355–4488 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 4355, 4359, 4368, 4370, 4372, 4382, 4384, 4386, 4389, 4393, 4416, 4425, 4428, 4431, 4434, 4437, 4439, 4441, 4443, 4445, 4447, 4452, 4455, 4458, 4461, 4464, 4466, 4471, 4477, 4479, 4481, 4486, 4488**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus

position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the

second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the

motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4355 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidote_Peak – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4355MH0001680011404691C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4355MH0002270001104750R00	4750	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4355MH0002270001104751S00	4751	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4355	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4355		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4355MH0001680021404692C00	4692	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4355MH0001680021404693C00	4693	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4355MH0001680021304694C00	4694	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4355MH0001680021304695C00	4695	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4355MH0001680021304696C00	4696	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4355MH0001680021304697C00	4697	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4355MH0001680021304698C00	4698	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4355MH0001680021304699C00	4699	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4355 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidote_Peak – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4355MH0001680011304701C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4355MH0002270001104748R00	4748	MOTOR COUNT:		14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4355MH0002270001104749S00	4749	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4355	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4355		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4355MH0001680021304702C00	4702	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4355MH0001680021304703C00	4703	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4355MH0001680021304704C00	4704	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4355MH0001680021304705C00	4705	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4355MH0001680021304706C00	4706	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4355MH0001680021304707C00	4707	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4355MH0001680021304708C00	4708	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
4355MH0001680021304709C00	4709	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4355 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidote_Peak – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4355MH0007430011304711C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4355MH0002270001104746R00	4746	MOTOR COUNT:		15168	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4355MH0002270001104747S00	4747	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4355	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4355	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4355MH0007430021304712C00	4712	15024	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4355MH0007430021304713C00	4713	15060	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4355MH0007430021304714C00	4714	15096	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
4355MH0007430021304715C00	4715	15132	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4355MH0007430021304716C00	4716	15168	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
4355MH0007430021304717C00	4717	15204	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4355MH0007430021304718C00	4718	15240	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4355MH0007430021304719C00	4719	15276	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4355 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millys_Foot_Path – stereo-1 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4355MH0002240011304723C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4355MH0002270001104744R00	4744	MOTOR COUNT:		14059	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4355MH0002270001104745S00	4745	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4355	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4355	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4355MH0002240021304724C00	4724	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
4355MH0002240021304725C00	4725	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4355MH0002240021304726C00	4726	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4355MH0002240021304727C00	4727	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4355MH0002240021304728C00	4728	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
4355MH0002240021304729C00	4729	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	95	6
4355MH0002240021304730C00	4730	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	63	7
4355MH0002240021304731C00	4731	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4355 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4355MH0002240011304733C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4355MH0002270001104742R00	4742	MOTOR COUNT:		14083	RANGE (cm):		6.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4355MH0002270001104743S00	4743	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4355		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4355
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4355MH0002240021304734C00	4734	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
4355MH0002240021304735C00	4735	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4355MH0002240021204736C00	4736	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4355MH0002240021204737C00	4737	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
4355MH0002240021104738C00	4738	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	127	5
4355MH0002240021104739C00	4739	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	95	6
4355MH0002240021104740C00	4740	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
4355MH0002240021104741C00	4741	14209	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Forester_Pass – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0003360011600004C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600087R00	87	MOTOR COUNT:	13980	RANGE (cm):	7.0			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600088S00	88	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:	12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4360				
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0003360021600005C00	5	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4359MH0003360021600006C00	6	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4359MH0003360021600007C00	7	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4359MH0003360021600008C00	8	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4359MH0003360021600009C00	9	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4359MH0003360021600010C00	10	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4359MH0003360021600011C00	11	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4359MH0003360021600012C00	12	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Forester_Pass – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0003360011600014C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600085R00	85	MOTOR COUNT:	13982	RANGE (cm):	7.0			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600086S00	86	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:	12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4360				
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0003360021600015C00	15	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4359MH0003360021600016C00	16	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4359MH0003360021600017C00	17	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4359MH0003360021600018C00	18	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4359MH0003360021600019C00	19	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4359MH0003360021600020C00	20	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4359MH0003360021600021C00	21	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4359MH0003360021600022C00	22	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Forester_Pass – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0008480011600024C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600083R00	83	MOTOR COUNT:		15020	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600084S00	84	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4360		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0008480021600025C00	25	14924	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
4359MH0008480021600026C00	26	14948	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	223	2
4359MH0008480021600027C00	27	14972	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
4359MH0008480021600028C00	28	14996	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4
4359MH0008480021600029C00	29	15020	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	127	5
4359MH0008480021600030C00	30	15044	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	95	6
4359MH0008480021600031C00	31	15068	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
4359MH0008480021600032C00	32	15092	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mahogany_Creek – stereo-1 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0003360011600036C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600081R00	81	MOTOR COUNT:		14198	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600082S00	82	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4360		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0003360021600037C00	37	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	255	1
4359MH0003360021600038C00	38	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	223	2
4359MH0003360021600039C00	39	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	191	3
4359MH0003360021600040C00	40	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	159	4
4359MH0003360021600041C00	41	14198	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
4359MH0003360021600042C00	42	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
4359MH0003360021600043C00	43	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
4359MH0003360021600044C00	44	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0003360011600046C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600079R00	79	MOTOR COUNT:		14204	RANGE (cm):		5.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600080S00	80	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4360	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0003360021600047C00	47	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	255	1
4359MH0003360021600048C00	48	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	223	2
4359MH0003360021600049C00	49	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	191	3
4359MH0003360021600050C00	50	14192	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
4359MH0003360021600051C00	51	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
4359MH0003360021600052C00	52	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
4359MH0003360021600053C00	53	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
4359MH0003360021600054C00	54	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buttress_Tree - stereo-1 - ~11 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0008920011600056C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600077R00	77	MOTOR COUNT:		13414	RANGE (cm):		13.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600078S00	78	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00892		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4359	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4360	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0008920021600057C00	57	13102	22.13	-1.3	1.4	84.8	4.6	255	1
4359MH0008920021600058C00	58	13180	19.12	-1.0	1.0	74.2	3.5	223	2
4359MH0008920021600059C00	59	13258	16.76	-0.8	0.8	65.9	2.7	191	3
4359MH0008920021600060C00	60	13336	14.85	-0.6	0.6	59.2	2.1	159	4
4359MH0008920021600061C00	61	13414	13.29	-0.5	0.5	53.7	1.7	127	5
4359MH0008920021600062C00	62	13492	11.97	-0.4	0.4	49.0	1.4	95	6
4359MH0008920021600063C00	63	13570	10.86	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	63	7
4359MH0008920021600064C00	64	13648	9.90	-0.3	0.3	41.7	1.0	31	8

UPDATED: 15_November_2024

SOL 4359 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - ~11 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4359MH0008920011600066C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4360MH0001710001600075R00	75	MOTOR COUNT:		13430	RANGE (cm):		13.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4360MH0001710001600076S00	76	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00892		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4359		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4360
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4359MH0008920021600067C00	67	13118	21.45	-1.2	1.3	82.4	4.3	255	1
4359MH0008920021600068C00	68	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	223	2
4359MH0008920021600069C00	69	13274	16.33	-0.7	0.7	64.4	2.5	191	3
4359MH0008920021600070C00	70	13352	14.51	-0.6	0.6	58.0	2.0	159	4
4359MH0008920021600071C00	71	13430	13.00	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	127	5
4359MH0008920021600072C00	72	13508	11.73	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	95	6
4359MH0008920021600073C00	73	13586	10.65	-0.3	0.3	44.4	1.1	63	7
4359MH0008920021600074C00	74	13664	9.72	-0.3	0.3	41.1	1.0	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calaveras – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0003360011600092C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600165R00	165	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600166S00	166	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0003360021600093C00	93	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4368MH0003360021600094C00	94	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4368MH0003360021600095C00	95	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4368MH0003360021600096C00	96	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4368MH0003360021600097C00	97	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4368MH0003360021600098C00	98	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4368MH0003360021600099C00	99	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4368MH0003360021600100C00	100	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calaveras – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0003360011600102C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600163R00	163	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600164S00	164	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0003360021600103C00	103	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4368MH0003360021600104C00	104	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4368MH0003360021600105C00	105	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4368MH0003360021600106C00	106	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4368MH0003360021600107C00	107	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4368MH0003360021600108C00	108	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4368MH0003360021600109C00	109	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4368MH0003360021600110C00	110	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calaveras - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0008640011600112C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600161R00	161	MOTOR COUNT:		15115	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600162S00	162	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0008640021600113C00	113	14995	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
4368MH0008640021600114C00	114	15025	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4368MH0008640021600115C00	115	15055	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4368MH0008640021600116C00	116	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
4368MH0008640021600117C00	117	15115	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4368MH0008640021600118C00	118	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4368MH0008640021600119C00	119	15175	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4368MH0008640021600120C00	120	15205	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Murphys - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0003360011600126C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600159R00	159	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600160S00	160	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0003360021600127C00	127	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4368MH0003360021600128C00	128	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4368MH0003360021600129C00	129	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4368MH0003360021600130C00	130	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4368MH0003360021600131C00	131	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4368MH0003360021600132C00	132	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4368MH0003360021600133C00	133	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4368MH0003360021600134C00	134	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Murphys - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0003360011600136C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600157R00	157	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600158S00	158	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0003360021600137C00	137	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4368MH0003360021600138C00	138	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4368MH0003360021600139C00	139	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4368MH0003360021600140C00	140	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4368MH0003360021600141C00	141	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4368MH0003360021600142C00	142	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4368MH0003360021600143C00	143	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4368MH0003360021600144C00	144	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_November_2024

SOL 4368 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Murphys - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4368MH0008480011600146C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4369MH0001630001600155R00	155	MOTOR COUNT:		15101	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4369MH0001630001600156S00	156	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4368	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4369		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4368MH0008480021600147C00	147	15005	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
4368MH0008480021600148C00	148	15029	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4368MH0008480021600149C00	149	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4368MH0008480021600150C00	150	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
4368MH0008480021600151C00	151	15101	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
4368MH0008480021600152C00	152	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4368MH0008480021600153C00	153	15149	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4368MH0008480021600154C00	154	15173	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - ~20 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008540011600168C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600299R00	299	MOTOR COUNT:		13098	RANGE (cm):	22.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600300S00	300	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008540021600169C00	169	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	255	1
4370MH0008540021600170C00	170	13008	27.08	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	223	2
4370MH0008540021600171C00	171	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	191	3
4370MH0008540021600172C00	172	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	159	4
4370MH0008540021600173C00	173	13098	22.31	-1.3	1.4	85.4	4.7	127	5
4370MH0008540021600174C00	174	13128	21.04	-1.1	1.2	81.0	4.2	95	6
4370MH0008540021600175C00	175	13158	19.89	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.8	63	7
4370MH0008540021600176C00	176	13188	18.85	-0.9	1.0	73.3	3.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - ~20 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008540011600178C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600297R00	297	MOTOR COUNT:		13114	RANGE (cm):	21.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600298S00	298	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008540021600179C00	179	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	255	1
4370MH0008540021600180C00	180	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	223	2
4370MH0008540021600181C00	181	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	191	3
4370MH0008540021600182C00	182	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	159	4
4370MH0008540021600183C00	183	13114	21.61	-1.2	1.3	83.0	4.4	127	5
4370MH0008540021600184C00	184	13144	20.41	-1.1	1.2	78.8	3.9	95	6
4370MH0008540021600185C00	185	13174	19.32	-1.0	1.0	74.9	3.5	63	7
4370MH0008540021600186C00	186	13204	18.33	-0.9	0.9	71.4	3.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - ~19 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008540011600188C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600295R00	295	MOTOR COUNT:		13135	RANGE (cm):	20.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600296S00	296	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008540021600189C00	189	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	255	1
4370MH0008540021600190C00	190	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	223	2
4370MH0008540021600191C00	191	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	191	3
4370MH0008540021600192C00	192	13105	22.00	-1.2	1.4	84.3	4.6	159	4
4370MH0008540021600193C00	193	13135	20.76	-1.1	1.2	80.0	4.1	127	5
4370MH0008540021600194C00	194	13165	19.64	-1.0	1.1	76.0	3.6	95	6
4370MH0008540021600195C00	195	13195	18.62	-0.9	1.0	72.4	3.3	63	7
4370MH0008540021600196C00	196	13225	17.69	-0.8	0.9	69.2	3.0	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - ~18 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008540011600198C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600293R00	293	MOTOR COUNT:		13150	RANGE (cm):	20.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600294S00	294	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008540021600199C00	199	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	255	1
4370MH0008540021600200C00	200	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	223	2
4370MH0008540021600201C00	201	13090	22.67	-1.3	1.4	86.7	4.8	191	3
4370MH0008540021600202C00	202	13120	21.36	-1.2	1.3	82.1	4.3	159	4
4370MH0008540021600203C00	203	13150	20.19	-1.1	1.1	78.0	3.9	127	5
4370MH0008540021600204C00	204	13180	19.12	-1.0	1.0	74.2	3.5	95	6
4370MH0008540021600205C00	205	13210	18.15	-0.9	0.9	70.8	3.1	63	7
4370MH0008540021600206C00	206	13240	17.26	-0.8	0.8	67.6	2.8	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - ~18 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008540011600208C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600291R00	291	MOTOR COUNT:		13164	RANGE (cm):	19.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600292S00	292	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008540021600209C00	209	13044	24.97	-1.6	1.8	94.8	5.9	255	1
4370MH0008540021600210C00	210	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	223	2
4370MH0008540021600211C00	211	13104	22.04	-1.3	1.4	84.5	4.6	191	3
4370MH0008540021600212C00	212	13134	20.80	-1.1	1.2	80.1	4.1	159	4
4370MH0008540021600213C00	213	13164	19.68	-1.0	1.1	76.2	3.7	127	5
4370MH0008540021600214C00	214	13194	18.65	-0.9	1.0	72.6	3.3	95	6
4370MH0008540021600215C00	215	13224	17.72	-0.8	0.9	69.3	3.0	63	7
4370MH0008540021600216C00	216	13254	16.87	-0.8	0.8	66.3	2.7	31	8

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SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - ~18 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008460011600218C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600289R00	289	MOTOR COUNT:		13164	RANGE (cm):	19.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600290S00	290	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0008460021600219C00	219	12948	31.42	-2.5	2.9	117.5	9.4	255	1
4370MH0008460021600220C00	220	13002	27.46	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	223	2
4370MH0008460021600221C00	221	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	191	3
4370MH0008460021600222C00	222	13110	21.78	-1.2	1.3	83.6	4.5	159	4
4370MH0008460021600223C00	223	13164	19.68	-1.0	1.1	76.2	3.7	127	5
4370MH0008460021600224C00	224	13218	17.90	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	95	6
4370MH0008460021600225C00	225	13272	16.39	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	63	7
4370MH0008460021600226C00	226	13326	15.08	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 7 of 8 - ~18 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008460011600228C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4371MH0004490001600287R00		287		MOTOR COUNT:		13158		RANGE (cm): 19.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4371MH0004490001600288S00		288		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		21-Nov-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4370		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4370MH0008460021600229C00	229	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	255	1		
4370MH0008460021600230C00	230	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	223	2		
4370MH0008460021600231C00	231	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	191	3		
4370MH0008460021600232C00	232	13104	22.04	-1.3	1.4	84.5	4.6	159	4		
4370MH0008460021600233C00	233	13158	19.89	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.8	127	5		
4370MH0008460021600234C00	234	13212	18.08	-0.9	0.9	70.6	3.1	95	6		
4370MH0008460021600235C00	235	13266	16.54	-0.7	0.8	65.1	2.6	63	7		
4370MH0008460021600236C00	236	13320	15.21	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	31	8		

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SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 8 of 8 - ~18 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0008460011600238C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4371MH0004490001600285R00		285		MOTOR COUNT:		13155		RANGE (cm): 20.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4371MH0004490001600286S00		286		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		21-Nov-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4370		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4370MH0008460021600239C00	239	12939	32.19	-2.6	3.0	120.2	9.8	255	1		
4370MH0008460021600240C00	240	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	223	2		
4370MH0008460021600241C00	241	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	191	3		
4370MH0008460021600242C00	242	13101	22.17	-1.3	1.4	85.0	4.6	159	4		
4370MH0008460021600243C00	243	13155	20.00	-1.0	1.1	77.3	3.8	127	5		
4370MH0008460021600244C00	244	13209	18.18	-0.9	0.9	70.9	3.1	95	6		
4370MH0008460021600245C00	245	13263	16.62	-0.7	0.8	65.4	2.6	63	7		
4370MH0008460021600246C00	246	13317	15.28	-0.6	0.6	60.7	2.2	31	8		

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SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buttermilk - APXS spot 3 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0002240011600250C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600283R00	283	MOTOR COUNT:		13940	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600284S00	284	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0002240021600251C00	251	13772	8.62	-0.2	0.2	37.3	0.8	255	1
4370MH0002240021600252C00	252	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
4370MH0002240021600253C00	253	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
4370MH0002240021600254C00	254	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
4370MH0002240021600255C00	255	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
4370MH0002240021600256C00	256	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
4370MH0002240021600257C00	257	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4370MH0002240021600258C00	258	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buttermilk - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0002240011600260C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600281R00	281	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600282S00	282	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0002240021600261C00	261	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	255	1
4370MH0002240021600262C00	262	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
4370MH0002240021600263C00	263	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
4370MH0002240021600264C00	264	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4370MH0002240021600265C00	265	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4370MH0002240021600266C00	266	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4370MH0002240021600267C00	267	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4370MH0002240021600268C00	268	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4370 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Buttermilk – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4370MH0002240011600270C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4371MH0004490001600279R00	279	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4371MH0004490001600280S00	280	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00449	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4370	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4371	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4370MH0002240021600271C00	271	13820	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
4370MH0002240021600272C00	272	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
4370MH0002240021600273C00	273	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
4370MH0002240021600274C00	274	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4370MH0002240021600275C00	275	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4370MH0002240021600276C00	276	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4370MH0002240021600277C00	277	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4370MH0002240021600278C00	278	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mount_Tallac - stereo-1 - ~10 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0002910011600302C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600373R00	373	MOTOR COUNT:		13503	RANGE (cm):	11.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600374S00	374	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00291	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0002910021600303C00	303	13359	14.36	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	255	1
4372MH0002910021600304C00	304	13395	13.64	-0.5	0.5	54.9	1.8	223	2
4372MH0002910021600305C00	305	13431	12.98	-0.5	0.5	52.6	1.7	191	3
4372MH0002910021600306C00	306	13467	12.37	-0.4	0.4	50.4	1.5	159	4
4372MH0002910021600307C00	307	13503	11.80	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	127	5
4372MH0002910021600308C00	308	13539	11.28	-0.4	0.4	46.6	1.3	95	6
4372MH0002910021600309C00	309	13575	10.79	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	63	7
4372MH0002910021600310C00	310	13611	10.34	-0.3	0.3	43.3	1.1	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mount_Tallac - stereo-2 - ~10 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0002910011600312C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600371R00	371	MOTOR COUNT:		13503	RANGE (cm):	11.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600372S00	372	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00291	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0002910021600313C00	313	13359	14.36	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	255	1
4372MH0002910021600314C00	314	13395	13.64	-0.5	0.5	54.9	1.8	223	2
4372MH0002910021600315C00	315	13431	12.98	-0.5	0.5	52.6	1.7	191	3
4372MH0002910021600316C00	316	13467	12.37	-0.4	0.4	50.4	1.5	159	4
4372MH0002910021600317C00	317	13503	11.80	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	127	5
4372MH0002910021600318C00	318	13539	11.28	-0.4	0.4	46.6	1.3	95	6
4372MH0002910021600319C00	319	13575	10.79	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	63	7
4372MH0002910021600320C00	320	13611	10.34	-0.3	0.3	43.3	1.1	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cienega_Mirth - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0003360011600324C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600369R00	369	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600370S00	370	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0003360021600325C00	325	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4372MH0003360021600326C00	326	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4372MH0003360021600327C00	327	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4372MH0003360021600328C00	328	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4372MH0003360021600329C00	329	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4372MH0003360021600330C00	330	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4372MH0003360021600331C00	331	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4372MH0003360021600332C00	332	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cienega_Mirth - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0003360011600334C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600367R00	367	MOTOR COUNT:		14023	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600368S00	368	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0003360021600335C00	335	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4372MH0003360021600336C00	336	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4372MH0003360021600337C00	337	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4372MH0003360021600338C00	338	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4372MH0003360021600339C00	339	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4372MH0003360021600340C00	340	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4372MH0003360021600341C00	341	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4372MH0003360021600342C00	342	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cienega_Mirth - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0008480011600344C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600365R00	365	MOTOR COUNT:		15162	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600366S00	366	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0008480021600345C00	345	15066	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4372MH0008480021600346C00	346	15090	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4372MH0008480021600347C00	347	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3
4372MH0008480021600348C00	348	15138	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
4372MH0008480021600349C00	349	15162	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4372MH0008480021600350C00	350	15186	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4372MH0008480021600351C00	351	15210	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
4372MH0008480021600352C00	352	15234	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_December_2024

SOL 4372 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cienega_Mirth - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4372MH0003360011600354C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4374MH0001630001600363R00	363	MOTOR COUNT:		14021	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4374MH0001630001600364S00	364	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4372	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4374		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4372MH0003360021600355C00	355	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4372MH0003360021600356C00	356	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4372MH0003360021600357C00	357	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4372MH0003360021600358C00	358	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4372MH0003360021600359C00	359	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4372MH0003360021600360C00	360	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
4372MH0003360021600361C00	361	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4372MH0003360021600362C00	362	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_December_2024

SOL 4382 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronet_Lake – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4382MH0008650011600376C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4382MH0001530001600435R00	435	MOTOR COUNT:		13015	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4382MH0001530001600436S00	436	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4382	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4382		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4382MH0008650021600377C00	377	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	255	1
4382MH0008650021600378C00	378	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	223	2
4382MH0008650021600379C00	379	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	191	3
4382MH0008650021600380C00	380	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	159	4
4382MH0008650021600381C00	381	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5
4382MH0008650021600382C00	382	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	95	6
4382MH0008650021600383C00	383	13063	23.97	-1.5	1.6	91.3	5.4	63	7
4382MH0008650021600384C00	384	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	31	8

UPDATED: 05_December_2024

SOL 4382 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronet_Lake – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4382MH0002240011600386C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4382MH0001530001600433R00	433	MOTOR COUNT:		13972	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4382MH0001530001600434S00	434	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4382	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4382		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4382MH0002240021600387C00	387	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
4382MH0002240021600388C00	388	13846	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	223	2
4382MH0002240021600389C00	389	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	191	3
4382MH0002240021600390C00	390	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
4382MH0002240021600391C00	391	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
4382MH0002240021600392C00	392	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4382MH0002240021600393C00	393	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4382MH0002240021600394C00	394	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_December_2024

SOL 4382 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronet_Lake – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4382MH0002240011600396C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4382MH0001530001600431R00	431	MOTOR COUNT:		13964	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4382MH0001530001600432S00	432	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4382	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4382		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4382MH0002240021600397C00	397	13796	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	255	1
4382MH0002240021600398C00	398	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
4382MH0002240021600399C00	399	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
4382MH0002240021600400C00	400	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
4382MH0002240021600401C00	401	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
4382MH0002240021600402C00	402	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4382MH0002240021600403C00	403	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4382MH0002240021600404C00	404	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_December_2024

SOL 4382 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coronet_Lake – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4382MH0008380011600406C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4382MH0001530001600429R00	429	MOTOR COUNT:		15012	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4382MH0001530001600430S00	430	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00838	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4382	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4382		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4382MH0008380021600407C00	407	14748	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	255	1
4382MH0008380021600408C00	408	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
4382MH0008380021600409C00	409	14880	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	191	3
4382MH0008380021600410C00	410	14946	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4
4382MH0008380021600411C00	411	15012	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	127	5
4382MH0008380021600412C00	412	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6
4382MH0008380021600413C00	413	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4382MH0008380021600414C00	414	15210	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Placerville - ~8 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008520011600441C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600535R00	535	MOTOR COUNT:		13635	RANGE (cm):	10.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600536S00	536	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00852	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008520031600443C00	443	13515	11.63	-0.4	0.4	47.8	1.4	255	1
4384MH0008520031600444C00	444	13545	11.20	-0.4	0.4	46.3	1.3	223	2
4384MH0008520031600445C00	445	13575	10.79	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	191	3
4384MH0008520031600446C00	446	13605	10.41	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	159	4
4384MH0008520031600447C00	447	13635	10.05	-0.3	0.3	42.3	1.0	127	5
4384MH0008520031600448C00	448	13665	9.71	-0.3	0.3	41.1	1.0	95	6
4384MH0008520031600449C00	449	13695	9.38	-0.3	0.3	39.9	0.9	63	7
4384MH0008520031600450C00	450	13725	9.07	-0.3	0.2	38.8	0.9	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008550011600452C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600533R00	533	MOTOR COUNT:		12965	RANGE (cm):	30.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600534S00	534	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008550021600453C00	453	12845	42.85	-4.4	5.6	157.8	17.6	255	1
4384MH0008550021600454C00	454	12875	38.80	-3.7	4.5	143.5	14.4	223	2
4384MH0008550021600455C00	455	12905	35.41	-3.1	3.7	131.6	11.9	191	3
4384MH0008550021600456C00	456	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	159	4
4384MH0008550021600457C00	457	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	127	5
4384MH0008550021600458C00	458	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	95	6
4384MH0008550021600459C00	459	13025	26.04	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	63	7
4384MH0008550021600460C00	460	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - ~65 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0001520011600462C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600531R00	531	MOTOR COUNT:		13812	RANGE (cm):	8.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600532S00	532	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0001520021600463C00	463	13620	10.23	-0.3	0.3	42.9	1.1	255	1
4384MH0001520021600464C00	464	13668	9.67	-0.3	0.3	41.0	1.0	223	2
4384MH0001520021600465C00	465	13716	9.16	-0.3	0.3	39.2	0.9	191	3
4384MH0001520021600466C00	466	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	159	4
4384MH0001520021600467C00	467	13812	8.26	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	127	5
4384MH0001520021600468C00	468	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	95	6
4384MH0001520021600469C00	469	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	63	7
4384MH0001520021600470C00	470	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - ~10 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0001520011600472C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600529R00	529	MOTOR COUNT:		13478	RANGE (cm):	12.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600530S00	530	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0001520021600473C00	473	13286	16.03	-0.7	0.7	63.3	2.5	255	1
4384MH0001520021600474C00	474	13334	14.90	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	223	2
4384MH0001520021600475C00	475	13382	13.89	-0.5	0.5	55.8	1.9	191	3
4384MH0001520021600476C00	476	13430	13.00	-0.5	0.5	52.7	1.7	159	4
4384MH0001520021600477C00	477	13478	12.19	-0.4	0.4	49.8	1.5	127	5
4384MH0001520021600478C00	478	13526	11.47	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	95	6
4384MH0001520021600479C00	479	13574	10.80	-0.3	0.3	44.9	1.2	63	7
4384MH0001520021600480C00	480	13622	10.20	-0.3	0.3	42.8	1.1	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008550011600482C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600527R00	527	MOTOR COUNT:		12962	RANGE (cm):	30.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600528S00	528	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008550021600483C00	483	12842	43.30	-4.5	5.7	159.3	18.0	255	1
4384MH0008550021600484C00	484	12872	39.17	-3.7	4.6	144.8	14.6	223	2
4384MH0008550021600485C00	485	12902	35.73	-3.1	3.8	132.7	12.1	191	3
4384MH0008550021600486C00	486	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	159	4
4384MH0008550021600487C00	487	12962	30.30	-2.3	2.7	113.6	8.7	127	5
4384MH0008550021600488C00	488	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	95	6
4384MH0008550021600489C00	489	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	63	7
4384MH0008550021600490C00	490	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008550011600492C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600525R00	525	MOTOR COUNT:		12964	RANGE (cm):	30.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600526S00	526	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008550021600493C00	493	12844	43.00	-4.5	5.6	158.3	17.7	255	1
4384MH0008550021600494C00	494	12874	38.92	-3.7	4.5	143.9	14.5	223	2
4384MH0008550021600495C00	495	12904	35.52	-3.1	3.7	131.9	12.0	191	3
4384MH0008550021600496C00	496	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	159	4
4384MH0008550021600497C00	497	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	127	5
4384MH0008550021600498C00	498	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	95	6
4384MH0008550021600499C00	499	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	63	7
4384MH0008550021600500C00	500	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008550011600502C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600523R00	523	MOTOR COUNT:		12968	RANGE (cm):	29.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600524S00	524	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008550021600503C00	503	12848	42.41	-4.3	5.5	156.2	17.2	255	1
4384MH0008550021600504C00	504	12878	38.44	-3.6	4.4	142.2	14.1	223	2
4384MH0008550021600505C00	505	12908	35.11	-3.0	3.6	130.5	11.7	191	3
4384MH0008550021600506C00	506	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	159	4
4384MH0008550021600507C00	507	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	127	5
4384MH0008550021600508C00	508	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	95	6
4384MH0008550021600509C00	509	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	63	7
4384MH0008550021600510C00	510	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_December_2024

SOL 4384 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - ~28 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4384MH0008550011600512C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4384MH0008930001600521R00	521	MOTOR COUNT:		12965	RANGE (cm):	30.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4384MH0008930001600522S00	522	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00893	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4384	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4384		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4384MH0008550021600513C00	513	12845	42.85	-4.4	5.6	157.8	17.6	255	1
4384MH0008550021600514C00	514	12875	38.80	-3.7	4.5	143.5	14.4	223	2
4384MH0008550021600515C00	515	12905	35.41	-3.1	3.7	131.6	11.9	191	3
4384MH0008550021600516C00	516	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	159	4
4384MH0008550021600517C00	517	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	127	5
4384MH0008550021600518C00	518	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	95	6
4384MH0008550021600519C00	519	13025	26.04	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	63	7
4384MH0008550021600520C00	520	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Icehouse_Canyon - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0008760011600547C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600618R00	618	MOTOR COUNT:		13021	RANGE (cm):	26.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600619S00	619	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4387		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0008760021600548C00	548	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	255	1
4386MH0008760021600549C00	549	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	223	2
4386MH0008760021600550C00	550	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	191	3
4386MH0008760021600551C00	551	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	159	4
4386MH0008760021600552C00	552	13021	26.28	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	127	5
4386MH0008760021600553C00	553	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	95	6
4386MH0008760021600554C00	554	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	63	7
4386MH0008760021600555C00	555	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0001520011600557C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600616R00	616	MOTOR COUNT:		14189	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600617S00	617	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4387		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0001520021600558C00	558	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4386MH0001520021600559C00	559	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	223	2
4386MH0001520021600560C00	560	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
4386MH0001520021600561C00	561	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4386MH0001520021600562C00	562	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
4386MH0001520021600563C00	563	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4386MH0001520021600564C00	564	14285	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	63	7
4386MH0001520021600565C00	565	14333	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0001520011600567C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600614R00	614	MOTOR COUNT:		14204	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600615S00	615	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4387		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0001520021600568C00	568	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
4386MH0001520021600569C00	569	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4386MH0001520021600570C00	570	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4386MH0001520021600571C00	571	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	159	4
4386MH0001520021600572C00	572	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	127	5
4386MH0001520021600573C00	573	14252	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
4386MH0001520021600574C00	574	14300	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	63	7
4386MH0001520021600575C00	575	14348	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunland - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0003360011600579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600612R00	612	MOTOR COUNT:		14027	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600613S00	613	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4387		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0003360021600580C00	580	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4386MH0003360021600581C00	581	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4386MH0003360021600582C00	582	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4386MH0003360021600583C00	583	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4386MH0003360021600584C00	584	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4386MH0003360021600585C00	585	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4386MH0003360021600586C00	586	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4386MH0003360021600587C00	587	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunland - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0003360011600589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600610R00	610	MOTOR COUNT:	14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600611S00	611	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4387			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0003360021600590C00	590	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4386MH0003360021600591C00	591	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4386MH0003360021600592C00	592	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4386MH0003360021600593C00	593	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4386MH0003360021600594C00	594	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4386MH0003360021600595C00	595	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4386MH0003360021600596C00	596	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4386MH0003360021600597C00	597	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4386 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sunland - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4386MH0008480011600599C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4387MH0001630001600608R00	608	MOTOR COUNT:	14918	RANGE (cm):	3.2			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4387MH0001630001600609S00	609	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4386	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4387			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4386MH0008480021600600C00	600	14822	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
4386MH0008480021600601C00	601	14846	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	223	2
4386MH0008480021600602C00	602	14870	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	191	3
4386MH0008480021600603C00	603	14894	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	159	4
4386MH0008480021600604C00	604	14918	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	127	5
4386MH0008480021600605C00	605	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	95	6
4386MH0008480021600606C00	606	14966	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	63	7
4386MH0008480021600607C00	607	14990	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4389 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4389MH0001680011600623C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4389MH0001930001600656R00	656	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4389MH0001930001600657S00	657	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4389	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4389		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4389MH0001680021600624C00	624	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4389MH0001680021600625C00	625	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4389MH0001680021600626C00	626	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4389MH0001680021600627C00	627	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4389MH0001680021600628C00	628	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4389MH0001680021600629C00	629	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4389MH0001680021600630C00	630	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4389MH0001680021600631C00	631	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_December_2024

SOL 4389 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4389MH0001680011600633C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4389MH0001930001600654R00	654	MOTOR COUNT:		14043	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4389MH0001930001600655S00	655	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4389	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4389		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4389MH0001680021600634C00	634	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4389MH0001680021600635C00	635	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4389MH0001680021600636C00	636	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4389MH0001680021600637C00	637	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4389MH0001680021600638C00	638	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4389MH0001680021600639C00	639	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4389MH0001680021600640C00	640	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4389MH0001680021600641C00	641	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4389 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cerro_Negro – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4389MH0007430011600643C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4389MH0001930001600652R00	652	MOTOR COUNT:		15097	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4389MH0001930001600653S00	653	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4389	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4389	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4389MH0007430021600644C00	644	14953	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1
4389MH0007430021600645C00	645	14989	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	223	2
4389MH0007430021600646C00	646	15025	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
4389MH0007430021600647C00	647	15061	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
4389MH0007430021600648C00	648	15097	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
4389MH0007430021600649C00	649	15133	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4389MH0007430021600650C00	650	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4389MH0007430021600651C00	651	15205	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Triunfo_Canyon – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0001680011600663C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4394MH0001630001600734R00		734		MOTOR COUNT:		13994		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600735S00		735		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Dec-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4393		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4393MH0001680021600664C00	664	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1		
4393MH0001680021600665C00	665	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2		
4393MH0001680021600666C00	666	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3		
4393MH0001680021600667C00	667	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4		
4393MH0001680021600668C00	668	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5		
4393MH0001680021600669C00	669	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6		
4393MH0001680021600670C00	670	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7		
4393MH0001680021600671C00	671	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Triunfo_Canyon – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0001680011600673C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4394MH0001630001600732R00		732		MOTOR COUNT:		13995		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4394MH0001630001600733S00		733		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Dec-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4393		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4393MH0001680021600674C00	674	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1		
4393MH0001680021600675C00	675	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2		
4393MH0001680021600676C00	676	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3		
4393MH0001680021600677C00	677	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4		
4393MH0001680021600678C00	678	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5		
4393MH0001680021600679C00	679	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6		
4393MH0001680021600680C00	680	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7		
4393MH0001680021600681C00	681	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Triunfo_Canyon – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0008640011600683C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4394MH0001630001600730R00	730	MOTOR COUNT:		15088	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4394MH0001630001600731S00	731	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4393	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4393MH0008640021600684C00	684	14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
4393MH0008640021600685C00	685	14998	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
4393MH0008640021600686C00	686	15028	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
4393MH0008640021600687C00	687	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
4393MH0008640021600688C00	688	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4393MH0008640021600689C00	689	15118	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4393MH0008640021600690C00	690	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4393MH0008640021600691C00	691	15178	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Calabajas_Peak – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0003360011600695C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4394MH0001630001600728R00	728	MOTOR COUNT:		14032	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4394MH0001630001600729S00	729	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Dec-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4393	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4393MH0003360021600696C00	696	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4393MH0003360021600697C00	697	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
4393MH0003360021600698C00	698	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4393MH0003360021600699C00	699	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4393MH0003360021600700C00	700	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4393MH0003360021600701C00	701	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4393MH0003360021600702C00	702	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4393MH0003360021600703C00	703	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calabaras_Peak – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0003360011600705C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4394MH0001630001600726R00	726	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4394MH0001630001600727S00	727	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4393	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4393MH0003360021600706C00	706	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
4393MH0003360021600707C00	707	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4393MH0003360021600708C00	708	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4393MH0003360021600709C00	709	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4393MH0003360021600710C00	710	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4393MH0003360021600711C00	711	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4393MH0003360021600712C00	712	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4393MH0003360021600713C00	713	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 18_December_2024

SOL 4393 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calabaras_Peak – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4393MH0008480011600715C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4394MH0001630001600724R00	724	MOTOR COUNT:		15207	RANGE (cm):	2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4394MH0001630001600725S00	725	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Dec-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4393	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4394		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4393MH0008480021600716C00	716	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1
4393MH0008480021600717C00	717	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4393MH0008480021600718C00	718	15159	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
4393MH0008480021600719C00	719	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
4393MH0008480021600720C00	720	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
4393MH0008480021600721C00	721	15231	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
4393MH0008480021600722C00	722	15255	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4393MH0008480021600723C00	723	15279	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2025

SOL 4416 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4416MH0003360011600739C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4417MH0002270001600798R00	798	MOTOR COUNT:		13970	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4417MH0002270001600799S00	799	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4416	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4417	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4416MH0003360021600740C00	740	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4416MH0003360021600741C00	741	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4416MH0003360021600742C00	742	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4416MH0003360021600743C00	743	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4416MH0003360021600744C00	744	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
4416MH0003360021600745C00	745	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
4416MH0003360021600746C00	746	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
4416MH0003360021600747C00	747	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2025

SOL 4416 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4416MH0003360011600749C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4417MH0002270001600796R00	796	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4417MH0002270001600797S00	797	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4416	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4417	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4416MH0003360021600750C00	750	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4416MH0003360021600751C00	751	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4416MH0003360021600752C00	752	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4416MH0003360021600753C00	753	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4416MH0003360021600754C00	754	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4416MH0003360021600755C00	755	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4416MH0003360021600756C00	756	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4416MH0003360021600757C00	757	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2025

SOL 4416 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Winter_Creek - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4416MH0003360011600761C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4417MH0002270001600794R00	794	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4417MH0002270001600795S00	795	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4416	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4417		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4416MH0003360021600762C00	762	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4416MH0003360021600763C00	763	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4416MH0003360021600764C00	764	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4416MH0003360021600765C00	765	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4416MH0003360021600766C00	766	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4416MH0003360021600767C00	767	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4416MH0003360021600768C00	768	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4416MH0003360021600769C00	769	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2025

SOL 4416 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Winter_Creek - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4416MH0003360011600771C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4417MH0002270001600792R00	792	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4417MH0002270001600793S00	793	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4416	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4417		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4416MH0003360021600772C00	772	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4416MH0003360021600773C00	773	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4416MH0003360021600774C00	774	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4416MH0003360021600775C00	775	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4416MH0003360021600776C00	776	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4416MH0003360021600777C00	777	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4416MH0003360021600778C00	778	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4416MH0003360021600779C00	779	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_January_2025

SOL 4416 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Winter_Creek - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4416MH0008480011600781C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4417MH0002270001600790R00	790	MOTOR COUNT:		15058	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4417MH0002270001600791S00	791	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4416	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4417	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4416MH0008480021600782C00	782	14962	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	255	1
4416MH0008480021600783C00	783	14986	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	223	2
4416MH0008480021600784C00	784	15010	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
4416MH0008480021600785C00	785	15034	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
4416MH0008480021600786C00	786	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4416MH0008480021600787C00	787	15082	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6
4416MH0008480021600788C00	788	15106	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7
4416MH0008480021600789C00	789	15130	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 27_January_2025

SOL 4425 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rancho_Potrero - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4425MH0001680011600803C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4425MH0002270001600860R00	860	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4425MH0002270001600861S00	861	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4425	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4425	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4425MH0001680021600804C00	804	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4425MH0001680021600805C00	805	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4425MH0001680021600806C00	806	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4425MH0001680021600807C00	807	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4425MH0001680021600808C00	808	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4425MH0001680021600809C00	809	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4425MH0001680021600810C00	810	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4425MH0001680021600811C00	811	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4425 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rancho_Potrero - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4425MH0001680011600813C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4425MH0002270001600858R00	858	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4425MH0002270001600859S00	859	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4425	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4425	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4425MH0001680021600814C00	814	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4425MH0001680021600815C00	815	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4425MH0001680021600816C00	816	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4425MH0001680021600817C00	817	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4425MH0001680021600818C00	818	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4425MH0001680021600819C00	819	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4425MH0001680021600820C00	820	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4425MH0001680021600821C00	821	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4425 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rancho_Potrero - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4425MH0007430011600823C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4425MH0002270001600856R00		856		MOTOR COUNT:		15212		RANGE (cm): 2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600857S00		857		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		16-Jan-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4425		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4425	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4425MH0007430021600824C00	824	15068	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1		
4425MH0007430021600825C00	825	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2		
4425MH0007430021600826C00	826	15140	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3		
4425MH0007430021600827C00	827	15176	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	159	4		
4425MH0007430021600828C00	828	15212	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5		
4425MH0007430021600829C00	829	15248	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	95	6		
4425MH0007430021600830C00	830	15284	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7		
4425MH0007430021600831C00	831	15320	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4425 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - ~18 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4425MH0008940011600833C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4425MH0002270001600854R00		854		MOTOR COUNT:		13156		RANGE (cm): 20.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4425MH0002270001600855S00		855		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00894		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		16-Jan-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4425		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4425	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4425MH0008940021600834C00	834	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	255	1		
4425MH0008940021600835C00	835	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	223	2		
4425MH0008940021600836C00	836	13072	23.52	-1.4	1.6	89.7	5.2	191	3		
4425MH0008940021600837C00	837	13114	21.61	-1.2	1.3	83.0	4.4	159	4		
4425MH0008940021600838C00	838	13156	19.96	-1.0	1.1	77.2	3.8	127	5		
4425MH0008940021600839C00	839	13198	18.52	-0.9	1.0	72.1	3.3	95	6		
4425MH0008940021600840C00	840	13240	17.26	-0.8	0.8	67.6	2.8	63	7		
4425MH0008940021600841C00	841	13282	16.13	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	31	8		

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SOL 4425 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - ~18 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4425MH0008940011600843C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4425MH0002270001600852R00	852	MOTOR COUNT:		13161	RANGE (cm):		19.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4425MH0002270001600853S00	853	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00894		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jan-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4425		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4425
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4425MH0008940021600844C00	844	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	255	1
4425MH0008940021600845C00	845	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	223	2
4425MH0008940021600846C00	846	13077	23.28	-1.4	1.5	88.8	5.1	191	3
4425MH0008940021600847C00	847	13119	21.41	-1.2	1.3	82.2	4.3	159	4
4425MH0008940021600848C00	848	13161	19.78	-1.0	1.1	76.5	3.7	127	5
4425MH0008940021600849C00	849	13203	18.36	-0.9	0.9	71.5	3.2	95	6
4425MH0008940021600850C00	850	13245	17.11	-0.8	0.8	67.1	2.8	63	7
4425MH0008940021600851C00	851	13287	16.00	-0.7	0.7	63.2	2.5	31	8

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SOL 4428 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4428MH0001680011600887C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4429MH0002270001600946R00	946	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600947S00	947	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4428	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4429	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4428MH0001680021600888C00	888	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4428MH0001680021600889C00	889	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4428MH0001680021600890C00	890	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4428MH0001680021600891C00	891	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4428MH0001680021600892C00	892	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4428MH0001680021600893C00	893	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4428MH0001680021600894C00	894	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4428MH0001680021600895C00	895	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4428 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4428MH0001680011600897C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4429MH0002270001600944R00	944	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600945S00	945	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4428	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4429	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4428MH0001680021600898C00	898	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
4428MH0001680021600899C00	899	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4428MH0001680021600900C00	900	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4428MH0001680021600901C00	901	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4428MH0001680021600902C00	902	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4428MH0001680021600903C00	903	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4428MH0001680021600904C00	904	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4428MH0001680021600905C00	905	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4428 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Idlehour - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4428MH0003360011600909C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4429MH0002270001600942R00	942	MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600943S00	943	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4428	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4429	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4428MH0003360021600910C00	910	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4428MH0003360021600911C00	911	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4428MH0003360021600912C00	912	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4428MH0003360021600913C00	913	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4428MH0003360021600914C00	914	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4428MH0003360021600915C00	915	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4428MH0003360021600916C00	916	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4428MH0003360021600917C00	917	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4428 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Idlehour - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4428MH0003360011600919C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4429MH0002270001600940R00	940	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600941S00	941	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4428	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4429	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4428MH0003360021600920C00	920	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4428MH0003360021600921C00	921	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4428MH0003360021600922C00	922	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4428MH0003360021600923C00	923	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4428MH0003360021600924C00	924	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4428MH0003360021600925C00	925	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4428MH0003360021600926C00	926	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4428MH0003360021600927C00	927	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4428 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Idlehour - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4428MH0008480011600929C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4429MH0002270001600938R00	938	MOTOR COUNT:		15167	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4429MH0002270001600939S00	939	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4428	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4429	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4428MH0008480021600930C00	930	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4428MH0008480021600931C00	931	15095	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4428MH0008480021600932C00	932	15119	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4428MH0008480021600933C00	933	15143	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
4428MH0008480021600934C00	934	15167	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
4428MH0008480021600935C00	935	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
4428MH0008480021600936C00	936	15215	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
4428MH0008480021600937C00	937	15239	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pleasant_View_Ridge - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0008760011600949C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4432MH0001630001601020R00	1020	MOTOR COUNT:		13012	RANGE (cm):	26.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4432MH0001630001601021S00	1021	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4431MH0008760021600950C00	950	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	255	1
4431MH0008760021600951C00	951	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	223	2
4431MH0008760021600952C00	952	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	191	3
4431MH0008760021600953C00	953	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	159	4
4431MH0008760021600954C00	954	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	127	5
4431MH0008760021600955C00	955	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	95	6
4431MH0008760021600956C00	956	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	63	7
4431MH0008760021600957C00	957	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	31	8

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SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0003060011600959C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4432MH0001630001601018R00	1018	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4432MH0001630001601019S00	1019	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4431MH0003060021600960C00	960	13777	8.58	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	255	1
4431MH0003060021600961C00	961	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
4431MH0003060021600962C00	962	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
4431MH0003060021600963C00	963	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
4431MH0003060021600964C00	964	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4431MH0003060021600965C00	965	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
4431MH0003060021600966C00	966	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
4431MH0003060021600967C00	967	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2025

SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0003060011600969C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4432MH0001630001601016R00	1016	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4432MH0001630001601017S00	1017	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4431MH0003060021600970C00	970	13773	8.61	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	255	1
4431MH0003060021600971C00	971	13827	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	223	2
4431MH0003060021600972C00	972	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
4431MH0003060021600973C00	973	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
4431MH0003060021600974C00	974	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4431MH0003060021600975C00	975	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
4431MH0003060021600976C00	976	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
4431MH0003060021600977C00	977	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2025

SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bee_Rock - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0003360011600981C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4432MH0001630001601014R00	1014	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4432MH0001630001601015S00	1015	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4431MH0003360021600982C00	982	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4431MH0003360021600983C00	983	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4431MH0003360021600984C00	984	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4431MH0003360021600985C00	985	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4431MH0003360021600986C00	986	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4431MH0003360021600987C00	987	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4431MH0003360021600988C00	988	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4431MH0003360021600989C00	989	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_January_2025

SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bee_Rock - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0003360011600991C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4432MH0001630001601012R00		1012		MOTOR COUNT:		14005		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601013S00		1013		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-Jan-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4431MH0003360021600992C00	992	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1		
4431MH0003360021600993C00	993	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2		
4431MH0003360021600994C00	994	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3		
4431MH0003360021600995C00	995	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4		
4431MH0003360021600996C00	996	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5		
4431MH0003360021600997C00	997	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4431MH0003360021600998C00	998	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7		
4431MH0003360021600999C00	999	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_January_2025

SOL 4431 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bee_Rock - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4431MH0008730011601001C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4432MH0001630001601010R00		1010		MOTOR COUNT:		14694		RANGE (cm): 3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4432MH0001630001601011S00		1011		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00873		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-Jan-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4431		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4432	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4431MH0008730021601002C00	1002	14598	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1		
4431MH0008730021601003C00	1003	14622	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2		
4431MH0008730021601004C00	1004	14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3		
4431MH0008730021601005C00	1005	14670	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4		
4431MH0008730021601006C00	1006	14694	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5		
4431MH0008730021601007C00	1007	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6		
4431MH0008730021601008C00	1008	14742	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7		
4431MH0008730021601009C00	1009	14766	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001820011601045C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601128R00	1128	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601129S00	1129	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001820021601046C00	1046	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
4434MH0001820021601047C00	1047	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001820021601048C00	1048	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4434MH0001820021601049C00	1049	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4434MH0001820021601050C00	1050	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4434MH0001820021601051C00	1051	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4434MH0001820021601052C00	1052	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4434MH0001820021601053C00	1053	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001820011601055C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601126R00	1126	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601127S00	1127	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001820021601056C00	1056	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4434MH0001820021601057C00	1057	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001820021601058C00	1058	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4434MH0001820021601059C00	1059	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4434MH0001820021601060C00	1060	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4434MH0001820021601061C00	1061	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4434MH0001820021601062C00	1062	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4434MH0001820021601063C00	1063	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Acton - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001730011601067C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601124R00	1124	MOTOR COUNT:		14110	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601125S00	1125	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001730021601068C00	1068	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
4434MH0001730021601069C00	1069	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001730021601070C00	1070	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
4434MH0001730021601071C00	1071	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	159	4
4434MH0001730021601072C00	1072	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4434MH0001730021601073C00	1073	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
4434MH0001730021601074C00	1074	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
4434MH0001730021601075C00	1075	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Acton - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001730011601077C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601122R00	1122	MOTOR COUNT:		14115	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601123S00	1123	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001730021601078C00	1078	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
4434MH0001730021601079C00	1079	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001730021601080C00	1080	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
4434MH0001730021601081C00	1081	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4434MH0001730021601082C00	1082	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
4434MH0001730021601083C00	1083	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
4434MH0001730021601084C00	1084	14175	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
4434MH0001730021601085C00	1085	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wildhorse - ~25 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0008760011601087C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601120R00	1120		MOTOR COUNT:		13015	RANGE (cm):	26.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601121S00	1121		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0008760021601088C00	1088	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	255	1
4434MH0008760021601089C00	1089	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	223	2
4434MH0008760021601090C00	1090	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	191	3
4434MH0008760021601091C00	1091	13003	27.40	-1.9	2.1	103.3	7.1	159	4
4434MH0008760021601092C00	1092	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5
4434MH0008760021601093C00	1093	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	95	6
4434MH0008760021601094C00	1094	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	63	7
4434MH0008760021601095C00	1095	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001520011601097C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601118R00	1118		MOTOR COUNT:		14101	RANGE (cm):	6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601119S00	1119		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001520021601098C00	1098	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4434MH0001520021601099C00	1099	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001520021601100C00	1100	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4434MH0001520021601101C00	1101	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
4434MH0001520021601102C00	1102	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
4434MH0001520021601103C00	1103	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	95	6
4434MH0001520021601104C00	1104	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
4434MH0001520021601105C00	1105	14245	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_January_2025

SOL 4434 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4434MH0001520011601107C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4435MH0001710001601116R00	1116	MOTOR COUNT:		14090	RANGE (cm):		6.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4435MH0001710001601117S00	1117	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jan-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4434		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4435
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4434MH0001520021601108C00	1108	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
4434MH0001520021601109C00	1109	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4434MH0001520021601110C00	1110	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4434MH0001520021601111C00	1111	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	159	4
4434MH0001520021601112C00	1112	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	127	5
4434MH0001520021601113C00	1113	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
4434MH0001520021601114C00	1114	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4434MH0001520021601115C00	1115	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4437 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Desert_View - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4437MH0001680011601133C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4437MH0001930001601166R00	1166	MOTOR COUNT:		14036	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4437MH0001930001601167S00	1167	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4437	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4437	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4437MH0001680021601134C00	1134	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4437MH0001680021601135C00	1135	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4437MH0001680021601136C00	1136	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4437MH0001680021601137C00	1137	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4437MH0001680021601138C00	1138	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
4437MH0001680021601139C00	1139	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4437MH0001680021601140C00	1140	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4437MH0001680021601141C00	1141	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4437 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Desert_View - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4437MH0001680011601143C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4437MH0001930001601164R00	1164	MOTOR COUNT:		14035	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4437MH0001930001601165S00	1165	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jan-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4437	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4437	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4437MH0001680021601144C00	1144	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4437MH0001680021601145C00	1145	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4437MH0001680021601146C00	1146	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4437MH0001680021601147C00	1147	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4437MH0001680021601148C00	1148	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4437MH0001680021601149C00	1149	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4437MH0001680021601150C00	1150	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4437MH0001680021601151C00	1151	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4437 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Desert_View - ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4437MH0007430011601153C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4437MH0001930001601162R00	1162	MOTOR COUNT:		15213	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4437MH0001930001601163S00	1163	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jan-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4437		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4437
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4437MH0007430021601154C00	1154	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4437MH0007430021601155C00	1155	15105	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4437MH0007430021601156C00	1156	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3
4437MH0007430021601157C00	1157	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	159	4
4437MH0007430021601158C00	1158	15213	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5
4437MH0007430021601159C00	1159	15249	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	95	6
4437MH0007430021601160C00	1160	15285	2.50	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
4437MH0007430021601161C00	1161	15321	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 04_February_2025

SOL 4439 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4439MH0001680011601171C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4439MH0002650001601192R00	1192	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4439MH0002650001601193S00	1193	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4439	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4439	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4439MH0001680021601172C00	1172	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4439MH0001680021601173C00	1173	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4439MH0001680021601174C00	1174	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4439MH0001680021601175C00	1175	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4439MH0001680021601176C00	1176	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4439MH0001680021601177C00	1177	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4439MH0001680021601178C00	1178	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4439MH0001680021601179C00	1179	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_February_2025

SOL 4439 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4439MH0001680011601181C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4439MH0002650001601190R00	1190	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4439MH0002650001601191S00	1191	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Jan-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4439	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4439	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4439MH0001680021601182C00	1182	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
4439MH0001680021601183C00	1183	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4439MH0001680021601184C00	1184	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4439MH0001680021601185C00	1185	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4439MH0001680021601186C00	1186	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4439MH0001680021601187C00	1187	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4439MH0001680021601188C00	1188	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4439MH0001680021601189C00	1189	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4441 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4441MH0003360011601197C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4442MH0001930001601238R00	1238	MOTOR COUNT:		14149	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4442MH0001930001601239S00	1239	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Feb-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4441	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4442	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4441MH0003360021601198C00	1198	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	255	1
4441MH0003360021601199C00	1199	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
4441MH0003360021601200C00	1200	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
4441MH0003360021601201C00	1201	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4441MH0003360021601202C00	1202	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5
4441MH0003360021601203C00	1203	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	95	6
4441MH0003360021601204C00	1204	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
4441MH0003360021601205C00	1205	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4441 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4441MH0003360011601207C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4442MH0001930001601236R00	1236	MOTOR COUNT:		14160	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4442MH0001930001601237S00	1237	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Feb-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4441	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4442	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4441MH0003360021601208C00	1208	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
4441MH0003360021601209C00	1209	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
4441MH0003360021601210C00	1210	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3
4441MH0003360021601211C00	1211	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4441MH0003360021601212C00	1212	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4441MH0003360021601213C00	1213	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
4441MH0003360021601214C00	1214	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4441MH0003360021601215C00	1215	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_February_2025

SOL 4441 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Coldwater_Canyon – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4441MH0008730011601225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4442MH0001930001601234R00	1234	MOTOR COUNT:		14666	RANGE (cm):		3.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4442MH0001930001601235S00	1235	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00873		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Feb-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4441		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4442
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4441MH0008730021601226C00	1226	14570	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
4441MH0008730021601227C00	1227	14594	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2
4441MH0008730021601228C00	1228	14618	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3
4441MH0008730021601229C00	1229	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
4441MH0008730021601230C00	1230	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	127	5
4441MH0008730021601231C00	1231	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	95	6
4441MH0008730021601232C00	1232	14714	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
4441MH0008730021601233C00	1233	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target San_Rafael_Hills – after DRT – stereo-1 – relief model position 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0001680011601243C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601330R00	1330	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601331S00	1331	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0001680021601244C00	1244	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4443MH0001680021601245C00	1245	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4443MH0001680021601246C00	1246	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4443MH0001680021601247C00	1247	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4443MH0001680021601248C00	1248	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4443MH0001680021601249C00	1249	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4443MH0001680021601250C00	1250	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4443MH0001680021601251C00	1251	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target San_Rafael_Hills – after DRT – stereo-2 – relief model position 2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0001680011601253C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601328R00	1328	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601329S00	1329	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0001680021601254C00	1254	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4443MH0001680021601255C00	1255	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4443MH0001680021601256C00	1256	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4443MH0001680021601257C00	1257	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4443MH0001680021601258C00	1258	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4443MH0001680021601259C00	1259	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4443MH0001680021601260C00	1260	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4443MH0001680021601261C00	1261	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target San_Rafael_Hills – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0007430011601269C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601326R00	1326	MOTOR COUNT:		15085	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601327S00	1327	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0007430021601270C00	1270	14941	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
4443MH0007430021601271C00	1271	14977	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
4443MH0007430021601272C00	1272	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
4443MH0007430021601273C00	1273	15049	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
4443MH0007430021601274C00	1274	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4443MH0007430021601275C00	1275	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
4443MH0007430021601276C00	1276	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
4443MH0007430021601277C00	1277	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Allison_Mine – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0008760011601279C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601324R00	1324	MOTOR COUNT:		13009	RANGE (cm):	27.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601325S00	1325	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0008760021601280C00	1280	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	255	1
4443MH0008760021601281C00	1281	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	223	2
4443MH0008760021601282C00	1282	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	191	3
4443MH0008760021601283C00	1283	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	159	4
4443MH0008760021601284C00	1284	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	127	5
4443MH0008760021601285C00	1285	13021	26.28	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	95	6
4443MH0008760021601286C00	1286	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	63	7
4443MH0008760021601287C00	1287	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Allison_Mine - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0003080011601289C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601322R00	1322	MOTOR COUNT:		14068	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601323S00	1323	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0003080021601290C00	1290	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
4443MH0003080021601291C00	1291	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
4443MH0003080021601292C00	1292	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
4443MH0003080021601293C00	1293	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4443MH0003080021601294C00	1294	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
4443MH0003080021601295C00	1295	14134	6.04	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4443MH0003080021601296C00	1296	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
4443MH0003080021601297C00	1297	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4443 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Allison_Mine - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0003080011601299C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601320R00	1320	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601321S00	1321	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0003080021601300C00	1300	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
4443MH0003080021601301C00	1301	13832	8.09	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
4443MH0003080021601302C00	1302	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	191	3
4443MH0003080021601303C00	1303	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4443MH0003080021601304C00	1304	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4443MH0003080021601305C00	1305	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	95	6
4443MH0003080021601306C00	1306	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
4443MH0003080021601307C00	1307	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 10_February_2025

SOL 4443 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Allison_Mine - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4443MH0001760011601309C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4444MH0001710001601318R00	1318	MOTOR COUNT:		14842	RANGE (cm):		3.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4444MH0001710001601319S00	1319	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00176		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Feb-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4443		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4444
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4443MH0001760021601310C00	1310	14650	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	255	1
4443MH0001760021601311C00	1311	14698	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	223	2
4443MH0001760021601312C00	1312	14746	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	191	3
4443MH0001760021601313C00	1313	14794	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	159	4
4443MH0001760021601314C00	1314	14842	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	127	5
4443MH0001760021601315C00	1315	14890	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	95	6
4443MH0001760021601316C00	1316	14938	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	63	7
4443MH0001760021601317C00	1317	14986	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4445 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zuma_Canyon – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4445MH0001680011601344C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4446MH0002270001601403R00	1403	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4446MH0002270001601404S00	1404	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4445	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4446	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4445MH0001680021601345C00	1345	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4445MH0001680021601346C00	1346	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4445MH0001680021601347C00	1347	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4445MH0001680021601348C00	1348	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4445MH0001680021601349C00	1349	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4445MH0001680021601350C00	1350	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4445MH0001680021601351C00	1351	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4445MH0001680021601352C00	1352	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4445 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zuma_Canyon – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4445MH0001680011601354C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4446MH0002270001601401R00	1401	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4446MH0002270001601402S00	1402	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4445	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4446	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4445MH0001680021601355C00	1355	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4445MH0001680021601356C00	1356	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4445MH0001680021601357C00	1357	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4445MH0001680021601358C00	1358	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4445MH0001680021601359C00	1359	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4445MH0001680021601360C00	1360	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4445MH0001680021601361C00	1361	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4445MH0001680021601362C00	1362	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4445 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bear_Canyon – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4445MH0003360011601366C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4446MH0002270001601399R00	1399	MOTOR COUNT:		13986	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4446MH0002270001601400S00	1400	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4445	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4446	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4445MH0003360021601367C00	1367	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4445MH0003360021601368C00	1368	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4445MH0003360021601369C00	1369	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4445MH0003360021601370C00	1370	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4445MH0003360021601371C00	1371	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4445MH0003360021601372C00	1372	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4445MH0003360021601373C00	1373	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7
4445MH0003360021601374C00	1374	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4445 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bear_Canyon – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4445MH0003360011601376C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4446MH0002270001601397R00	1397	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4446MH0002270001601398S00	1398	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4445	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4446	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4445MH0003360021601377C00	1377	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4445MH0003360021601378C00	1378	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4445MH0003360021601379C00	1379	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4445MH0003360021601380C00	1380	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4445MH0003360021601381C00	1381	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4445MH0003360021601382C00	1382	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4445MH0003360021601383C00	1383	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4445MH0003360021601384C00	1384	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4445 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bear_Canyon – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4445MH0008480011601386C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4446MH0002270001601395R00		1395		MOTOR COUNT:		15050		RANGE (cm):	2.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4446MH0002270001601396S00		1396		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		6-Feb-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4445		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4446	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4445MH0008480021601387C00	1387	14954	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1		
4445MH0008480021601388C00	1388	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2		
4445MH0008480021601389C00	1389	15002	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3		
4445MH0008480021601390C00	1390	15026	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4		
4445MH0008480021601391C00	1391	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5		
4445MH0008480021601392C00	1392	15074	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	95	6		
4445MH0008480021601393C00	1393	15098	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	63	7		
4445MH0008480021601394C00	1394	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 4447 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4447MH0001680011601408C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4449MH0002270001601469R00	1469	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4449MH0002270001601470S00	1470	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4447	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4449	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4447MH0001680021601409C00	1409	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4447MH0001680021601410C00	1410	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4447MH0001680021601411C00	1411	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4447MH0001680021601412C00	1412	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4447MH0001680021601413C00	1413	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4447MH0001680021601414C00	1414	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4447MH0001680021601415C00	1415	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4447MH0001680021601416C00	1416	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4447 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4447MH0001680011601418C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4449MH0002270001601467R00	1467	MOTOR COUNT:		14022	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4449MH0002270001601468S00	1468	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4447	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4449	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4447MH0001680021601419C00	1419	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4447MH0001680021601420C00	1420	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4447MH0001680021601421C00	1421	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4447MH0001680021601422C00	1422	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4447MH0001680021601423C00	1423	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4447MH0001680021601424C00	1424	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4447MH0001680021601425C00	1425	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4447MH0001680021601426C00	1426	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4447 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aliso_Canyon - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4447MH0001680011601432C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4449MH0002270001601465R00	1465	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4449MH0002270001601466S00	1466	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4447	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4449	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4447MH0001680021601433C00	1433	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4447MH0001680021601434C00	1434	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4447MH0001680021601435C00	1435	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4447MH0001680021601436C00	1436	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4447MH0001680021601437C00	1437	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4447MH0001680021601438C00	1438	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4447MH0001680021601439C00	1439	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4447MH0001680021601440C00	1440	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4447 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aliso_Canyon - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4447MH0001680011601442C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4449MH0002270001601463R00	1463	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4449MH0002270001601464S00	1464	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4447	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4449	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4447MH0001680021601443C00	1443	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4447MH0001680021601444C00	1444	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4447MH0001680021601445C00	1445	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4447MH0001680021601446C00	1446	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4447MH0001680021601447C00	1447	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4447MH0001680021601448C00	1448	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4447MH0001680021601449C00	1449	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
4447MH0001680021601450C00	1450	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 13_February_2025

SOL 4447 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aliso_Canyon - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4447MH0003020011601452C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4449MH0002270001601461R00	1461	MOTOR COUNT:		14697	RANGE (cm):		3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4449MH0002270001601462S00	1462	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4447	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4449	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4447MH0003020021601453C00	1453	14577	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1
4447MH0003020021601454C00	1454	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
4447MH0003020021601455C00	1455	14637	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
4447MH0003020021601456C00	1456	14667	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
4447MH0003020021601457C00	1457	14697	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
4447MH0003020021601458C00	1458	14727	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
4447MH0003020021601459C00	1459	14757	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
4447MH0003020021601460C00	1460	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4452 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Catalina_Island - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4452MH0001680011601474C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4452MH0001930001601507R00	1507	MOTOR COUNT:		14039	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4452MH0001930001601508S00	1508	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4452	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4452	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4452MH0001680021601475C00	1475	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4452MH0001680021601476C00	1476	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4452MH0001680021601477C00	1477	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4452MH0001680021601478C00	1478	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
4452MH0001680021601479C00	1479	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
4452MH0001680021601480C00	1480	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4452MH0001680021601481C00	1481	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4452MH0001680021601482C00	1482	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4452 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Catalina_Island - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4452MH0001680011601484C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4452MH0001930001601505R00	1505	MOTOR COUNT:		14044	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4452MH0001930001601506S00	1506	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4452	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4452	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4452MH0001680021601485C00	1485	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4452MH0001680021601486C00	1486	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4452MH0001680021601487C00	1487	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4452MH0001680021601488C00	1488	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4452MH0001680021601489C00	1489	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4452MH0001680021601490C00	1490	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4452MH0001680021601491C00	1491	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4452MH0001680021601492C00	1492	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4452 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Catalina_Island – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4452MH0007430011601494C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4452MH0001930001601503R00	1503	MOTOR COUNT:		15228	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4452MH0001930001601504S00	1504	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Feb-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4452		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4452
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4452MH0007430021601495C00	1495	15084	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4452MH0007430021601496C00	1496	15120	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2
4452MH0007430021601497C00	1497	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
4452MH0007430021601498C00	1498	15192	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
4452MH0007430021601499C00	1499	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
4452MH0007430021601500C00	1500	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6
4452MH0007430021601501C00	1501	15300	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
4452MH0007430021601502C00	1502	15336	2.42	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0008760011601510C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601665R00	1665	MOTOR COUNT:		13012	RANGE (cm):	26.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601666S00	1666	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0008760021601511C00	1511	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	255	1
4455MH0008760021601512C00	1512	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	223	2
4455MH0008760021601513C00	1513	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	191	3
4455MH0008760021601514C00	1514	13000	27.59	-1.9	2.2	104.0	7.2	159	4
4455MH0008760021601515C00	1515	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	127	5
4455MH0008760021601516C00	1516	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	95	6
4455MH0008760021601517C00	1517	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	63	7
4455MH0008760021601518C00	1518	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0008760011601520C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601663R00	1663	MOTOR COUNT:		13011	RANGE (cm):	26.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601664S00	1664	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0008760021601521C00	1521	12963	30.22	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	255	1
4455MH0008760021601522C00	1522	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	223	2
4455MH0008760021601523C00	1523	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	191	3
4455MH0008760021601524C00	1524	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	159	4
4455MH0008760021601525C00	1525	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	127	5
4455MH0008760021601526C00	1526	13023	26.16	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	95	6
4455MH0008760021601527C00	1527	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	63	7
4455MH0008760021601528C00	1528	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0001660011601530C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601661R00	1661	MOTOR COUNT:		14120	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601662S00	1662	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00166	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0001660021601531C00	1531	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
4455MH0001660021601532C00	1532	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
4455MH0001660021601533C00	1533	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4455MH0001660021601534C00	1534	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	159	4
4455MH0001660021601535C00	1535	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
4455MH0001660021601536C00	1536	14198	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
4455MH0001660021601537C00	1537	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
4455MH0001660021601538C00	1538	14354	4.99	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0001660011601540C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601659R00	1659	MOTOR COUNT:		14112	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601660S00	1660	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00166	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0001660021601541C00	1541	13800	8.37	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1
4455MH0001660021601542C00	1542	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
4455MH0001660021601543C00	1543	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4455MH0001660021601544C00	1544	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
4455MH0001660021601545C00	1545	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4455MH0001660021601546C00	1546	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
4455MH0001660021601547C00	1547	14268	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4455MH0001660021601548C00	1548	14346	5.02	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Arrowhead - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0003360011601552C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601657R00	1657	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601658S00	1658	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0003360021601553C00	1553	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4455MH0003360021601554C00	1554	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4455MH0003360021601555C00	1555	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4455MH0003360021601556C00	1556	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4455MH0003360021601557C00	1557	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4455MH0003360021601558C00	1558	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4455MH0003360021601559C00	1559	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4455MH0003360021601560C00	1560	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Arrowhead - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0003360011601562C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601655R00	1655	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601656S00	1656	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0003360021601563C00	1563	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4455MH0003360021601564C00	1564	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4455MH0003360021601565C00	1565	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4455MH0003360021601566C00	1566	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4455MH0003360021601567C00	1567	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4455MH0003360021601568C00	1568	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4455MH0003360021601569C00	1569	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4455MH0003360021601570C00	1570	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lake_Arrowhead - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0008480011601572C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601653R00	1653	MOTOR COUNT:		15050	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601654S00	1654	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0008480021601573C00	1573	14954	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1
4455MH0008480021601574C00	1574	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
4455MH0008480021601575C00	1575	15002	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
4455MH0008480021601576C00	1576	15026	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4455MH0008480021601577C00	1577	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4455MH0008480021601578C00	1578	15074	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	95	6
4455MH0008480021601579C00	1579	15098	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	63	7
4455MH0008480021601580C00	1580	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 18_February_2025

SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0003590011601582C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601651R00	1651	MOTOR COUNT:		13024	RANGE (cm):	26.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601652S00	1652	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0003590021601583C00	1583	12952	31.10	-2.4	2.8	116.4	9.2	255	1
4455MH0003590021601584C00	1584	12970	29.69	-2.2	2.5	111.4	8.3	223	2
4455MH0003590021601585C00	1585	12988	28.40	-2.0	2.3	106.9	7.6	191	3
4455MH0003590021601586C00	1586	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	159	4
4455MH0003590021601587C00	1587	13024	26.10	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	127	5
4455MH0003590021601588C00	1588	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	95	6
4455MH0003590021601589C00	1589	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	63	7
4455MH0003590021601590C00	1590	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	31	8

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SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0003590011601592C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601649R00	1649	MOTOR COUNT:		13025	RANGE (cm):	26.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601650S00	1650	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0003590021601593C00	1593	12953	31.01	-2.4	2.8	116.1	9.1	255	1
4455MH0003590021601594C00	1594	12971	29.62	-2.2	2.5	111.2	8.3	223	2
4455MH0003590021601595C00	1595	12989	28.33	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	191	3
4455MH0003590021601596C00	1596	13007	27.14	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	159	4
4455MH0003590021601597C00	1597	13025	26.04	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	127	5
4455MH0003590021601598C00	1598	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	95	6
4455MH0003590021601599C00	1599	13061	24.07	-1.5	1.6	91.6	5.5	63	7
4455MH0003590021601600C00	1600	13079	23.18	-1.4	1.5	88.5	5.1	31	8

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SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0001820011601602C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601647R00	1647	MOTOR COUNT:		14109	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601648S00	1648	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0001820021601603C00	1603	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
4455MH0001820021601604C00	1604	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	223	2
4455MH0001820021601605C00	1605	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
4455MH0001820021601606C00	1606	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4455MH0001820021601607C00	1607	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
4455MH0001820021601608C00	1608	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4455MH0001820021601609C00	1609	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
4455MH0001820021601610C00	1610	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0001820011601612C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601645R00	1645	MOTOR COUNT:		14112	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601646S00	1646	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0001820021601613C00	1613	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
4455MH0001820021601614C00	1614	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
4455MH0001820021601615C00	1615	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
4455MH0001820021601616C00	1616	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
4455MH0001820021601617C00	1617	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
4455MH0001820021601618C00	1618	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
4455MH0001820021601619C00	1619	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
4455MH0001820021601620C00	1620	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4455 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Strawberry_Peak - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4455MH0007430011601634C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4456MH0004580001601643R00	1643	MOTOR COUNT:		15037	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4456MH0004580001601644S00	1644	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00458	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4455	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4456	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4455MH0007430021601635C00	1635	14893	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1
4455MH0007430021601636C00	1636	14929	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
4455MH0007430021601637C00	1637	14965	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3
4455MH0007430021601638C00	1638	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4
4455MH0007430021601639C00	1639	15037	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	127	5
4455MH0007430021601640C00	1640	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	95	6
4455MH0007430021601641C00	1641	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7
4455MH0007430021601642C00	1642	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wheeler_Gorge - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0003360011601670C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601741R00	1741	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601742S00	1742	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0003360021601671C00	1671	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4458MH0003360021601672C00	1672	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4458MH0003360021601673C00	1673	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4458MH0003360021601674C00	1674	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
4458MH0003360021601675C00	1675	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4458MH0003360021601676C00	1676	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4458MH0003360021601677C00	1677	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4458MH0003360021601678C00	1678	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wheeler_Gorge - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0003360011601680C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601739R00	1739	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601740S00	1740	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0003360021601681C00	1681	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
4458MH0003360021601682C00	1682	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4458MH0003360021601683C00	1683	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4458MH0003360021601684C00	1684	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4458MH0003360021601685C00	1685	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4458MH0003360021601686C00	1686	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
4458MH0003360021601687C00	1687	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4458MH0003360021601688C00	1688	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wheeler_Gorge - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0008480011601690C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601737R00	1737	MOTOR COUNT:		14841	RANGE (cm):	3.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601738S00	1738	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0008480021601691C00	1691	14745	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
4458MH0008480021601692C00	1692	14769	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	223	2
4458MH0008480021601693C00	1693	14793	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	191	3
4458MH0008480021601694C00	1694	14817	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	159	4
4458MH0008480021601695C00	1695	14841	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	127	5
4458MH0008480021601696C00	1696	14865	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	95	6
4458MH0008480021601697C00	1697	14889	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	63	7
4458MH0008480021601698C00	1698	14913	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Chumash_Trail - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0003360011601702C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601735R00	1735	MOTOR COUNT:		14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601736S00	1736	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0003360021601703C00	1703	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4458MH0003360021601704C00	1704	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4458MH0003360021601705C00	1705	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4458MH0003360021601706C00	1706	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4458MH0003360021601707C00	1707	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4458MH0003360021601708C00	1708	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4458MH0003360021601709C00	1709	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4458MH0003360021601710C00	1710	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chumash_Trail - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0003360011601712C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601733R00	1733	MOTOR COUNT:		14027	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601734S00	1734	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0003360021601713C00	1713	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4458MH0003360021601714C00	1714	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4458MH0003360021601715C00	1715	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4458MH0003360021601716C00	1716	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4458MH0003360021601717C00	1717	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4458MH0003360021601718C00	1718	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4458MH0003360021601719C00	1719	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4458MH0003360021601720C00	1720	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4458 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chumash_Trail - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4458MH0008480011601722C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4459MH0001630001601731R00	1731	MOTOR COUNT:		15171	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4459MH0001630001601732S00	1732	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4458	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4459	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4458MH0008480021601723C00	1723	15075	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	255	1
4458MH0008480021601724C00	1724	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
4458MH0008480021601725C00	1725	15123	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4458MH0008480021601726C00	1726	15147	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
4458MH0008480021601727C00	1727	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
4458MH0008480021601728C00	1728	15195	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4458MH0008480021601729C00	1729	15219	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
4458MH0008480021601730C00	1730	15243	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4461MH0002990011601755C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4462MH0001530001601808R00	1808	MOTOR COUNT:		14179	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4462MH0001530001601809S00	1809	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4461	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4462	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4461MH0002990021601756C00	1756	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	255	1
4461MH0002990021601757C00	1757	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4461MH0002990021601758C00	1758	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4461MH0002990021601759C00	1759	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4461MH0002990021601760C00	1760	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
4461MH0002990021601761C00	1761	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
4461MH0002990021601762C00	1762	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	63	7
4461MH0002990021601763C00	1763	14287	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 24_February_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4461MH0002990011601765C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4462MH0001530001601806R00	1806	MOTOR COUNT:		14192	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4462MH0001530001601807S00	1807	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4461	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4462	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4461MH0002990021601766C00	1766	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	255	1
4461MH0002990021601767C00	1767	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
4461MH0002990021601768C00	1768	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	191	3
4461MH0002990021601769C00	1769	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	159	4
4461MH0002990021601770C00	1770	14192	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
4461MH0002990021601771C00	1771	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6
4461MH0002990021601772C00	1772	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4461MH0002990021601773C00	1773	14300	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 24_February_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4461MH0003360011601783C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4462MH0001530001601804R00	1804	MOTOR COUNT:		14159	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4462MH0001530001601805S00	1805	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4461	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4462	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4461MH0003360021601784C00	1784	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
4461MH0003360021601785C00	1785	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
4461MH0003360021601786C00	1786	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3
4461MH0003360021601787C00	1787	14147	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
4461MH0003360021601788C00	1788	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4461MH0003360021601789C00	1789	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
4461MH0003360021601790C00	1790	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4461MH0003360021601791C00	1791	14195	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 24_February_2025

SOL 4461 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4461MH0003360011601793C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4462MH0001530001601802R00	1802	MOTOR COUNT:		14164	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4462MH0001530001601803S00	1803	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4461	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4462	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4461MH0003360021601794C00	1794	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	255	1
4461MH0003360021601795C00	1795	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	223	2
4461MH0003360021601796C00	1796	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
4461MH0003360021601797C00	1797	14152	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	159	4
4461MH0003360021601798C00	1798	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4461MH0003360021601799C00	1799	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
4461MH0003360021601800C00	1800	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
4461MH0003360021601801C00	1801	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_March_2025

SOL 4464 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Matilija_Poppy - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4464MH0003590011601811C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4464MH0001930001601844R00	1844	MOTOR COUNT:		13017	RANGE (cm):	26.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4464MH0001930001601845S00	1845	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4464	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4464	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4464MH0003590021601812C00	1812	12945	31.68	-2.5	2.9	118.4	9.5	255	1
4464MH0003590021601813C00	1813	12963	30.22	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	223	2
4464MH0003590021601814C00	1814	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	191	3
4464MH0003590021601815C00	1815	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	159	4
4464MH0003590021601816C00	1816	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	127	5
4464MH0003590021601817C00	1817	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	95	6
4464MH0003590021601818C00	1818	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	63	7
4464MH0003590021601819C00	1819	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_March_2025

SOL 4464 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Matilija_Poppy - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4464MH0001820011601821C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4464MH0001930001601842R00	1842	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4464MH0001930001601843S00	1843	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4464	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4464	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4464MH0001820021601822C00	1822	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
4464MH0001820021601823C00	1823	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4464MH0001820021601824C00	1824	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
4464MH0001820021601825C00	1825	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4464MH0001820021601826C00	1826	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4464MH0001820021601827C00	1827	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4464MH0001820021601828C00	1828	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4464MH0001820021601829C00	1829	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_March_2025

SOL 4464 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Matilija_Poppy - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4464MH0001820011601831C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4464MH0001930001601840R00	1840	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4464MH0001930001601841S00	1841	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4464	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4464	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4464MH0001820021601832C00	1832	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
4464MH0001820021601833C00	1833	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
4464MH0001820021601834C00	1834	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4464MH0001820021601835C00	1835	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4464MH0001820021601836C00	1836	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
4464MH0001820021601837C00	1837	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4464MH0001820021601838C00	1838	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4464MH0001820021601839C00	1839	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4466 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trippet_Ranch - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4466MH0003360011601849C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4466MH0001930001601882R00	1882	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4466MH0001930001601883S00	1883	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4466	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4466	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4466MH0003360021601850C00	1850	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
4466MH0003360021601851C00	1851	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4466MH0003360021601852C00	1852	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
4466MH0003360021601853C00	1853	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4466MH0003360021601854C00	1854	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4466MH0003360021601855C00	1855	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4466MH0003360021601856C00	1856	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4466MH0003360021601857C00	1857	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_March_2025

SOL 4466 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trippet_Ranch - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4466MH0003360011601859C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4466MH0001930001601880R00	1880	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4466MH0001930001601881S00	1881	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Feb-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4466	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4466	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4466MH0003360021601860C00	1860	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4466MH0003360021601861C00	1861	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4466MH0003360021601862C00	1862	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4466MH0003360021601863C00	1863	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4466MH0003360021601864C00	1864	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4466MH0003360021601865C00	1865	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4466MH0003360021601866C00	1866	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4466MH0003360021601867C00	1867	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_March_2025

SOL 4466 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trippet_Ranch – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4466MH0008640011601869C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4466MH0001930001601878R00	1878	MOTOR COUNT:		15107	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4466MH0001930001601879S00	1879	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Feb-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4466	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4466	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4466MH0008640021601870C00	1870	14987	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4466MH0008640021601871C00	1871	15017	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
4466MH0008640021601872C00	1872	15047	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
4466MH0008640021601873C00	1873	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
4466MH0008640021601874C00	1874	15107	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4466MH0008640021601875C00	1875	15137	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4466MH0008640021601876C00	1876	15167	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4466MH0008640021601877C00	1877	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 12_March_2025

SOL 4471 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ramona_Trail - after DRT - ~24 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4471MH0008760011601885C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4471MH0001530001601930R00		1930		MOTOR COUNT:		13023		RANGE (cm): 26.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601931S00		1931		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4471		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4471	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4471MH0008760021601886C00	1886	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	255	1		
4471MH0008760021601887C00	1887	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	223	2		
4471MH0008760021601888C00	1888	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	191	3		
4471MH0008760021601889C00	1889	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	159	4		
4471MH0008760021601890C00	1890	13023	26.16	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	127	5		
4471MH0008760021601891C00	1891	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	95	6		
4471MH0008760021601892C00	1892	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	63	7		
4471MH0008760021601893C00	1893	13059	24.17	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_March_2025

SOL 4471 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ramona_Trail - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4471MH0001680011601895C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4471MH0001530001601928R00		1928		MOTOR COUNT:		14050		RANGE (cm): 6.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4471MH0001530001601929S00		1929		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4471		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4471	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4471MH0001680021601896C00	1896	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1		
4471MH0001680021601897C00	1897	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2		
4471MH0001680021601898C00	1898	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3		
4471MH0001680021601899C00	1899	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4		
4471MH0001680021601900C00	1900	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5		
4471MH0001680021601901C00	1901	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6		
4471MH0001680021601902C00	1902	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7		
4471MH0001680021601903C00	1903	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 12_March_2025

SOL 4471 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ramona_Trail - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4471MH0001680011601905C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4471MH0001530001601926R00	1926	MOTOR COUNT:		14052	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4471MH0001530001601927S00	1927	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4471	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4471	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4471MH0001680021601906C00	1906	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4471MH0001680021601907C00	1907	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
4471MH0001680021601908C00	1908	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4471MH0001680021601909C00	1909	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
4471MH0001680021601910C00	1910	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
4471MH0001680021601911C00	1911	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
4471MH0001680021601912C00	1912	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4471MH0001680021601913C00	1913	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 12_March_2025

SOL 4471 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ramona_Trail - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4471MH0008640011601915C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4471MH0001530001601924R00	1924	MOTOR COUNT:		15009	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4471MH0001530001601925S00	1925	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4471	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4471	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4471MH0008640021601916C00	1916	14889	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	255	1
4471MH0008640021601917C00	1917	14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
4471MH0008640021601918C00	1918	14949	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	191	3
4471MH0008640021601919C00	1919	14979	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	159	4
4471MH0008640021601920C00	1920	15009	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	127	5
4471MH0008640021601921C00	1921	15039	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	95	6
4471MH0008640021601922C00	1922	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
4471MH0008640021601923C00	1923	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angeles_Crest - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008340011601936C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4478MH0007890001602007R00	2007	MOTOR COUNT:		14155	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4478MH0007890001602008S00	2008	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00789	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4477MH0008340031601938C00	1938	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	255	1
4477MH0008340031601939C00	1939	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	223	2
4477MH0008340031601940C00	1940	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	191	3
4477MH0008340031601941C00	1941	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4477MH0008340031601942C00	1942	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
4477MH0008340031601943C00	1943	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
4477MH0008340031601944C00	1944	14191	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	63	7
4477MH0008340031601945C00	1945	14209	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angeles_Crest - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008340011601947C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4478MH0007890001602005R00	2005	MOTOR COUNT:		14163	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4478MH0007890001602006S00	2006	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00789	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4477MH0008340031601949C00	1949	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	255	1
4477MH0008340031601950C00	1950	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
4477MH0008340031601951C00	1951	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
4477MH0008340031601952C00	1952	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4477MH0008340031601953C00	1953	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4477MH0008340031601954C00	1954	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
4477MH0008340031601955C00	1955	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
4477MH0008340031601956C00	1956	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 1 of 4 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008770011601958C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4478MH0007890001602003R00	2003	MOTOR COUNT:		13208	RANGE (cm):	18.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4478MH0007890001602004S00	2004	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00789	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4477MH0008770021601959C00	1959	13088	22.76	-1.3	1.5	87.0	4.9	255	1
4477MH0008770021601960C00	1960	13118	21.45	-1.2	1.3	82.4	4.3	223	2
4477MH0008770021601961C00	1961	13148	20.26	-1.1	1.1	78.2	3.9	191	3
4477MH0008770021601962C00	1962	13178	19.19	-1.0	1.0	74.4	3.5	159	4
4477MH0008770021601963C00	1963	13208	18.21	-0.9	0.9	71.0	3.1	127	5
4477MH0008770021601964C00	1964	13238	17.31	-0.8	0.8	67.8	2.9	95	6
4477MH0008770021601965C00	1965	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	63	7
4477MH0008770021601966C00	1966	13298	15.73	-0.7	0.7	62.3	2.4	31	8

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 2 of 4 - ~15 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008770011601968C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4478MH0007890001602001R00	2001	MOTOR COUNT:		13243	RANGE (cm):	17.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4478MH0007890001602002S00	2002	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00789	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4477MH0008770021601969C00	1969	13123	21.24	-1.2	1.3	81.7	4.3	255	1
4477MH0008770021601970C00	1970	13153	20.08	-1.1	1.1	77.6	3.8	223	2
4477MH0008770021601971C00	1971	13183	19.02	-0.9	1.0	73.8	3.4	191	3
4477MH0008770021601972C00	1972	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	159	4
4477MH0008770021601973C00	1973	13243	17.17	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	127	5
4477MH0008770021601974C00	1974	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	95	6
4477MH0008770021601975C00	1975	13303	15.61	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	63	7
4477MH0008770021601976C00	1976	13333	14.92	-0.6	0.6	59.4	2.1	31	8

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 3 of 4 - ~15 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008770011601978C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4478MH0007890001601999R00		1999		MOTOR COUNT:		13272		RANGE (cm): 16.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001602000S00		2000		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		11-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00789		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4477MH0008770021601979C00	1979	13152	20.11	-1.1	1.1	77.7	3.8	255	1		
4477MH0008770021601980C00	1980	13182	19.05	-1.0	1.0	74.0	3.4	223	2		
4477MH0008770021601981C00	1981	13212	18.08	-0.9	0.9	70.6	3.1	191	3		
4477MH0008770021601982C00	1982	13242	17.20	-0.8	0.8	67.4	2.8	159	4		
4477MH0008770021601983C00	1983	13272	16.39	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	127	5		
4477MH0008770021601984C00	1984	13302	15.64	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	95	6		
4477MH0008770021601985C00	1985	13332	14.94	-0.6	0.6	59.5	2.1	63	7		
4477MH0008770021601986C00	1986	13362	14.30	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 13_March_2025

SOL 4477 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 4 of 4 - ~15 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4477MH0008770011601988C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4478MH0007890001601997R00		1997		MOTOR COUNT:		13273		RANGE (cm): 16.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4478MH0007890001601998S00		1998		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00877		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		11-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00789		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4477		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4478	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4477MH0008770021601989C00	1989	13153	20.08	-1.1	1.1	77.6	3.8	255	1		
4477MH0008770021601990C00	1990	13183	19.02	-0.9	1.0	73.8	3.4	223	2		
4477MH0008770021601991C00	1991	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	191	3		
4477MH0008770021601992C00	1992	13243	17.17	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	159	4		
4477MH0008770021601993C00	1993	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	127	5		
4477MH0008770021601994C00	1994	13303	15.61	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	95	6		
4477MH0008770021601995C00	1995	13333	14.92	-0.6	0.6	59.4	2.1	63	7		
4477MH0008770021601996C00	1996	13363	14.28	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - ~26 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008550011602010C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602127R00	2127	MOTOR COUNT:		12996	RANGE (cm):	27.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602128S00	2128	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0008550021602011C00	2011	12876	38.68	-3.6	4.5	143.1	14.3	255	1
4479MH0008550021602012C00	2012	12906	35.31	-3.1	3.7	131.2	11.9	223	2
4479MH0008550021602013C00	2013	12936	32.45	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	191	3
4479MH0008550021602014C00	2014	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	159	4
4479MH0008550021602015C00	2015	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	127	5
4479MH0008550021602016C00	2016	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	95	6
4479MH0008550021602017C00	2017	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	63	7
4479MH0008550021602018C00	2018	13086	22.85	-1.3	1.5	87.3	4.9	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0002970011602020C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602125R00	2125	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602126S00	2126	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0002970021602021C00	2021	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
4479MH0002970021602022C00	2022	13812	8.26	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	223	2
4479MH0002970021602023C00	2023	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
4479MH0002970021602024C00	2024	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
4479MH0002970021602025C00	2025	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4479MH0002970021602026C00	2026	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4479MH0002970021602027C00	2027	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
4479MH0002970021602028C00	2028	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0002970011602030C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602123R00	2123	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602124S00	2124	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0002970021602031C00	2031	13757	8.76	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	255	1
4479MH0002970021602032C00	2032	13817	8.22	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	223	2
4479MH0002970021602033C00	2033	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	191	3
4479MH0002970021602034C00	2034	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
4479MH0002970021602035C00	2035	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4479MH0002970021602036C00	2036	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4479MH0002970021602037C00	2037	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
4479MH0002970021602038C00	2038	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stunt_Ranch - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0006490011602040C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602121R00	2121	MOTOR COUNT:		15099	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602122S00	2122	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00649	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0006490021602041C00	2041	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	255	1
4479MH0006490021602042C00	2042	14865	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	223	2
4479MH0006490021602043C00	2043	14943	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	191	3
4479MH0006490021602044C00	2044	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4479MH0006490021602045C00	2045	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
4479MH0006490021602046C00	2046	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
4479MH0006490021602047C00	2047	15255	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
4479MH0006490021602048C00	2048	15333	2.42	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - ~26 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008550011602050C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4480MH0003690001602119R00		2119		MOTOR COUNT:		13001		RANGE (cm): 27.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602120S00		2120		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4479MH0008550021602051C00	2051	12881	38.08	-3.5	4.3	140.9	13.8	255	1		
4479MH0008550021602052C00	2052	12911	34.80	-3.0	3.6	129.4	11.5	223	2		
4479MH0008550021602053C00	2053	12941	32.02	-2.5	3.0	119.6	9.7	191	3		
4479MH0008550021602054C00	2054	12971	29.62	-2.2	2.5	111.2	8.3	159	4		
4479MH0008550021602055C00	2055	13001	27.53	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	127	5		
4479MH0008550021602056C00	2056	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	95	6		
4479MH0008550021602057C00	2057	13061	24.07	-1.5	1.6	91.6	5.5	63	7		
4479MH0008550021602058C00	2058	13091	22.62	-1.3	1.4	86.5	4.8	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - ~26 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008550011602060C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4480MH0003690001602117R00		2117		MOTOR COUNT:		12995		RANGE (cm): 27.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4480MH0003690001602118S00		2118		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4479MH0008550021602061C00	2061	12875	38.80	-3.7	4.5	143.5	14.4	255	1		
4479MH0008550021602062C00	2062	12905	35.41	-3.1	3.7	131.6	11.9	223	2		
4479MH0008550021602063C00	2063	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	191	3		
4479MH0008550021602064C00	2064	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	159	4		
4479MH0008550021602065C00	2065	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	127	5		
4479MH0008550021602066C00	2066	13025	26.04	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	95	6		
4479MH0008550021602067C00	2067	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	63	7		
4479MH0008550021602068C00	2068	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pacifico_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~75 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008950011602070C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602115R00	2115	MOTOR COUNT:		13682	RANGE (cm):	9.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602116S00	2116	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00895	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0008950021602071C00	2071	13442	12.79	-0.5	0.5	51.9	1.6	255	1
4479MH0008950021602072C00	2072	13502	11.82	-0.4	0.4	48.5	1.4	223	2
4479MH0008950021602073C00	2073	13562	10.96	-0.4	0.3	45.5	1.2	191	3
4479MH0008950021602074C00	2074	13622	10.20	-0.3	0.3	42.8	1.1	159	4
4479MH0008950021602075C00	2075	13682	9.52	-0.3	0.3	40.4	0.9	127	5
4479MH0008950021602076C00	2076	13742	8.91	-0.3	0.2	38.3	0.8	95	6
4479MH0008950021602077C00	2077	13802	8.35	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	63	7
4479MH0008950021602078C00	2078	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pacifico_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~8 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008950011602080C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602113R00	2113	MOTOR COUNT:		13629	RANGE (cm):	10.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602114S00	2114	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00895	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0008950021602081C00	2081	13389	13.76	-0.5	0.5	55.3	1.8	255	1
4479MH0008950021602082C00	2082	13449	12.67	-0.5	0.5	51.5	1.6	223	2
4479MH0008950021602083C00	2083	13509	11.71	-0.4	0.4	48.1	1.4	191	3
4479MH0008950021602084C00	2084	13569	10.87	-0.3	0.3	45.2	1.2	159	4
4479MH0008950021602085C00	2085	13629	10.12	-0.3	0.3	42.5	1.0	127	5
4479MH0008950021602086C00	2086	13689	9.45	-0.3	0.3	40.1	0.9	95	6
4479MH0008950021602087C00	2087	13749	8.84	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	63	7
4479MH0008950021602088C00	2088	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pacifico_Mountain - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~85 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008950011602090C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602111R00	2111	MOTOR COUNT:		13608	RANGE (cm):	10.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602112S00	2112	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00895	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0008950021602091C00	2091	13368	14.17	-0.6	0.6	56.8	1.9	255	1
4479MH0008950021602092C00	2092	13428	13.03	-0.5	0.5	52.8	1.7	223	2
4479MH0008950021602093C00	2093	13488	12.03	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	191	3
4479MH0008950021602094C00	2094	13548	11.15	-0.4	0.4	46.2	1.3	159	4
4479MH0008950021602095C00	2095	13608	10.37	-0.3	0.3	43.4	1.1	127	5
4479MH0008950021602096C00	2096	13668	9.67	-0.3	0.3	41.0	1.0	95	6
4479MH0008950021602097C00	2097	13728	9.04	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	63	7
4479MH0008950021602098C00	2098	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	31	8

UPDATED: 14_March_2025

SOL 4479 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pacifico_Mountain - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4479MH0008550011602100C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4480MH0003690001602109R00	2109	MOTOR COUNT:		13005	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4480MH0003690001602110S00	2110	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4479	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4480	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4479MH0008550021602101C00	2101	12885	37.61	-3.5	4.2	139.3	13.5	255	1
4479MH0008550021602102C00	2102	12915	34.40	-2.9	3.5	128.0	11.2	223	2
4479MH0008550021602103C00	2103	12945	31.68	-2.5	2.9	118.4	9.5	191	3
4479MH0008550021602104C00	2104	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	159	4
4479MH0008550021602105C00	2105	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	127	5
4479MH0008550021602106C00	2106	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	95	6
4479MH0008550021602107C00	2107	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	63	7
4479MH0008550021602108C00	2108	13095	22.44	-1.3	1.4	85.9	4.8	31	8

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yerba_Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 1 of 5 - ~13 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008460011602130C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602295R00	2295	MOTOR COUNT:		13339	RANGE (cm):	14.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602296S00	2296	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0008460021602131C00	2131	13123	21.24	-1.2	1.3	81.7	4.3	255	1
4481MH0008460021602132C00	2132	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	223	2
4481MH0008460021602133C00	2133	13231	17.51	-0.8	0.9	68.6	2.9	191	3
4481MH0008460021602134C00	2134	13285	16.05	-0.7	0.7	63.4	2.5	159	4
4481MH0008460021602135C00	2135	13339	14.79	-0.6	0.6	59.0	2.1	127	5
4481MH0008460021602136C00	2136	13393	13.68	-0.5	0.5	55.1	1.8	95	6
4481MH0008460021602137C00	2137	13447	12.70	-0.5	0.5	51.6	1.6	63	7
4481MH0008460021602138C00	2138	13501	11.83	-0.4	0.4	48.6	1.4	31	8

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yerba_Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 2 of 5 - ~15 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008460011602140C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602293R00	2293	MOTOR COUNT:		13252	RANGE (cm):	16.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602294S00	2294	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0008460021602141C00	2141	13036	25.41	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	255	1
4481MH0008460021602142C00	2142	13090	22.67	-1.3	1.4	86.7	4.8	223	2
4481MH0008460021602143C00	2143	13144	20.41	-1.1	1.2	78.8	3.9	191	3
4481MH0008460021602144C00	2144	13198	18.52	-0.9	1.0	72.1	3.3	159	4
4481MH0008460021602145C00	2145	13252	16.92	-0.8	0.8	66.5	2.7	127	5
4481MH0008460021602146C00	2146	13306	15.54	-0.7	0.7	61.6	2.3	95	6
4481MH0008460021602147C00	2147	13360	14.34	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	63	7
4481MH0008460021602148C00	2148	13414	13.29	-0.5	0.5	53.7	1.7	31	8

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yerba_Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 3 of 5 - ~20 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008460011602150C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4483MH0007280001602291R00		2291		MOTOR COUNT:		13120	RANGE (cm):	21.4
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602292S00		2292		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4481MH0008460021602151C00	2151	12904	35.52	-3.1	3.7	131.9	12.0	255	1	
4481MH0008460021602152C00	2152	12958	30.61	-2.3	2.7	114.7	8.9	223	2	
4481MH0008460021602153C00	2153	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	191	3	
4481MH0008460021602154C00	2154	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	159	4	
4481MH0008460021602155C00	2155	13120	21.36	-1.2	1.3	82.1	4.3	127	5	
4481MH0008460021602156C00	2156	13174	19.32	-1.0	1.0	74.9	3.5	95	6	
4481MH0008460021602157C00	2157	13228	17.60	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	63	7	
4481MH0008460021602158C00	2158	13282	16.13	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	31	8	

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yerba_Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 4 of 5 - ~21 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008460011602160C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4483MH0007280001602289R00		2289		MOTOR COUNT:		13094	RANGE (cm):	22.5
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602290S00		2290		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4481MH0008460021602161C00	2161	12878	38.44	-3.6	4.4	142.2	14.1	255	1	
4481MH0008460021602162C00	2162	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	223	2	
4481MH0008460021602163C00	2163	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	191	3	
4481MH0008460021602164C00	2164	13040	25.19	-1.6	1.8	95.6	6.0	159	4	
4481MH0008460021602165C00	2165	13094	22.49	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	127	5	
4481MH0008460021602166C00	2166	13148	20.26	-1.1	1.1	78.2	3.9	95	6	
4481MH0008460021602167C00	2167	13202	18.40	-0.9	0.9	71.7	3.2	63	7	
4481MH0008460021602168C00	2168	13256	16.81	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	31	8	

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Yerba_Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 5 of 5 - ~21 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008460011602170C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4483MH0007280001602287R00		2287		MOTOR COUNT:		13095		RANGE (cm): 22.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602288S00		2288		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00846		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4481MH0008460021602171C00	2171	12879	38.31	-3.6	4.4	141.8	14.0	255	1		
4481MH0008460021602172C00	2172	12933	32.72	-2.7	3.1	122.1	10.2	223	2		
4481MH0008460021602173C00	2173	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	191	3		
4481MH0008460021602174C00	2174	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	159	4		
4481MH0008460021602175C00	2175	13095	22.44	-1.3	1.4	85.9	4.8	127	5		
4481MH0008460021602176C00	2176	13149	20.22	-1.1	1.1	78.1	3.9	95	6		
4481MH0008460021602177C00	2177	13203	18.36	-0.9	0.9	71.5	3.2	63	7		
4481MH0008460021602178C00	2178	13257	16.78	-0.8	0.8	66.0	2.7	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target South_Fork - ~25 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008550011602180C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4483MH0007280001602285R00		2285		MOTOR COUNT:		13017		RANGE (cm): 26.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4483MH0007280001602286S00		2286		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4481MH0008550021602181C00	2181	12897	36.26	-3.2	3.9	134.5	12.5	255	1		
4481MH0008550021602182C00	2182	12927	33.26	-2.7	3.2	124.0	10.5	223	2		
4481MH0008550021602183C00	2183	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	191	3		
4481MH0008550021602184C00	2184	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	159	4		
4481MH0008550021602185C00	2185	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	127	5		
4481MH0008550021602186C00	2186	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	95	6		
4481MH0008550021602187C00	2187	13077	23.28	-1.4	1.5	88.8	5.1	63	7		
4481MH0008550021602188C00	2188	13107	21.91	-1.2	1.3	84.0	4.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 18_March_2025

SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target South_Fork - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0003080011602190C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602283R00	2283	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602284S00	2284	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC				
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4481MH0003080021602191C00	2191	13738	8.95	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1	
4481MH0003080021602192C00	2192	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2	
4481MH0003080021602193C00	2193	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3	
4481MH0003080021602194C00	2194	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4	
4481MH0003080021602195C00	2195	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5	
4481MH0003080021602196C00	2196	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6	
4481MH0003080021602197C00	2197	14134	6.04	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	63	7	
4481MH0003080021602198C00	2198	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8	

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target South_Fork - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0003080011602200C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602281R00	2281	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602282S00	2282	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC				
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4481MH0003080021602201C00	2201	13743	8.90	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	255	1	
4481MH0003080021602202C00	2202	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	223	2	
4481MH0003080021602203C00	2203	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3	
4481MH0003080021602204C00	2204	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4	
4481MH0003080021602205C00	2205	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5	
4481MH0003080021602206C00	2206	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6	
4481MH0003080021602207C00	2207	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	63	7	
4481MH0003080021602208C00	2208	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8	

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target South_Fork - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0007960011602210C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602279R00	2279	MOTOR COUNT:		14878	RANGE (cm):	3.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602280S00	2280	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0007960021602211C00	2211	14710	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	255	1
4481MH0007960021602212C00	2212	14752	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	223	2
4481MH0007960021602213C00	2213	14794	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	191	3
4481MH0007960021602214C00	2214	14836	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	159	4
4481MH0007960021602215C00	2215	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	127	5
4481MH0007960021602216C00	2216	14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	95	6
4481MH0007960021602217C00	2217	14962	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	63	7
4481MH0007960021602218C00	2218	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008550011602220C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602277R00	2277	MOTOR COUNT:		13026	RANGE (cm):	26.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602278S00	2278	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0008550021602221C00	2221	12906	35.31	-3.1	3.7	131.2	11.9	255	1
4481MH0008550021602222C00	2222	12936	32.45	-2.6	3.1	121.1	10.0	223	2
4481MH0008550021602223C00	2223	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	191	3
4481MH0008550021602224C00	2224	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
4481MH0008550021602225C00	2225	13026	25.99	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	127	5
4481MH0008550021602226C00	2226	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	95	6
4481MH0008550021602227C00	2227	13086	22.85	-1.3	1.5	87.3	4.9	63	7
4481MH0008550021602228C00	2228	13116	21.53	-1.2	1.3	82.7	4.4	31	8

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-3 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008550011602230C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602275R00	2275	MOTOR COUNT:		13028	RANGE (cm):	25.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602276S00	2276	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0008550021602231C00	2231	12908	35.11	-3.0	3.6	130.5	11.7	255	1
4481MH0008550021602232C00	2232	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	223	2
4481MH0008550021602233C00	2233	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	191	3
4481MH0008550021602234C00	2234	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	159	4
4481MH0008550021602235C00	2235	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	127	5
4481MH0008550021602236C00	2236	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	95	6
4481MH0008550021602237C00	2237	13088	22.76	-1.3	1.5	87.0	4.9	63	7
4481MH0008550021602238C00	2238	13118	21.45	-1.2	1.3	82.4	4.3	31	8

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0008550011602240C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602273R00	2273	MOTOR COUNT:		13027	RANGE (cm):	25.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602274S00	2274	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0008550021602241C00	2241	12907	35.21	-3.0	3.7	130.8	11.8	255	1
4481MH0008550021602242C00	2242	12937	32.36	-2.6	3.1	120.8	9.9	223	2
4481MH0008550021602243C00	2243	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	191	3
4481MH0008550021602244C00	2244	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	159	4
4481MH0008550021602245C00	2245	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	127	5
4481MH0008550021602246C00	2246	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	95	6
4481MH0008550021602247C00	2247	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	63	7
4481MH0008550021602248C00	2248	13117	21.49	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	31	8

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0006730011602250C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602271R00	2271	MOTOR COUNT:		14100	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602272S00	2272	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00673	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0006730021602251C00	2251	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
4481MH0006730021602252C00	2252	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
4481MH0006730021602253C00	2253	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
4481MH0006730021602254C00	2254	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4481MH0006730021602255C00	2255	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
4481MH0006730021602256C00	2256	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6
4481MH0006730021602257C00	2257	14268	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4481MH0006730021602258C00	2258	14352	4.99	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4481 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4481MH0006730011602260C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4483MH0007280001602269R00	2269	MOTOR COUNT:		14157	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4483MH0007280001602270S00	2270	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00673	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00728	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4481	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4483	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4481MH0006730021602261C00	2261	13821	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
4481MH0006730021602262C00	2262	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
4481MH0006730021602263C00	2263	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4481MH0006730021602264C00	2264	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
4481MH0006730021602265C00	2265	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4481MH0006730021602266C00	2266	14241	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	95	6
4481MH0006730021602267C00	2267	14325	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	63	7
4481MH0006730021602268C00	2268	14409	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palm_Grove - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0001680011602300C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602537R00	2537	MOTOR COUNT:		14024	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602538S00	2538	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0001680021602301C00	2301	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4486MH0001680021602302C00	2302	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
4486MH0001680021602303C00	2303	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4486MH0001680021602304C00	2304	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4486MH0001680021602305C00	2305	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4486MH0001680021602306C00	2306	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
4486MH0001680021602307C00	2307	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
4486MH0001680021602308C00	2308	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palm_Grove - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0001680011602310C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602535R00	2535	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602536S00	2536	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0001680021602311C00	2311	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4486MH0001680021602312C00	2312	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4486MH0001680021602313C00	2313	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4486MH0001680021602314C00	2314	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4486MH0001680021602315C00	2315	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4486MH0001680021602316C00	2316	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4486MH0001680021602317C00	2317	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4486MH0001680021602318C00	2318	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palm_Grove - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0001680011602320C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602533R00	2533	MOTOR COUNT:	14035	RANGE (cm):	6.6			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602534S00	2534	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4487			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0001680021602321C00	2321	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4486MH0001680021602322C00	2322	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4486MH0001680021602323C00	2323	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4486MH0001680021602324C00	2324	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4486MH0001680021602325C00	2325	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
4486MH0001680021602326C00	2326	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4486MH0001680021602327C00	2327	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
4486MH0001680021602328C00	2328	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Palm_Grove - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008640011602330C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602531R00	2531	MOTOR COUNT:	14903	RANGE (cm):	3.3			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602532S00	2532	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4487			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008640021602331C00	2331	14783	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	255	1
4486MH0008640021602332C00	2332	14813	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
4486MH0008640021602333C00	2333	14843	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	191	3
4486MH0008640021602334C00	2334	14873	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	159	4
4486MH0008640021602335C00	2335	14903	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5
4486MH0008640021602336C00	2336	14933	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	95	6
4486MH0008640021602337C00	2337	14963	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	63	7
4486MH0008640021602338C00	2338	14993	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 1 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602340C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602529R00		2529		MOTOR COUNT:		13304		RANGE (cm): 15.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602530S00		2530		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4486MH0008960021602341C00	2341	13208	18.21	-0.9	0.9	71.0	3.1	255	1		
4486MH0008960021602342C00	2342	13232	17.49	-0.8	0.8	68.4	2.9	223	2		
4486MH0008960021602343C00	2343	13256	16.81	-0.8	0.8	66.1	2.7	191	3		
4486MH0008960021602344C00	2344	13280	16.18	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	159	4		
4486MH0008960021602345C00	2345	13304	15.59	-0.7	0.7	61.8	2.3	127	5		
4486MH0008960021602346C00	2346	13328	15.03	-0.6	0.6	59.8	2.2	95	6		
4486MH0008960021602347C00	2347	13352	14.51	-0.6	0.6	58.0	2.0	63	7		
4486MH0008960021602348C00	2348	13376	14.01	-0.5	0.5	56.2	1.9	31	8		

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 2 of 16 - ~13 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602350C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602527R00		2527		MOTOR COUNT:		13315		RANGE (cm): 15.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602528S00		2528		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4486MH0008960021602351C00	2351	13219	17.87	-0.8	0.9	69.8	3.0	255	1		
4486MH0008960021602352C00	2352	13243	17.17	-0.8	0.8	67.3	2.8	223	2		
4486MH0008960021602353C00	2353	13267	16.52	-0.7	0.8	65.0	2.6	191	3		
4486MH0008960021602354C00	2354	13291	15.90	-0.7	0.7	62.9	2.4	159	4		
4486MH0008960021602355C00	2355	13315	15.33	-0.6	0.7	60.9	2.3	127	5		
4486MH0008960021602356C00	2356	13339	14.79	-0.6	0.6	59.0	2.1	95	6		
4486MH0008960021602357C00	2357	13363	14.28	-0.6	0.6	57.2	2.0	63	7		
4486MH0008960021602358C00	2358	13387	13.80	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	31	8		

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 3 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602360C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602525R00		2525		MOTOR COUNT:		13313		RANGE (cm): 15.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602526S00		2526		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4486MH0008960021602361C00	2361	13217	17.93	-0.9	0.9	70.0	3.1	255	1		
4486MH0008960021602362C00	2362	13241	17.23	-0.8	0.8	67.5	2.8	223	2		
4486MH0008960021602363C00	2363	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	191	3		
4486MH0008960021602364C00	2364	13289	15.95	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	159	4		
4486MH0008960021602365C00	2365	13313	15.37	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	127	5		
4486MH0008960021602366C00	2366	13337	14.83	-0.6	0.6	59.1	2.1	95	6		
4486MH0008960021602367C00	2367	13361	14.32	-0.6	0.6	57.3	2.0	63	7		
4486MH0008960021602368C00	2368	13385	13.83	-0.5	0.5	55.6	1.9	31	8		

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 4 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602370C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602523R00		2523		MOTOR COUNT:		13301		RANGE (cm): 15.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602524S00		2524		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4486MH0008960021602371C00	2371	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	255	1		
4486MH0008960021602372C00	2372	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	223	2		
4486MH0008960021602373C00	2373	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	191	3		
4486MH0008960021602374C00	2374	13277	16.26	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	159	4		
4486MH0008960021602375C00	2375	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	127	5		
4486MH0008960021602376C00	2376	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	95	6		
4486MH0008960021602377C00	2377	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	63	7		
4486MH0008960021602378C00	2378	13373	14.07	-0.5	0.6	56.4	1.9	31	8		

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SOL 4486 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista – mosaic position 5 of 16 – ~14 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602380C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602521R00	2521		MOTOR COUNT:		13301	RANGE (cm):	15.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602522S00	2522		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602381C00	2381	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	255	1
4486MH0008960021602382C00	2382	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	223	2
4486MH0008960021602383C00	2383	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	191	3
4486MH0008960021602384C00	2384	13277	16.26	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	159	4
4486MH0008960021602385C00	2385	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	127	5
4486MH0008960021602386C00	2386	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	95	6
4486MH0008960021602387C00	2387	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	63	7
4486MH0008960021602388C00	2388	13373	14.07	-0.5	0.6	56.4	1.9	31	8

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SOL 4486 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista – mosaic position 6 of 16 – ~14 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602390C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602519R00	2519		MOTOR COUNT:		13310	RANGE (cm):	15.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602520S00	2520		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602391C00	2391	13214	18.02	-0.9	0.9	70.3	3.1	255	1
4486MH0008960021602392C00	2392	13238	17.31	-0.8	0.8	67.8	2.9	223	2
4486MH0008960021602393C00	2393	13262	16.65	-0.7	0.8	65.5	2.6	191	3
4486MH0008960021602394C00	2394	13286	16.03	-0.7	0.7	63.3	2.5	159	4
4486MH0008960021602395C00	2395	13310	15.44	-0.6	0.7	61.3	2.3	127	5
4486MH0008960021602396C00	2396	13334	14.90	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	95	6
4486MH0008960021602397C00	2397	13358	14.38	-0.6	0.6	57.5	2.0	63	7
4486MH0008960021602398C00	2398	13382	13.89	-0.5	0.5	55.8	1.9	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 7 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602400C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602517R00	2517	MOTOR COUNT:		13305	RANGE (cm):	15.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602518S00	2518	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602401C00	2401	13209	18.18	-0.9	0.9	70.9	3.1	255	1
4486MH0008960021602402C00	2402	13233	17.46	-0.8	0.8	68.3	2.9	223	2
4486MH0008960021602403C00	2403	13257	16.78	-0.8	0.8	66.0	2.7	191	3
4486MH0008960021602404C00	2404	13281	16.15	-0.7	0.7	63.8	2.5	159	4
4486MH0008960021602405C00	2405	13305	15.56	-0.7	0.7	61.7	2.3	127	5
4486MH0008960021602406C00	2406	13329	15.01	-0.6	0.6	59.7	2.2	95	6
4486MH0008960021602407C00	2407	13353	14.49	-0.6	0.6	57.9	2.0	63	7
4486MH0008960021602408C00	2408	13377	13.99	-0.5	0.5	56.2	1.9	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 8 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602410C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0008970001602515R00	2515	MOTOR COUNT:		13293	RANGE (cm):	15.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0008970001602516S00	2516	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602411C00	2411	13197	18.56	-0.9	1.0	72.2	3.3	255	1
4486MH0008960021602412C00	2412	13221	17.81	-0.8	0.9	69.6	3.0	223	2
4486MH0008960021602413C00	2413	13245	17.11	-0.8	0.8	67.1	2.8	191	3
4486MH0008960021602414C00	2414	13269	16.46	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	159	4
4486MH0008960021602415C00	2415	13293	15.85	-0.7	0.7	62.7	2.4	127	5
4486MH0008960021602416C00	2416	13317	15.28	-0.6	0.6	60.7	2.2	95	6
4486MH0008960021602417C00	2417	13341	14.74	-0.6	0.6	58.8	2.1	63	7
4486MH0008960021602418C00	2418	13365	14.24	-0.6	0.6	57.0	2.0	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 9 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602420C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602513R00		2513		MOTOR COUNT:		13286	RANGE (cm):	16.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602514S00		2514		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4486MH0008960021602421C00	2421	13190	18.78	-0.9	1.0	73.0	3.3	255	1	
4486MH0008960021602422C00	2422	13214	18.02	-0.9	0.9	70.3	3.1	223	2	
4486MH0008960021602423C00	2423	13238	17.31	-0.8	0.8	67.8	2.9	191	3	
4486MH0008960021602424C00	2424	13262	16.65	-0.7	0.8	65.5	2.6	159	4	
4486MH0008960021602425C00	2425	13286	16.03	-0.7	0.7	63.3	2.5	127	5	
4486MH0008960021602426C00	2426	13310	15.44	-0.6	0.7	61.3	2.3	95	6	
4486MH0008960021602427C00	2427	13334	14.90	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	63	7	
4486MH0008960021602428C00	2428	13358	14.38	-0.6	0.6	57.5	2.0	31	8	

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 10 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602430C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4487MH0008970001602511R00		2511		MOTOR COUNT:		13301	RANGE (cm):	15.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4487MH0008970001602512S00		2512		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		20-Mar-25				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00897	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
4486MH0008960021602431C00	2431	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	255	1	
4486MH0008960021602432C00	2432	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	223	2	
4486MH0008960021602433C00	2433	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	191	3	
4486MH0008960021602434C00	2434	13277	16.26	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	159	4	
4486MH0008960021602435C00	2435	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	127	5	
4486MH0008960021602436C00	2436	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	95	6	
4486MH0008960021602437C00	2437	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	63	7	
4486MH0008960021602438C00	2438	13373	14.07	-0.5	0.6	56.4	1.9	31	8	

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 11 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602440C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602509R00	2509	MOTOR COUNT:		13288	RANGE (cm):	16.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602510S00	2510	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602441C00	2441	13192	18.72	-0.9	1.0	72.8	3.3	255	1
4486MH0008960021602442C00	2442	13216	17.96	-0.9	0.9	70.1	3.1	223	2
4486MH0008960021602443C00	2443	13240	17.26	-0.8	0.8	67.6	2.8	191	3
4486MH0008960021602444C00	2444	13264	16.60	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	159	4
4486MH0008960021602445C00	2445	13288	15.98	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	127	5
4486MH0008960021602446C00	2446	13312	15.40	-0.6	0.7	61.1	2.3	95	6
4486MH0008960021602447C00	2447	13336	14.85	-0.6	0.6	59.2	2.1	63	7
4486MH0008960021602448C00	2448	13360	14.34	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 12 of 16 - ~15 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602450C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602507R00	2507	MOTOR COUNT:		13273	RANGE (cm):	16.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602508S00	2508	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602451C00	2451	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	255	1
4486MH0008960021602452C00	2452	13201	18.43	-0.9	0.9	71.8	3.2	223	2
4486MH0008960021602453C00	2453	13225	17.69	-0.8	0.9	69.2	3.0	191	3
4486MH0008960021602454C00	2454	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	159	4
4486MH0008960021602455C00	2455	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	127	5
4486MH0008960021602456C00	2456	13297	15.76	-0.7	0.7	62.4	2.4	95	6
4486MH0008960021602457C00	2457	13321	15.19	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	63	7
4486MH0008960021602458C00	2458	13345	14.66	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 13 of 16 - ~15 cm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602460C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602505R00	2505		MOTOR COUNT:		13265	RANGE (cm):	16.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602506S00	2506		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602461C00	2461	13169	19.50	-1.0	1.1	75.5	3.6	255	1
4486MH0008960021602462C00	2462	13193	18.69	-0.9	1.0	72.7	3.3	223	2
4486MH0008960021602463C00	2463	13217	17.93	-0.9	0.9	70.0	3.1	191	3
4486MH0008960021602464C00	2464	13241	17.23	-0.8	0.8	67.5	2.8	159	4
4486MH0008960021602465C00	2465	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	127	5
4486MH0008960021602466C00	2466	13289	15.95	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	95	6
4486MH0008960021602467C00	2467	13313	15.37	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	63	7
4486MH0008960021602468C00	2468	13337	14.83	-0.6	0.6	59.1	2.1	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 14 of 16 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602470C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602503R00	2503		MOTOR COUNT:		13277	RANGE (cm):	16.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602504S00	2504		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602471C00	2471	13181	19.08	-1.0	1.0	74.1	3.5	255	1
4486MH0008960021602472C00	2472	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	223	2
4486MH0008960021602473C00	2473	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	191	3
4486MH0008960021602474C00	2474	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	159	4
4486MH0008960021602475C00	2475	13277	16.26	-0.7	0.7	64.1	2.5	127	5
4486MH0008960021602476C00	2476	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	95	6
4486MH0008960021602477C00	2477	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	63	7
4486MH0008960021602478C00	2478	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 15 of 16 - ~15 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602480C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602501R00	2501		MOTOR COUNT:		13268	RANGE (cm):	16.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602502S00	2502		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602481C00	2481	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	255	1
4486MH0008960021602482C00	2482	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	223	2
4486MH0008960021602483C00	2483	13220	17.84	-0.8	0.9	69.7	3.0	191	3
4486MH0008960021602484C00	2484	13244	17.14	-0.8	0.8	67.2	2.8	159	4
4486MH0008960021602485C00	2485	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	127	5
4486MH0008960021602486C00	2486	13292	15.88	-0.7	0.7	62.8	2.4	95	6
4486MH0008960021602487C00	2487	13316	15.30	-0.6	0.6	60.8	2.2	63	7
4486MH0008960021602488C00	2488	13340	14.76	-0.6	0.6	58.9	2.1	31	8

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SOL 4486 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 16 of 16 - ~15 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4486MH0008960011602490C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4487MH0001630001602499R00	2499		MOTOR COUNT:		13258	RANGE (cm):	16.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4487MH0001630001602500S00	2500		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00896	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-Mar-25			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4486	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4487	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4486MH0008960021602491C00	2491	13162	19.75	-1.0	1.1	76.4	3.7	255	1
4486MH0008960021602492C00	2492	13186	18.92	-0.9	1.0	73.5	3.4	223	2
4486MH0008960021602493C00	2493	13210	18.15	-0.9	0.9	70.8	3.1	191	3
4486MH0008960021602494C00	2494	13234	17.43	-0.8	0.8	68.2	2.9	159	4
4486MH0008960021602495C00	2495	13258	16.76	-0.8	0.8	65.9	2.7	127	5
4486MH0008960021602496C00	2496	13282	16.13	-0.7	0.7	63.7	2.5	95	6
4486MH0008960021602497C00	2497	13306	15.54	-0.7	0.7	61.6	2.3	63	7
4486MH0008960021602498C00	2498	13330	14.99	-0.6	0.6	59.7	2.2	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Solstice_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0003360011602542C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602623R00	2623	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602624S00	2624	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0003360021602543C00	2543	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4488MH0003360021602544C00	2544	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4488MH0003360021602545C00	2545	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4488MH0003360021602546C00	2546	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4488MH0003360021602547C00	2547	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4488MH0003360021602548C00	2548	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4488MH0003360021602549C00	2549	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4488MH0003360021602550C00	2550	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Solstice_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0003360011602552C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602621R00	2621	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602622S00	2622	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0003360021602553C00	2553	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4488MH0003360021602554C00	2554	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4488MH0003360021602555C00	2555	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4488MH0003360021602556C00	2556	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4488MH0003360021602557C00	2557	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4488MH0003360021602558C00	2558	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4488MH0003360021602559C00	2559	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4488MH0003360021602560C00	2560	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Solstice_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0003360011602562C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602619R00	2619	MOTOR COUNT:		13947	RANGE (cm):	7.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602620S00	2620	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0003360021602563C00	2563	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
4488MH0003360021602564C00	2564	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
4488MH0003360021602565C00	2565	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
4488MH0003360021602566C00	2566	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
4488MH0003360021602567C00	2567	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5
4488MH0003360021602568C00	2568	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	95	6
4488MH0003360021602569C00	2569	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	63	7
4488MH0003360021602570C00	2570	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Solstice_Canyon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0008480011602572C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602617R00	2617	MOTOR COUNT:		14874	RANGE (cm):	3.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602618S00	2618	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0008480021602573C00	2573	14778	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	255	1
4488MH0008480021602574C00	2574	14802	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	223	2
4488MH0008480021602575C00	2575	14826	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	191	3
4488MH0008480021602576C00	2576	14850	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	159	4
4488MH0008480021602577C00	2577	14874	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	127	5
4488MH0008480021602578C00	2578	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	95	6
4488MH0008480021602579C00	2579	14922	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	63	7
4488MH0008480021602580C00	2580	14946	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Oak - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0003590011602582C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602615R00	2615	MOTOR COUNT:		13034	RANGE (cm):	25.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602616S00	2616	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0003590021602583C00	2583	12962	30.30	-2.3	2.7	113.6	8.7	255	1
4488MH0003590021602584C00	2584	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	223	2
4488MH0003590021602585C00	2585	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	191	3
4488MH0003590021602586C00	2586	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	159	4
4488MH0003590021602587C00	2587	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	127	5
4488MH0003590021602588C00	2588	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	95	6
4488MH0003590021602589C00	2589	13070	23.62	-1.4	1.6	90.0	5.3	63	7
4488MH0003590021602590C00	2590	13088	22.76	-1.3	1.5	87.0	4.9	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Oak - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0001660011602592C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602613R00	2613	MOTOR COUNT:		14342	RANGE (cm):	5.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602614S00	2614	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00166	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0001660021602593C00	2593	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	255	1
4488MH0001660021602594C00	2594	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
4488MH0001660021602595C00	2595	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	191	3
4488MH0001660021602596C00	2596	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	159	4
4488MH0001660021602597C00	2597	14342	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	127	5
4488MH0001660021602598C00	2598	14420	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	95	6
4488MH0001660021602599C00	2599	14498	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	63	7
4488MH0001660021602600C00	2600	14576	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	31	8

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SOL 4488 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4488MH0001660011602602C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4489MH0001710001602611R00	2611	MOTOR COUNT:		14357	RANGE (cm):		5.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4489MH0001710001602612S00	2612	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00166		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Mar-25		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4488		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4489
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4488MH0001660021602603C00	2603	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	255	1
4488MH0001660021602604C00	2604	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
4488MH0001660021602605C00	2605	14201	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	191	3
4488MH0001660021602606C00	2606	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	159	4
4488MH0001660021602607C00	2607	14357	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	127	5
4488MH0001660021602608C00	2608	14435	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	95	6
4488MH0001660021602609C00	2609	14513	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	63	7
4488MH0001660021602610C00	2610	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 4355–4488. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 4355, 4359, 4360, 4368, 4369, 4370, 4371, 4372, 4374, 4382, 4384, 4386, 4387, 4389, 4393, 4394, 4416, 4417, 4425, 4428, 4429, 4431, 4432, 4434, 4435, 4437, 4439, 4441, 4442, 4443, 4444, 4445, 4446, 4447, 4449, 4452, 4455, 4456, 4458, 4459, 4461, 4462, 4464, 4466, 4471, 4477, 4478, 4479, 4480, 4481, 4483, 4486, 4487, 4488.**

updated: 10_June_2025

Sol 4355 - MAHLI Images

		acquired(performed date(s))	5-Nov-24	
		camera position:	54	Image ID:
		total parent images:	5	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	54	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT - brushed target Epidote_Peak and the target Millys_Foot_Path. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Epidote_Peak after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4355MH0019000110468800	4688	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4355MH0019000110468900	4689	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Epidote_Peak after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4355MH0016800110469000	4690	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4355MH0016800110469100	4691	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4355MH0016800110469200	4692	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469300	4693	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469400	4694	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469500	4695	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469600	4696	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469700	4697	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469800	4698	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110469900	4699	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Epidote_Peak after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4355MH0016800110470000	4700	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4355MH0016800110470100	4701	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4355MH0016800110470200	4702	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470300	4703	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470400	4704	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470500	4705	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470600	4706	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470700	4707	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470800	4708	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0016800110470900	4709	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Epidote_Peak after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4355MH0074300110471000	4710	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4355MH0074300110471100	4711	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4355MH0074300110471200	4712	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471300	4713	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471400	4714	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471500	4715	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471600	4716	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471700	4717	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471800	4718	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0074300110471900	4719	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Millys_Foot_Path ~24 cm standoff	4355MH0019000110472000	4720	autofocus sub-frame for target Millys_Foot_Path - standoff near 24 cm
		4355MH0019000110472100	4721	target Millys_Foot_Path - standoff near 24 cm
mN00224	Millys_Foot_Path stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4355MH0022400110472200	4722	autofocus sub-frame for target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4355MH0022400110472300	4723	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4355MH0022400110472400	4724	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110472500	4725	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110472600	4726	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110472700	4727	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110472800	4728	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110472900	4729	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473000	4730	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473100	4731	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Millys_Foot_Path stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4355MH0022400110473200	4732	autofocus sub-frame for target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4355MH0022400110473300	4733	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4355MH0022400110473400	4734	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473500	4735	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473600	4736	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473700	4737	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473800	4738	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110473900	4739	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110474000	4740	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4355MH0022400110474100	4741	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	4355MH00227000110474200	4742	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4734-4741 - best focus image product
		4355MH00227000110474300	4743	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4734-4741 - range map product
		4355MH00227000110474400	4744	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4724-4731 - best focus image product
		4355MH00227000110474500	4745	target Millys_Foot_Path - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4724-4731 - range map product
		4355MH00227000110474600	4746	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4712-4719 - best focus image product
		4355MH00227000110474700	4747	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4712-4719 - range map product
		4355MH00227000110474800	4748	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4702-4709 - best focus image product
		4355MH00227000110474900	4749	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4702-4709 - range map product
4355MH00227000110475000	4750	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4692-4699 - best focus image product		
4355MH00227000110475100	4751	target Epidote_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4355 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4692-4699 - range map product		

updated: 10_June_2025

Sol 4359 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	10-Nov-24	
		camera position	75	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	74	
summary of MAHLI activities: On Sol 4357, MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3506 (data from Sols 4139-4306) were deleted from the MAHLI OGA non-volatile memory storage. On Sol 4359, MAHLI image the DRT-brushed target Forester_Pass and the targets Mahogany_Creek and Buttruss_Tree.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Forester_Pass after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4359MH001900001700010C00	1	autofocus sub-frame for target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4359MH001900011600002C00	2	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Forester_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4359MH003360001600030C00	3	autofocus sub-frame for target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4359MH003360011600004C00	4	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4359MH003360021600005C00	5	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360031600006C00	6	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360041600007C00	7	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360051600008C00	8	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360061600009C00	9	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360071600010C00	10	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360081600011C00	11	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360091600012C00	12	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Forester_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4359MH003360001600013C00	13	autofocus sub-frame for target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4359MH003360011600014C00	14	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4359MH003360021600015C00	15	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360031600016C00	16	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360041600017C00	17	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360051600018C00	18	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360061600019C00	19	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360071600020C00	20	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360081600021C00	21	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360091600022C00	22	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Forester_Pass after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4359MH008480001600033C00	23	autofocus sub-frame for target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4359MH008480011600024C00	24	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4359MH008480021600025C00	25	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480031600026C00	26	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480041600027C00	27	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480051600028C00	28	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480061600029C00	29	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480071600030C00	30	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480081600031C00	31	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008480091600032C00	32	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Mahogany_Creek ~24 cm standoff	4359MH001900001600033C00	33	autofocus sub-frame for target Mahogany_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
		4359MH001900011600034C00	34	target Mahogany_Creek - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Mahogany_Creek stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4359MH003360001600035C00	35	autofocus sub-frame for target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4359MH003360011600036C00	36	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4359MH003360021600037C00	37	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360031600038C00	38	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360041600039C00	39	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360051600040C00	40	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360061600041C00	41	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360071600042C00	42	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360081600043C00	43	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360091600044C00	44	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Mahogany_Creek stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4359MH003360001600045C00	45	autofocus sub-frame for target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4359MH003360011600046C00	46	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4359MH003360021600047C00	47	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360031600048C00	48	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360041600049C00	49	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360051600050C00	50	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360061600051C00	51	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360071600052C00	52	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360081600053C00	53	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH003360091600054C00	54	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00892	Buttruss_Tree stereo-1 ~11 cm standoff	4359MH008920001600055C00	55	autofocus sub-frame for target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm
		4359MH008920011600056C00	56	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm
		4359MH008920021600057C00	57	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920031600058C00	58	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920041600059C00	59	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920051600060C00	60	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920061600061C00	61	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920071600062C00	62	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920081600063C00	63	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH008920091600064C00	64	target Buttruss_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00892	Buttress_Tree stereo-2 -11 cm standoff	4359MH000892001160065C00	65	autofocus sub-frame for target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm
		4359MH000892001160066C00	66	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm
		4359MH000892001160067C00	67	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160068C00	68	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160069C00	69	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160070C00	70	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160071C00	71	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160072C00	72	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160073C00	73	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4359MH000892001160074C00	74	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 11_November_2024

Sol 4360 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Nov-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4359 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4360MH00017J000160007900	75	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 67-74 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160007650	76	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-2 - standoff near 11 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 67-74 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160007700	77	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160007850	78	target Buttress_Tree - stereo-1 - standoff near 11 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160007900	79	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 47-54 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160008050	80	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 47-54 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160008100	81	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 37-44 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160008250	82	target Mahogany_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 37-44 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160008300	83	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 25-32 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160008450	84	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 25-32 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160008500	85	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 15-22 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160008650	86	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 15-22 - range map product
		4360MH00017J000160008700	87	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 9-12 - best focus image product
		4360MH00017J000160008850	88	target Forester_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4359 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 9-12 - range map product

Sol 4368 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19-Nov-24
camera position	65
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	65

MAHLI image ID: **black** = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; **orange** = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID: **CPDPID**
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI image the DRT brushed targets Calaveras and Murphys.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALIZE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Calaveras after DRT stereo-1 ~25 cm standoff	4368MH00190001600893CD	89	autofocus sub-frame for target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4368MH00190001600900CD	90	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Calaveras after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4368MH00336001600910CD	91	autofocus sub-frame for target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH00336001600920CD	92	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH00336001600930CD	93	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600940CD	94	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600950CD	95	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600960CD	96	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600970CD	97	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600980CD	98	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001600990CD	99	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601000CD	100	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Calaveras after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4368MH00336001601010CD	101	autofocus sub-frame for target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH00336001601020CD	102	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH00336001601030CD	103	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601040CD	104	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601050CD	105	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601060CD	106	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601070CD	107	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601080CD	108	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601090CD	109	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH00336001601100CD	110	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Calaveras after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4368MH008640016001110CD	111	autofocus sub-frame for target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4368MH008640016001120CD	112	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4368MH008640016001130CD	113	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001140CD	114	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001150CD	115	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001160CD	116	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001170CD	117	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001180CD	118	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001190CD	119	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008640016001200CD	120	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Calaveras after DRT stereo-2 ~25 cm standoff	4368MH001900016001210CD	121	autofocus sub-frame for target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4368MH001900016001220CD	122	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00190	Murphys after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4368MH001900016001230CD	123	autofocus sub-frame for target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4368MH001900016001240CD	124	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Murphys after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4368MH003360016001250CD	125	autofocus sub-frame for target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH003360016001260CD	126	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH003360016001270CD	127	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001280CD	128	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001290CD	129	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001300CD	130	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001310CD	131	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001320CD	132	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001330CD	133	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001340CD	134	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Murphys after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4368MH003360016001350CD	135	autofocus sub-frame for target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH003360016001360CD	136	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4368MH003360016001370CD	137	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001380CD	138	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001390CD	139	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001400CD	140	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001410CD	141	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001420CD	142	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001430CD	143	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH003360016001440CD	144	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Murphys after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4368MH008480016001450CD	145	autofocus sub-frame for target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4368MH008480016001460CD	146	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4368MH008480016001470CD	147	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001480CD	148	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001490CD	149	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001500CD	150	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001510CD	151	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001520CD	152	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001530CD	153	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4368MH008480016001540CD	154	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 20_November_2024

Sol 4369 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Nov-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4368 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4369MH00163000160015900	155	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 147-154 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600156500	156	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 147-154 - range map product
		4369MH001630001600157800	157	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 137-144 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600158500	158	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 137-144 - range map product
		4369MH001630001600159800	159	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 127-134 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600160500	160	target Murphys - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 127-134 - range map product
		4369MH001630001600161800	161	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 113-120 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600162500	162	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 113-120 - range map product
		4369MH001630001600163800	163	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 103-110 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600164500	164	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 103-110 - range map product
		4369MH001630001600165800	165	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 93-100 - best focus image product
		4369MH001630001600166500	166	target Calaveras - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4368 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 93-100 - range map product

updated: 10_June_2025

Sol 4370 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-Nov-24	
		camera position	112	Image ID:
		total parent images:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	112	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI acquired an 8-position L-shaped mosaic on the target Lee_Vining. MAHLI also imaged the target Buttermilk.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00854	Lee_Vining mosaic position 1 of 8 ~20 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216001670CD	167	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm
		4370MH0008400216001680CD	168	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm
		4370MH0008400216001690CD	169	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001700CD	170	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001710CD	171	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001720CD	172	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001730CD	173	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001740CD	174	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Lee_Vining mosaic position 2 of 8 ~20 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216001770CD	177	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm
		4370MH0008400216001780CD	178	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm
		4370MH0008400216001790CD	179	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001800CD	180	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001810CD	181	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001820CD	182	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001830CD	183	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001840CD	184	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Lee_Vining mosaic position 3 of 8 ~19 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216001870CD	187	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm
		4370MH0008400216001880CD	188	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm
		4370MH0008400216001890CD	189	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001900CD	190	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001910CD	191	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001920CD	192	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001930CD	193	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216001940CD	194	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Lee_Vining mosaic position 4 of 8 ~18 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216001970CD	197	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216001980CD	198	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216001990CD	199	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002000CD	200	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002010CD	201	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002020CD	202	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002030CD	203	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002040CD	204	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00854	Lee_Vining mosaic position 5 of 8 ~18 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216002050CD	205	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002060CD	206	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002070CD	207	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216002080CD	208	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216002090CD	209	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002100CD	210	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002110CD	211	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002120CD	212	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00846	Lee_Vining mosaic position 6 of 8 ~18 cm standoff	4370MH0008400216002130CD	213	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002140CD	214	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002150CD	215	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002160CD	216	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002170CD	217	autofocus sub-frame for target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216002180CD	218	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm
		4370MH0008400216002190CD	219	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4370MH0008400216002200CD	220	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4370MH0008400216002210CD	221	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4370MH0008400216002220CD	222	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4370MH0008400216002230CD	223	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4370MH0008400216002240CD	224	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4370MH0008400216002250CD	225	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4370MH0008400216002260CD	226	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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updated: 22_November_2024

Sol 4371 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Nov-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	11
total focus merge products	22
total parent images + focus merge products	22
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4370 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1H00449	Focus Merges	4371MH000449000160027900	279	target Butternilk - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 271-278 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160028050	280	target Butternilk - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 271-278 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160028100	281	target Butternilk - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 261-268 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160028250	282	target Butternilk - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 261-268 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160028300	283	target Butternilk - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 251-258 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160028450	284	target Butternilk - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 251-258 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160028500	285	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 8 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 239-246 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160028650	286	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 8 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 239-246 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160028700	287	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 7 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 229-236 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160028850	288	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 7 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 229-236 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160028900	289	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 219-226 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160029050	290	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 6 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 219-226 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160029100	291	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 209-216 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160029250	292	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 5 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 209-216 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160029300	293	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 199-206 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160029450	294	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 4 of 8 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 199-206 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160029500	295	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 189-196 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160029650	296	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 3 of 8 - standoff near 19 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 189-196 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160029700	297	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 179-186 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160029850	298	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 2 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 179-186 - range map product
		4371MH000449000160029900	299	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 169-176 - best focus image product
		4371MH000449000160030050	300	target Lee_Vining - mosaic position 1 of 8 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4370 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 169-176 - range map product

updated: 06_March_2025

Sol 4374 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Nov-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4372 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4374MH000163000160036300	363	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 355-362 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160036400	364	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 355-362 - range map product
		4374MH000163000160036500	365	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 345-352 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160036600	366	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 345-352 - range map product
		4374MH000163000160036700	367	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 335-342 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160036800	368	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 335-342 - range map product
		4374MH000163000160036900	369	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 325-332 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160037000	370	target Cienega_Mirrh - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 325-332 - range map product
		4374MH000163000160037100	371	target Mount_Tallac - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 313-320 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160037200	372	target Mount_Tallac - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 313-320 - range map product
		4374MH000163000160037300	373	target Mount_Tallac - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 303-310 - best focus image product
		4374MH000163000160037400	374	target Mount_Tallac - stereo-1 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4372 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 303-310 - range map product

updated: 15_October_2025

Sol 4382 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	9-Dec-24			
		camera position	13	Image ID:		
		total parent images	54	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	62			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Coronet_Lake. MAHLI also imaged the target Excelsior_Mountain, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a new capability that uses MAHLI onboard r-range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface. The focus stack images were also merged.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00865	Coronet_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4382MH0008650011600375CD	375	autofocus sub-frame for target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm		
		4382MH0008650011600376CD	376	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm		
		4382MH0008650011600377CD	377	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600378CD	378	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600379CD	379	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600380CD	380	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600381CD	381	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600382CD	382	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600383CD	383	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0008650011600384CD	384	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00224	Coronet_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4382MH0002240011600395CD	385	autofocus sub-frame for target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4382MH0002240011600396CD	386	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4382MH0002240011600397CD	387	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4382MH0002240011600398CD	388	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4382MH0002240011600399CD	389			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0002240011600390CD	390			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0002240011600391CD	391			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0002240011600392CD	392			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0002240011600393CD	393			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0002240011600394CD	394			target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00224	Coronet_Lake stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4382MH0002240011600395CD	395	autofocus sub-frame for target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4382MH0002240011600396CD	396	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4382MH0002240011600397CD	397	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4382MH0002240011600398CD	398	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4382MH0002240011600399CD	399	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0002240011600400CD	400	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0002240011600401CD	401	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0002240011600402CD	402	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0002240011600403CD	403	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4382MH0002240011600404CD	404	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00838	Coronet_Lake ~1 cm standoff	4382MH0008380011600405CD	405	autofocus sub-frame for target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
				4382MH0008380011600406CD	406	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
				4382MH0008380011600407CD	407	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4382MH0008380011600408CD	408	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4382MH0008380011600409CD	409			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0008380011600410CD	410			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0008380011600411CD	411			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0008380011600412CD	412			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0008380011600413CD	413			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4382MH0008380011600414CD	414			target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00250	Excelsior_Mountain ~24 cm standoff			4382MH0001900011600415CD	415	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - standoff near 24 cm
				4382MH0001900011600416CD	416	target Excelsior_Mountain - standoff near 24 cm
mN00866	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff			4382MH0008660011600417CD	417	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
				4382MH0008660011600418CD	418	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00867	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4382MH0008670011600419CD	419	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm		
		4382MH0008670011600420CD	420	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm		
mN00868	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~3 cm standoff	4382MH0008680011600421CD	421	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm		
		4382MH0008680011600422CD	422	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm		
mN00869	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~2 cm standoff	4382MH0008690011600423CD	423	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm		
		4382MH0008690011600424CD	424	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm		
mN00870	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~15 mm standoff	4382MH0008700011600425CD	425	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm		
		4382MH0008700011600426CD	426	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 15 mm		
mN00871	Excelsior_Mountain MAHLI prox mode ~1 cm standoff	4382MH0008710011600427CD	427	autofocus sub-frame for target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm		
		4382MH0008710011600428CD	428	target Excelsior_Mountain - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 1 cm		
mN00253	Focus Merges	4382MH0001330011600429RD	429	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 407-414 - best focus image product		
		4382MH0001330011600430RD	430	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 407-414 - range map product		
		4382MH0001330011600431RD	431	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 397-404 - best focus image product		
		4382MH0001330011600432RD	432	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 397-404 - range map product		
		4382MH0001330011600433RD	433	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 387-394 - best focus image product		
		4382MH0001330011600434RD	434	target Coronet_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 387-394 - range map product		
		4382MH0001330011600435RD	435	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 377-384 - best focus image product		
		4382MH0001330011600436RD	436	target Coronet_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4382 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 377-384 - range map product		

Sol 4384 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6-Dec-24
camera position	Image ID:
total parent images	85 black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	8 CDPID:
total focus merge products	18 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products	100

MAHLI imaged the targets Placerville and Three_Brothers. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00705	Placerville ~23 cm standoff	438MH000706001600437ZC0	437	autofocus sub-frame for target Placerville - standoff near 23 cm		
		438MH000706001600438ZC0	438	target Placerville - standoff near 23 cm		
		438MH000706001600439ZC0	439	target Placerville - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00852	Placerville ~8 cm standoff	438MH000852001600440ZC0	440	autofocus sub-frame for target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm		
		438MH000852001600441ZC0	441	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm		
		438MH000852001600442ZC0	442	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		438MH000852001600443ZC0	443	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600444ZC0	444	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600445ZC0	445	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600446ZC0	446	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600447ZC0	447	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600448ZC0	448	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600449ZC0	449	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000852001600450ZC0	450	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00855	Three_Brothers Stereo 1 ~28 cm standoff	438MH000855001600451ZC0	451	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm
				438MH000855001600452ZC0	452	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm
438MH000855001600453ZC0	453			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600454ZC0	454			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600455ZC0	455			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600456ZC0	456			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600457ZC0	457			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600458ZC0	458			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600459ZC0	459			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600460ZC0	460			target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00152	Three_Brothers Stereo 1 ~65 mm standoff			438MH000152001600461ZC0	461	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm
				438MH000152001600462ZC0	462	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm
				438MH000152001600463ZC0	463	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		438MH000152001600464ZC0	464	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600465ZC0	465	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600466ZC0	466	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600467ZC0	467	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600468ZC0	468	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600469ZC0	469	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000152001600470ZC0	470	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00152	Three_Brothers Stereo 2 ~10 cm standoff	438MH000152001600471ZC0	471	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm
				438MH000152001600472ZC0	472	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm
				438MH000152001600473ZC0	473	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
438MH000152001600474ZC0	474			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600475ZC0	475			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600476ZC0	476			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600477ZC0	477			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600478ZC0	478			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600479ZC0	479			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000152001600480ZC0	480			target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00855	Three_Brothers Stereo 2 ~28 cm standoff			438MH000855001600481ZC0	481	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm
				438MH000855001600482ZC0	482	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm
				438MH000855001600483ZC0	483	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		438MH000855001600484ZC0	484	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600485ZC0	485	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600486ZC0	486	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600487ZC0	487	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600488ZC0	488	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600489ZC0	489	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		438MH000855001600490ZC0	490	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00855	Three_Brothers Stereo 3 ~28 cm standoff	438MH000855001600491ZC0	491	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm
				438MH000855001600492ZC0	492	target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm
				438MH000855001600493ZC0	493	target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
438MH000855001600494ZC0	494			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600495ZC0	495			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600496ZC0	496			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600497ZC0	497			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600498ZC0	498			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600499ZC0	499			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
438MH000855001600500ZC0	500			target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00855	Three_Brothers stereo-4 -28 cm standoff	4384MH00855001600501C00	501	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm
		4384MH00855001600502C00	502	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm
		4384MH00855001600503C00	503	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600504C00	504	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600505C00	505	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600506C00	506	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600507C00	507	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600508C00	508	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600509C00	509	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600510C00	510	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00855	Three_Brothers stereo-5 -28 cm standoff	4384MH00855001600511C00	511	autofocus sub-frame for target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm
		4384MH00855001600512C00	512	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm
		4384MH00855001600513C00	513	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600514C00	514	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600515C00	515	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600516C00	516	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600517C00	517	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600518C00	518	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600519C00	519	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4384MH00855001600520C00	520	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00893	Focus Merges	4384MH00893001600521R00	521	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 513-520 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600522S00	522	target Three_Brothers - stereo-5 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 513-520 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600523R00	523	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 503-510 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600524S00	524	target Three_Brothers - stereo-4 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 503-510 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600525R00	525	target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 493-500 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600526S00	526	target Three_Brothers - stereo-3 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 493-500 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600527R00	527	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 483-490 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600528S00	528	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 483-490 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600529R00	529	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 473-480 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600530S00	530	target Three_Brothers - stereo-2 - standoff near 10 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 473-480 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600531R00	531	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 463-470 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600532S00	532	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 65 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 463-470 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600533R00	533	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 453-460 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600534S00	534	target Three_Brothers - stereo-1 - standoff near 28 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 453-460 - range map product
		4384MH00893001600535R00	535	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 443-450 - best focus image product
		4384MH00893001600536S00	536	target Placerville - standoff near 8 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4384 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 443-450 - range map product

updated: 12_December_2024

Sol 4386 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	7 Dec 24
camera positions	13
total parent images	71
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	71

MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Icehouse_Canyon and the DRT-brushed target Sunland.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4386MH0003720016005700D	537	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		4386MH0003710016005380D	538	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4386MH0003720016005990D	539	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		4386MH0003730016005400D	540	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00374	MAHLI cal target + wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4386MH0003740016005410D	541	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4386MH0003740016005420D	542	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4386MH0003740016005430D	543	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mN00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4386MH0003730016005440D	544	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		4386MH0003730016005450D	545	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mN00376	Icehouse_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	4386MH0008760016005460D	546	autofocus sub-frame for target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4386MH0008760016005470D	547	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4386MH0008760016005480D	548	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005490D	549	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005500D	550	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005510D	551	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005520D	552	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005530D	553	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005540D	554	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0008760016005550D	555	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00352	Icehouse_Canyon stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4386MH0001520016005560D	556	autofocus sub-frame for target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4386MH0001520016005570D	557	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4386MH0001520016005580D	558	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005590D	559	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005600D	560	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005610D	561	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005620D	562	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005630D	563	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005640D	564	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005650D	565	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00352	Icehouse_Canyon stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4386MH0001520016005660D	566	autofocus sub-frame for target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4386MH0001520016005670D	567	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4386MH0001520016005680D	568	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005690D	569	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005700D	570	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005710D	571	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005720D	572	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005730D	573	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005740D	574	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0001520016005750D	575	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00390	Sunland after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4386MH0001900016005760D	576	autofocus sub-frame for target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4386MH0001900016005770D	577	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00396	Sunland after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4386MH0003360016005780D	578	autofocus sub-frame for target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4386MH0003360016005790D	579	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4386MH0003360016005800D	580	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005810D	581	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005820D	582	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005830D	583	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005840D	584	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005850D	585	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005860D	586	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005870D	587	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00396	Sunland after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4386MH0003360016005880D	588	autofocus sub-frame for target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4386MH0003360016005890D	589	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4386MH0003360016005900D	590	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005910D	591	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005920D	592	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005930D	593	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005940D	594	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005950D	595	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005960D	596	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH0003360016005970D	597	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mN00848	Sunland after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4386MH00848001600598C00	598	autofocus sub-frame for target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4386MH00848001600599C00	599	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4386MH00848001600600C00	600	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600601C00	601	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600602C00	602	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600603C00	603	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600604C00	604	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600605C00	605	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4386MH00848001600606C00	606	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4386MH00848001600607C00	607	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 09_December_2024

Sol 4387 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Dec 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4386 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	4387MH00163000160060800	608	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 600-607 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160060900	609	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 600-607 - range map product
		4387MH00163000160061000	610	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 590-597 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160061100	611	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 590-597 - range map product
		4387MH00163000160061200	612	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 580-587 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160061300	613	target Sunland - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 580-587 - range map product
		4387MH00163000160061400	614	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 568-575 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160061500	615	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 568-575 - range map product
		4387MH00163000160061600	616	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 558-565 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160061700	617	target Icehouse_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 558-565 - range map product
		4387MH00163000160061800	618	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 548-555 - best focus image product
		4387MH00163000160061900	619	target Icehouse_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4386 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 548-555 - range map product

updated: 12_December_2024

Sol 4389 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Dec-24
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Cerro Negro and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Cerro Negro ~25 cm standoff	4389MH00190001609620C0	620	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 25 cm
		4389MH00190001609624C0	621	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Cerro Negro stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4389MH00168001609623C0	622	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4389MH00168001609623C0	623	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4389MH00168001609624C0	624	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609625C0	625	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609626C0	626	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609627C0	627	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609628C0	628	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609629C0	629	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609630C0	630	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609631C0	631	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Cerro Negro stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4389MH00168001609632C0	632	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4389MH00168001609633C0	633	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4389MH00168001609634C0	634	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609635C0	635	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609636C0	636	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609637C0	637	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609638C0	638	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609639C0	639	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609640C0	640	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00168001609641C0	641	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Cerro Negro ~1 cm standoff	4389MH00743001609642C0	642	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm
		4389MH00743001609643C0	643	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm
		4389MH00743001609644C0	644	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609645C0	645	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609646C0	646	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609647C0	647	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609648C0	648	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609649C0	649	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609650C0	650	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4389MH00743001609651C0	651	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4389MH0019300160965200	652	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 644-651 - best focus image product
		4389MH0019300160965300	653	target Cerro_Negro - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 644-651 - range map product
		4389MH0019300160965400	654	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 634-641 - best focus image product
		4389MH0019300160965500	655	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 634-641 - range map product
		4389MH0019300160965600	656	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 624-631 - best focus image product
		4389MH0019300160965700	657	target Cerro_Negro - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4389 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 624-631 - range map product

updated: 16_December_2024

Sol 4394 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-Dec-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3507 through 4751 (data from Sols 4307-4355) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. Focus stack images from Sol 4393 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4394MH001630001600724900	724	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 716-723 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600725500	725	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 716-723 - range map product
		4394MH001630001600726900	726	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 706-713 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600727500	727	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 706-713 - range map product
		4394MH001630001600728900	728	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 696-703 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600729500	729	target Calabasas_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 696-703 - range map product
		4394MH001630001600730900	730	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 684-691 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600731500	731	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 684-691 - range map product
		4394MH001630001600732900	732	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 674-681 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600733500	733	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 674-681 - range map product
		4394MH001630001600734900	734	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 664-671 - best focus image product
		4394MH001630001600735500	735	target Triunfo_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4393 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 664-671 - range map product

updated: 22_January_2025

Sol 4416 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the target Snow_Creek and the DRT-brushed target Winter_Creek.														
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)												
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>acquired/performed date(s)</td> <td>7-Jan-25</td> </tr> <tr> <td>camera position</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total parent images</td> <td>54</td> </tr> <tr> <td>focus merges performed</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total focus merge products</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total parent images + focus merge products</td> <td>54</td> </tr> </table>					acquired/performed date(s)	7-Jan-25	camera position	2	total parent images	54	focus merges performed	0	total focus merge products	0	total parent images + focus merge products	54
acquired/performed date(s)	7-Jan-25															
camera position	2															
total parent images	54															
focus merges performed	0															
total focus merge products	0															
total parent images + focus merge products	54															
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Image ID:</td> <td>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CPDPD:</td> <td>Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels</td> </tr> </table>					Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	CPDPD:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels								
Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received															
CPDPD:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels															
mN00190	Snow_Creek ~25 cm standoff	4416MH001900011600736CD	736	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Creek - standoff near 25 cm												
		4416MH001900011600737CD	737	target Snow_Creek - standoff near 25 cm												
		4416MH003360011600738CD	738	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600739CD	739	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600740CD	740	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600741CD	741	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600742CD	742	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600743CD	743	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600744CD	744	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600745CD	745	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600746CD	746	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600747CD	747	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600748CD	748	autofocus sub-frame for target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600749CD	749	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600750CD	750	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600751CD	751	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600752CD	752	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600753CD	753	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600754CD	754	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600755CD	755	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600756CD	756	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600757CD	757	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
mN00190	Winter_Creek after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4416MH001900011600758CD	758	autofocus sub-frame for target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm												
		4416MH001900011600759CD	759	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm												
		4416MH003360011600760CD	760	autofocus sub-frame for target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600761CD	761	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600762CD	762	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600763CD	763	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600764CD	764	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600765CD	765	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600766CD	766	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600767CD	767	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600768CD	768	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600769CD	769	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600770CD	770	autofocus sub-frame for target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600771CD	771	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm												
		4416MH003360011600772CD	772	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600773CD	773	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600774CD	774	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600775CD	775	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600776CD	776	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600777CD	777	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600778CD	778	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600779CD	779	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH003360011600780CD	780	autofocus sub-frame for target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm												
		4416MH008480011600781CD	781	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm												
		4416MH008480011600782CD	782	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600783CD	783	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600784CD	784	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600785CD	785	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600786CD	786	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600787CD	787	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600788CD	788	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		4416MH008480011600789CD	789	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												

updated: 17_January_2025

Sol 4417 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-Jan-25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Focus stack images from Sol 4416 were merged.				
mN00227	Focus Merges	4417MH0002270001600790R00	790	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 782-789 - best focus image product
		4417MH0002270001600791S00	791	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 782-789 - range map product
		4417MH0002270001600792R00	792	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 772-779 - best focus image product
		4417MH0002270001600793S00	793	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 772-779 - range map product
		4417MH0002270001600794R00	794	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 762-769 - best focus image product
		4417MH0002270001600795S00	795	target Winter_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 762-769 - range map product
		4417MH0002270001600796R00	796	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 750-757 - best focus image product
		4417MH0002270001600797S00	797	target Snow_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 750-757 - range map product
		4417MH0002270001600798R00	798	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 740-747 - best focus image product
		4417MH0002270001600799S00	799	target Snow_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4416 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 740-747 - range map product

updated: 27_January_2025

Sol 4425 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	16-Jan-25	
		camera position	53	Image ID:
		total parent images	53	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	63	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Rancho_Potrero and the target Fawnskin. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Rancho_Potrero after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4425MH0001900001600800C00	800	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4425MH000190001600801C00	801	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Rancho_Potrero after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4425MH0001680001600802C00	802	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4425MH000168001600803C00	803	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4425MH0001680021600804C00	804	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680031600805C00	805	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680041600806C00	806	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680051600807C00	807	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680061600808C00	808	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680071600809C00	809	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680081600810C00	810	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680091600811C00	811	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Rancho_Potrero after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4425MH0001680001600812C00	812	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4425MH0001680011600813C00	813	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4425MH0001680021600814C00	814	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680031600815C00	815	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680041600816C00	816	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680051600817C00	817	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680061600818C00	818	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680071600819C00	819	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680081600820C00	820	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0001680091600821C00	821	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Rancho_Potrero after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4425MH0007430001600822C00	822	autofocus sub-frame for target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4425MH000743001600823C00	823	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4425MH0007430021600824C00	824	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430031600825C00	825	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430041600826C00	826	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430051600827C00	827	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430061600828C00	828	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430071600829C00	829	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430081600830C00	830	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0007430091600831C00	831	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00894	Fawnskin stereo-1 ~18 cm standoff	4425MH0008940001600832C00	832	autofocus sub-frame for target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm
		4425MH000894001600833C00	833	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm
		4425MH0008940021600834C00	834	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940031600835C00	835	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940041600836C00	836	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940051600837C00	837	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940061600838C00	838	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940071600839C00	839	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940081600840C00	840	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940091600841C00	841	target Fawnskin - stereo-1 - standoff near 18 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00894	Fawnskin stereo-2 ~18 cm standoff	4425MH0008940001600842C00	842	autofocus sub-frame for target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm
		4425MH000894001600843C00	843	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm
		4425MH0008940021600844C00	844	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940031600845C00	845	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940041600846C00	846	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940051600847C00	847	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940061600848C00	848	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940071600849C00	849	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940081600850C00	850	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4425MH0008940091600851C00	851	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	4425MH0002270001600852000	852	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 844-851 - best focus image product
		4425MH0002270001600853000	853	target Fawnskin - stereo-2 - standoff near 18 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 844-851 - range map product
		4425MH0002270001600854000	854	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 834-841 - best focus image product
		4425MH0002270001600855000	855	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 834-841 - range map product
		4425MH0002270001600856000	856	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 824-831 - best focus image product
		4425MH0002270001600857000	857	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 824-831 - range map product
		4425MH0002270001600858000	858	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 814-821 - best focus image product
		4425MH0002270001600859000	859	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 814-821 - range map product
4425MH0002270001600860000	860	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 804-811 - best focus image product		
4425MH0002270001600861000	861	target Rancho_Potrero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4425 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 804-811 - range map product		

Sol 4428 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
		camera position	75		Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		total parent images	0		CPDPD:
		focus merges performed	0		
		total focus merge products	0		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	76		
summary of MAHLI activities					
MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHLI also imaged the target Magk_Mountain and the DRT-brushed target Idiehour.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +90° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4428MH0007120011600862C00	862	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 9 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance of 21 mm	
		4428MH0007120011600863C00	863	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm	
		4428MH0007120011600864C00	864	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm	
		4428MH0007120011600865C00	865	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm	
		4428MH0007120011600866C00	866	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus	
mN00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +90° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4428MH0004530011600867C00	867	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance of 21 mm	
		4428MH0004530011600868C00	868	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm	
		4428MH0004530011600869C00	869	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm	
		4428MH0004530011600870C00	870	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm	
		4428MH0004530011600871C00	871	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm	
mN00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +90° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4428MH0004530011600872C00	872	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus	
		4428MH0004530011600873C00	873	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance of 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0004530011600874C00	874	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0004530011600875C00	875	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0004530011600876C00	876	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
mN00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +90° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4428MH0004530011600877C00	877	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0004530011600878C00	878	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0007120011600879C00	879	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance of 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0007120011600880C00	880	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0007120011600881C00	881	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +90° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	4428MH0007120011600882C00	882	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0007120011600883C00	883	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol	
		4428MH0001900011600884C00	884	autofocus sub-frame for target Magic_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm	
		4428MH0001900011600885C00	885	target Magic_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm	
		4428MH0001680011600886C00	886	autofocus sub-frame for target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
mN00458	Magic_Mountain stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4428MH0001680011600887C00	887	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0001680011600888C00	888	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600889C00	889	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600890C00	890	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600891C00	891	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600892C00	892	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600893C00	893	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600894C00	894	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600895C00	895	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600896C00	896	autofocus sub-frame for target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
mN00458	Magic_Mountain stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4428MH0001680011600897C00	897	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0001680011600898C00	898	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600899C00	899	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600900C00	900	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600901C00	901	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600902C00	902	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600903C00	903	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600904C00	904	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001680011600905C00	905	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0001900011600906C00	906	autofocus sub-frame for target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
mN00336	Idiehour after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4428MH0001900011600907C00	907	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm	
		4428MH0003360011600908C00	908	autofocus sub-frame for target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0003360011600909C00	909	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0003360011600910C00	910	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600911C00	911	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00336	Idiehour after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4428MH0003360011600912C00	912	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600913C00	913	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600914C00	914	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600915C00	915	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600916C00	916	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600917C00	917	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600918C00	918	autofocus sub-frame for target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0003360011600919C00	919	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		4428MH0003360011600920C00	920	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600921C00	921	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00336	Idiehour after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4428MH0003360011600922C00	922	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600923C00	923	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600924C00	924	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600925C00	925	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600926C00	926	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4428MH0003360011600927C00	927	target Idiehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	

Continued on Next Page...

mH00848	Idlehour after DRT ~1 cm standoff	442BMH00848001600928C00	928	autofocus sub-frame for target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		442BMH00848001600929C00	929	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		442BMH00848001600930C00	930	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600931C00	931	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600932C00	932	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600933C00	933	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600934C00	934	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600935C00	935	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		442BMH00848001600936C00	936	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
442BMH00848001600937C00	937	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 23_January_2025

Sol 4429 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20 Jan 25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4428 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4429MH0002270001600938R00	938	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 930-937 - best focus image product
		4429MH0002270001600939S00	939	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 930-937 - range map product
		4429MH0002270001600940R00	940	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 920-927 - best focus image product
		4429MH0002270001600941S00	941	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 920-927 - range map product
		4429MH0002270001600942R00	942	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 910-917 - best focus image product
		4429MH0002270001600943S00	943	target Idlehour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 910-917 - range map product
		4429MH0002270001600944R00	944	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 898-905 - best focus image product
		4429MH0002270001600945S00	945	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 898-905 - range map product
		4429MH0002270001600946R00	946	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 888-895 - best focus image product
		4429MH0002270001600947S00	947	target Magic_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 888-895 - range map product

updated: 29_January_2025

Sol 4431 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jan 25			
		camera position	7	Image ID:		
		total parent images	63	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	63			
MAHLI image the target Pleasant_View_Ridge and the DRT brushed target Bee_Rock.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00876	Pleasant_View_Ridge ~25 cm standoff	4431MH0008760021600948C00	948	autofocus sub-frame for target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm		
		4431MH0008760021600949C00	949	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm		
		4431MH0008760021600950C00	950	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600951C00	951	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600952C00	952	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600953C00	953	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600954C00	954	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600955C00	955	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600956C00	956	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0008760021600957C00	957	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00306	Pleasant_View_Ridge Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4431MH0003060021600958C00	958	autofocus sub-frame for target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003060021600959C00	959	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003060021600960C00	960	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4431MH0003060021600961C00	961	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4431MH0003060021600962C00	962			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003060021600963C00	963			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003060021600964C00	964			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003060021600965C00	965			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003060021600966C00	966			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003060021600967C00	967			target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00306	Pleasant_View_Ridge Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4431MH0003060021600968C00	968	autofocus sub-frame for target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003060021600969C00	969	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003060021600970C00	970	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4431MH0003060021600971C00	971	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4431MH0003060021600972C00	972	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003060021600973C00	973	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003060021600974C00	974	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003060021600975C00	975	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003060021600976C00	976	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003060021600977C00	977	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Bee_Rock after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4431MH0001900021600978C00	978	autofocus sub-frame for target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
				4431MH0001900021600979C00	979	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		mN00336	Bee_Rock after DRT Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4431MH0003360021600980C00	980	autofocus sub-frame for target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003360021600981C00	981	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
4431MH0003360021600982C00	982			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600983C00	983			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600984C00	984			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600985C00	985			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600986C00	986			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600987C00	987			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600988C00	988			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0003360021600989C00	989			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00336	Bee_Rock after DRT Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4431MH0003360021600990C00	990	autofocus sub-frame for target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003360021600991C00	991	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4431MH0003360021600992C00	992	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4431MH0003360021600993C00	993	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4431MH0003360021600994C00	994	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003360021600995C00	995	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003360021600996C00	996	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003360021600997C00	997	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003360021600998C00	998	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4431MH0003360021600999C00	999	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00873	Bee_Rock after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4431MH0008730021601000C00	1000	autofocus sub-frame for target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
				4431MH0008730021601001C00	1001	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
				4431MH0008730021601002C00	1002	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4431MH0008730021601003C00	1003	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4431MH0008730021601004C00	1004			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0008730021601005C00	1005			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0008730021601006C00	1006			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0008730021601007C00	1007			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0008730021601008C00	1008			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4431MH0008730021601009C00	1009			target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 24_January_2025

Sol 4432 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-Jan-2013
Camera position	25
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	33

Focus stack images from Sol 4432 were merged. MAHLI images > 360° of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000163	Focus Merges	4432MH000163000160101000	1010	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1002-1009 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601011500	1011	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1002-1009 - range map product
		4432MH0001630001601012000	1012	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 992-999 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601013500	1013	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 992-999 - range map product
		4432MH0001630001601014000	1014	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 982-989 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601015500	1015	target Bee_Rock - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 982-989 - range map product
		4432MH0001630001601016000	1016	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 970-977 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601017500	1017	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 970-977 - range map product
		4432MH0001630001601018000	1018	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 960-967 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601019500	1019	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 960-967 - range map product
		4432MH0001630001601020000	1020	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 950-957 - best focus image product
		4432MH0001630001601021500	1021	target Pleasant_View_Ridge - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4431 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 950-957 - range map product
		mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4432MH0007690011601022001
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4432MH0007700011601023001	1023	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4432MH0007710011601024001	1024	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4432MH0007720011601025001	1025	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4432MH0007690011601026001	1026	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4432MH0007700011601027001	1027	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4432MH0007710011601028001	1028	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4432MH0007720011601029001	1029	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4432MH0007690011601030001	1030	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4432MH0007700011601031001	1031	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4432MH0007710011601032001	1032	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4432MH0007720011601033001	1033	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4432MH0007690011601034001	1034	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4432MH0007700011601035001	1035	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4432MH0007710011601036001	1036	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4432MH0007720011601037001	1037	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4432MH0007690011601038001	1038	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4432MH0007700011601039001	1039	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4432MH0007710011601040001	1040	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4432MH0007720011601041001	1041	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4432 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

updated: 28_January_2025

Sol 4434 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Jan-25
camera position	74
total parent images	74
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI images of the targets Little_Jimmy, Acton and Wildhorse.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Little_jimmy ~25 cm standoff	443MH000190001601042C0D	1042	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Jimmy - standoff near 25 cm
		443MH000190001601043C0D	1043	target Little_Jimmy - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Little_jimmy stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	443MH0001820021601044C0D	1044	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		443MH0001820021601045C0D	1045	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		443MH0001820021601046C0D	1046	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601047C0D	1047	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601048C0D	1048	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601049C0D	1049	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601050C0D	1050	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601051C0D	1051	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601052C0D	1052	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601053C0D	1053	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Little_jimmy stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	443MH0001820021601054C0D	1054	autofocus sub-frame for target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		443MH0001820021601055C0D	1055	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		443MH0001820021601056C0D	1056	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601057C0D	1057	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601058C0D	1058	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601059C0D	1059	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601060C0D	1060	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601061C0D	1061	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601062C0D	1062	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001820021601063C0D	1063	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Acton ~24 cm standoff	443MH000190001601064C0D	1064	autofocus sub-frame for target Acton - standoff near 24 cm
		443MH000190001601065C0D	1065	target Acton - standoff near 24 cm
mN00173	Acton stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	443MH0001730021601066C0D	1066	autofocus sub-frame for target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH0001730021601067C0D	1067	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH0001730021601068C0D	1068	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601069C0D	1069	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601070C0D	1070	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601071C0D	1071	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601072C0D	1072	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601073C0D	1073	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601074C0D	1074	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601075C0D	1075	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Acton stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	443MH0001730021601076C0D	1076	autofocus sub-frame for target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		443MH0001730021601077C0D	1077	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		443MH0001730021601078C0D	1078	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601079C0D	1079	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601080C0D	1080	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601081C0D	1081	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601082C0D	1082	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601083C0D	1083	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601084C0D	1084	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001730021601085C0D	1085	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00876	Wildhorse ~25 cm standoff	443MH0008760021601086C0D	1086	autofocus sub-frame for target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm
		443MH0008760021601087C0D	1087	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm
		443MH0008760021601088C0D	1088	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601089C0D	1089	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601090C0D	1090	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601091C0D	1091	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601092C0D	1092	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601093C0D	1093	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601094C0D	1094	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0008760021601095C0D	1095	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Wildhorse stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	443MH0001520021601096C0D	1096	autofocus sub-frame for target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH0001520021601097C0D	1097	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH0001520021601098C0D	1098	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601099C0D	1099	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601100C0D	1100	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601101C0D	1101	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601102C0D	1102	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601103C0D	1103	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601104C0D	1104	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH0001520021601105C0D	1105	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00152	Wildhorse stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	443MH000152001601106C00	1106	autofocus sub-frame for target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH000152001601107C00	1107	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		443MH000152001601108C00	1108	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601109C00	1109	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601110C00	1110	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601111C00	1111	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601112C00	1112	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601113C00	1113	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601114C00	1114	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		443MH000152001601115C00	1115	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 18_November_2025

Sol 4435 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Jan-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4434 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4435MH00017J0001601116R00	1116	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1108-1115 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601117S00	1117	target Wildhorse - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1108-1115 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601118R00	1118	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1098-1105 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601119S00	1119	target Wildhorse - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1098-1105 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601120R00	1120	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1088-1095 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601121S00	1121	target Wildhorse - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1088-1095 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601122R00	1122	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1078-1085 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601123S00	1123	target Acton - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1078-1085 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601124R00	1124	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1068-1075 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601125S00	1125	target Acton - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1068-1075 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601126R00	1126	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1056-1063 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601127S00	1127	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1056-1063 - range map product
		4435MH00017J0001601128R00	1128	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1046-1053 - best focus image product
		4435MH00017J0001601129S00	1129	target Little_Jimmy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4434 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1046-1053 - range map product

updated: 03_February_2025

Sol 4437 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-Jan-25
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Desert_View and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Desert_View ~24 cm standoff	4437MH000190001601130C00	1130	autoFocus sub-frame for target Desert_View - standoff near 24 cm
		4437MH000190001601131C00	1131	target Desert_View - standoff near 24 cm
mN002198	Desert_View stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4437MH0001680021601122C00	1132	autoFocus sub-frame for target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4437MH0001680021601133C00	1133	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4437MH0001680021601134C00	1134	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601135C00	1135	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601136C00	1136	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601137C00	1137	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601138C00	1138	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601139C00	1139	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601140C00	1140	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601141C00	1141	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002198	Desert_View stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4437MH0001680021601142C00	1142	autoFocus sub-frame for target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4437MH0001680021601143C00	1143	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4437MH0001680021601144C00	1144	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601145C00	1145	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601146C00	1146	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601147C00	1147	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601148C00	1148	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601149C00	1149	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601150C00	1150	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0001680021601151C00	1151	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Desert_View ~5 mm standoff	4437MH0007430021601152C00	1152	autoFocus sub-frame for target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm
		4437MH0007430021601153C00	1153	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm
		4437MH0007430021601154C00	1154	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601155C00	1155	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601156C00	1156	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601157C00	1157	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601158C00	1158	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601159C00	1159	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601160C00	1160	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4437MH0007430021601161C00	1161	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4437MH0001930001601162R00	1162	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1154-1161 - best focus image product
		4437MH0001930001601163S00	1163	target Desert_View - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1154-1161 - range map product
		4437MH0001930001601164R00	1164	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1144-1151 - best focus image product
		4437MH0001930001601165S00	1165	target Desert_View - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1144-1151 - range map product
		4437MH0001930001601166R00	1166	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1141 - best focus image product
		4437MH0001930001601167S00	1167	target Desert_View - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4437 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1134-1141 - range map product

updated: 04_February_2025

Sol 4439 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25 Jan 25
camera position	2
total parent images	25 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	2 <small>CDPID</small>
total focus merge products	4 <small>Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels</small>
total parent images + focus merge products	29

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Deer_Springs and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Deer_Springs ~25 cm standoff	4439MH00190001601168C00	1168	autoFocus sub-frame for target Deer_Springs - standoff near 25 cm
		4439MH00190001601169C00	1169	target Deer_Springs - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Deer_Springs stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4439MH001680021601170C00	1170	autoFocus sub-frame for target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4439MH00168001601171C00	1171	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4439MH001680021601172C00	1172	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601173C00	1173	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601174C00	1174	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH00168001601175C00	1175	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601176C00	1176	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601177C00	1177	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601178C00	1178	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH00168001601179C00	1179	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Deer_Springs stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4439MH001680021601180C00	1180	autoFocus sub-frame for target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4439MH00168001601181C00	1181	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4439MH001680021601182C00	1182	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH00168001601183C00	1183	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601184C00	1184	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601185C00	1185	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601186C00	1186	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601187C00	1187	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH001680021601188C00	1188	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4439MH00168001601189C00	1189	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	4439MH002050001601190R00	1190	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1182-1189 - best focus image product
		4439MH002050001601191S00	1191	target Deer_Springs - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1182-1189 - range map product
		4439MH002050001601192R00	1192	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1172-1179 - best focus image product
		4439MH002050001601193S00	1193	target Deer_Springs - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1172-1179 - range map product

updated: 03_February_2025

Sol 4441 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	40
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	40

MAHLI imaged the target Coldwater_Canyon, which included a run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Coldwater_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	4441MH0001900016011940D	1194	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4441MH0001900016011950D	1195	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
mN003336	Coldwater_Canyon stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4441MH00033600216011960D	1196	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH0003360016011970D	1197	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH00033600216011980D	1198	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216011990D	1199	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012000D	1200	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012010D	1201	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012020D	1202	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012030D	1203	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012040D	1204	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012050D	1205	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN003336	Coldwater_Canyon stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4441MH00033600216012060D	1206	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH0003360016012070D	1207	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH00033600216012080D	1208	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012090D	1209	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012100D	1210	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012110D	1211	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012120D	1212	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012130D	1213	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012140D	1214	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00033600216012150D	1215	target Coldwater_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00866	Coldwater_Canyon MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4441MH0008660016012160D	1216	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH0008660016012170D	1217	target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00867	Coldwater_Canyon MAHLI prox mode ~4 cm standoff	4441MH0008670016012180D	1218	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
		4441MH0008670016012190D	1219	target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 4 cm
mN00868	Coldwater_Canyon MAHLI prox mode ~3 cm standoff	4441MH0008680016012200D	1220	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
		4441MH0008680016012210D	1221	target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 3 cm
mN00869	Coldwater_Canyon MAHLI prox mode ~2 cm standoff	4441MH0008690016012220D	1222	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
		4441MH0008690016012230D	1223	target Coldwater_Canyon - MAHLI proximity mode - standoff near 2 cm
mN00873	Coldwater_Canyon ~2 cm standoff	4441MH00087300216012240D	1224	autofocus sub-frame for target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm
		4441MH0008730016012250D	1225	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm
		4441MH00087300216012260D	1226	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012270D	1227	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012280D	1228	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012290D	1229	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012300D	1230	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012310D	1231	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012320D	1232	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4441MH00087300216012330D	1233	target Coldwater_Canyon - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 03_February_2025

Sol 4442 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-FEB-25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	6

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4441 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00289	Focus Merges	4442MH001930001601234800	1234	target Coldwater_canyon - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1226-1233 - best focus image product
		4442MH001930001601235500	1235	target Coldwater_canyon - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1226-1233 - range map product
		4442MH001930001601236800	1236	target Coldwater_canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1208-1215 - best focus image product
		4442MH001930001601237500	1237	target Coldwater_canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1208-1215 - range map product
		4442MH001930001601238800	1238	target Coldwater_canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1198-1205 - best focus image product
		4442MH001930001601239500	1239	target Coldwater_canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4441 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1198-1205 - range map product

mH00176	Allison_Mine -15 mm standoff	4443MH00176001601308C00	1308	autofocus sub-frame for target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm
		4443MH00176001601309C00	1309	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm
		4443MH00176001601310C00	1310	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601311C00	1311	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601312C00	1312	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601313C00	1313	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601314C00	1314	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601315C00	1315	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4443MH00176001601316C00	1316	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4443MH00176001601317C00	1317	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 05_February_2025

Sol 4444 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4443 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4444MH00017J0001601318R00	1318	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1310-1317 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601319S00	1319	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1310-1317 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601320R00	1320	target Allison_Mine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1300-1307 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601321S00	1321	target Allison_Mine - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1300-1307 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601322R00	1322	target Allison_Mine - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1290-1297 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601323S00	1323	target Allison_Mine - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1290-1297 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601324R00	1324	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1280-1287 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601325S00	1325	target Allison_Mine - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1280-1287 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601326R00	1326	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1270-1277 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601327S00	1327	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1270-1277 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601328R00	1328	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1254-1261 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601329S00	1329	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1254-1261 - range map product
		4444MH00017J0001601330R00	1330	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1244-1251 - best focus image product
		4444MH00017J0001601331S00	1331	target San_Rafael_Hills - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4443 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1244-1251 - range map product

updated: 13_February_2025

Sol 4445 - MAHLI Images

		acquired(performed date(s))	CPDP	
		camera position	13	Image ID:
		total parent images	13	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CPDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	13	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the target Zuma_Canyon and the DRT-brushed target Bear_Canyon.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4445MH0003720011601332C0D	1332	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		4445MH0003710011601333C0D	1333	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
m1N00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4445MH0003720011601334C0D	1334	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		4445MH0003730011601335C0D	1335	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
m1N00374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4445MH0003740011601336C0D	1336	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4445MH0003740011601337C0D	1337	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4445MH0003740011601338C0D	1338	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
m1N00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4445MH0003730011601339C0D	1339	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH0003730011601340C0D	1340	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
m1N00390	Zuma_Canyon ~25 cm standoff	4445MH0001900011601341C0D	1341	autofocus sub-frame for target Zuma_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm
		4445MH0001900011601342C0D	1342	target Zuma_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm
m1N00368	Zuma_Canyon stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4445MH00016800011601343C0D	1343	autofocus sub-frame for target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00016800011601344C0D	1344	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00016800011601345C0D	1345	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601346C0D	1346	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601347C0D	1347	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601348C0D	1348	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601349C0D	1349	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601350C0D	1350	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601351C0D	1351	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601352C0D	1352	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00368	Zuma_Canyon stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4445MH00016800011601353C0D	1353	autofocus sub-frame for target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00016800011601354C0D	1354	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00016800011601355C0D	1355	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601356C0D	1356	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601357C0D	1357	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601358C0D	1358	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601359C0D	1359	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601360C0D	1360	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601361C0D	1361	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00016800011601362C0D	1362	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00372	Bear_Canyon after DRT ~20 cm standoff	4445MH0001720011601363C0D	1363	autofocus sub-frame for target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 20 cm
		4445MH0001720011601364C0D	1364	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 20 cm
m1N00396	Bear_Canyon after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4445MH00033600011601365C0D	1365	autofocus sub-frame for target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00033600011601366C0D	1366	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00033600011601367C0D	1367	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601368C0D	1368	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601369C0D	1369	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601370C0D	1370	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601371C0D	1371	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601372C0D	1372	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601373C0D	1373	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601374C0D	1374	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00396	Bear_Canyon after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4445MH00033600011601375C0D	1375	autofocus sub-frame for target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00033600011601376C0D	1376	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4445MH00033600011601377C0D	1377	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601378C0D	1378	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601379C0D	1379	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601380C0D	1380	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601381C0D	1381	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601382C0D	1382	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601383C0D	1383	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00033600011601384C0D	1384	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00848	Bear_Canyon after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4445MH00084800011601385C0D	1385	autofocus sub-frame for target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4445MH00084800011601386C0D	1386	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4445MH00084800011601387C0D	1387	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601388C0D	1388	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601389C0D	1389	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601390C0D	1390	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601391C0D	1391	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601392C0D	1392	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601393C0D	1393	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4445MH00084800011601394C0D	1394	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 07_February_2025

Sol 4446 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Feb 25
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4445 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	4446MH002270001601395R00	1395	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1387-1394 - best focus image product
		4446MH002270001601396S00	1396	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1387-1394 - range map product
		4446MH002270001601397R00	1397	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1377-1384 - best focus image product
		4446MH002270001601398S00	1398	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1377-1384 - range map product
		4446MH002270001601399R00	1399	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1367-1374 - best focus image product
		4446MH002270001601400S00	1400	target Bear_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1367-1374 - range map product
		4446MH002270001601401R00	1401	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1355-1362 - best focus image product
		4446MH002270001601402S00	1402	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1355-1362 - range map product
		4446MH002270001601403R00	1403	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1345-1352 - best focus image product
		4446MH002270001601404S00	1404	target Zuma_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4445 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1345-1352 - range map product

updated: 13_February_2025

Sol 4447 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	55
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	55

MAHLI imaged the target Bridge_To_Nowhere, which included a 2x1 mosaic, and the DRT-brushed target Aliso_Canyon.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Bridge_To_Nowhere mosaic position 1 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	4447MH0019000116014050CD	1405	autofocus sub-frame for target Bridge_To_Nowhere - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4447MH0019000116014060CD	1406	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Bridge_To_Nowhere stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4447MH0016800116014070CD	1407	autofocus sub-frame for target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014080CD	1408	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014090CD	1409	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014100CD	1410	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014110CD	1411	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014120CD	1412	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014130CD	1413	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014140CD	1414	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014150CD	1415	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014160CD	1416	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Bridge_To_Nowhere stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4447MH0016800116014170CD	1417	autofocus sub-frame for target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014180CD	1418	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014190CD	1419	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014200CD	1420	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014210CD	1421	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014220CD	1422	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014230CD	1423	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014240CD	1424	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014250CD	1425	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014260CD	1426	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Bridge_To_Nowhere mosaic position 2 of 2 ~24 cm standoff	4447MH0019000116014270CD	1427	autofocus sub-frame for target Bridge_To_Nowhere - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4447MH0019000116014280CD	1428	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00190	Aliso_Canyon after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4447MH0019000116014290CD	1429	autofocus sub-frame for target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4447MH0019000116014300CD	1430	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Aliso_Canyon after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4447MH0016800116014310CD	1431	autofocus sub-frame for target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014320CD	1432	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014330CD	1433	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014340CD	1434	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014350CD	1435	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014360CD	1436	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014370CD	1437	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014380CD	1438	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014390CD	1439	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014400CD	1440	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Aliso_Canyon after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4447MH0016800116014410CD	1441	autofocus sub-frame for target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014420CD	1442	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4447MH0016800116014430CD	1443	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014440CD	1444	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014450CD	1445	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014460CD	1446	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014470CD	1447	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014480CD	1448	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014490CD	1449	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0016800116014500CD	1450	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Aliso_Canyon after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4447MH0030200116014510CD	1451	autofocus sub-frame for target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4447MH0030200116014520CD	1452	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4447MH0030200116014530CD	1453	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014540CD	1454	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014550CD	1455	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014560CD	1456	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014570CD	1457	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014580CD	1458	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014590CD	1459	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4447MH0030200116014600CD	1460	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 12_February_2025

Sol 4449 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 4447 were merged.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
mN00227	Focus Merges	4449MH0002270001601461900	1461	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1453-1460 - best focus image product
		4449MH0002270001601462500	1462	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1453-1460 - range map product
		4449MH0002270001601463900	1463	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1443-1450 - best focus image product
		4449MH0002270001601464500	1464	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1443-1450 - range map product
		4449MH0002270001601465900	1465	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1433-1440 - best focus image product
		4449MH0002270001601466500	1466	target Aliso_Canyon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1433-1440 - range map product
		4449MH0002270001601467900	1467	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1419-1426 - best focus image product
		4449MH0002270001601468500	1468	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1419-1426 - range map product
		4449MH0002270001601469900	1469	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1409-1416 - best focus image product
		4449MH0002270001601470500	1470	target Bridge_To_Nowhere - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4447 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1409-1416 - range map product

updated: 18_February_2025

Sol 4452 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	18-Feb-25	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Catalina_Island and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALS_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Catalina_Island after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4452MH00190001601471ZC00	1471	autoFocus sub-frame for target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4452MH00190001601472ZC00	1472	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Catalina_Island after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4452MH001680001601473Z00	1473	autoFocus sub-frame for target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4452MH00168001601474ZC00	1474	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4452MH001680021601475Z00	1475	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601476ZC00	1476	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601477Z00	1477	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601478ZC00	1478	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601479Z00	1479	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601480ZC00	1480	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601481Z00	1481	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601482ZC00	1482	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Catalina_Island after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4452MH001680001601483Z00	1483	autoFocus sub-frame for target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4452MH00168001601484ZC00	1484	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4452MH001680021601485Z00	1485	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601486ZC00	1486	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601487Z00	1487	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601488ZC00	1488	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601489Z00	1489	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601490ZC00	1490	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601491Z00	1491	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH001680021601492ZC00	1492	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Catalina_Island after DRT ~5 mm standoff	4452MH007430001601493Z00	1493	autoFocus sub-frame for target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4452MH007430011601494ZC00	1494	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		4452MH007430021601495Z00	1495	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601496ZC00	1496	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601497Z00	1497	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601498ZC00	1498	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601499Z00	1499	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601500ZC00	1500	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601501Z00	1501	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4452MH007430021601502ZC00	1502	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4452MH001930001601503Z00	1503	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1502 - best focus image product
		4452MH001930001601504Z00	1504	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1502 - range map product
		4452MH001930001601505Z00	1505	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1492 - best focus image product
		4452MH001930001601506Z00	1506	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1492 - range map product
		4452MH001930001601507Z00	1507	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1475-1482 - best focus image product
		4452MH001930001601508Z00	1508	target Catalina_Island - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4452 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1475-1482 - range map product

Sol 4455 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Feb-25
camera position	45
total parent images	134
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	134

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Skyline_Trail and the DRT-brushed target Lake_Arrowhead. MAHLI also imaged the target Strawberry_Peak, which included a full run of the MAHLI proximity mode, a capability that uses MAHLI onboard range-finding to guide MAHLI closer to the surface.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00876	Skyline_Trail stereo-1 ~25 cm standoff	4455MH0008760021601509000	1509	autofocus sub-frame for target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4455MH0008760021601510000	1510	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		4455MH0008760021601511000	1511	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601512000	1512	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601513000	1513	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601514000	1514	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601515000	1515	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601516000	1516	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601517000	1517	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601518000	1518	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00876	Skyline_Trail stereo-2 ~25 cm standoff	4455MH0008760021601519000	1519	autofocus sub-frame for target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4455MH0008760021601520000	1520	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4455MH0008760021601521000	1521	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601522000	1522	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601523000	1523	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601524000	1524	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601525000	1525	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601526000	1526	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601527000	1527	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0008760021601528000	1528	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00166	Skyline_Trail stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4455MH0001660021601529000	1529	autofocus sub-frame for target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4455MH0001660021601530000	1530	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4455MH0001660021601531000	1531	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601532000	1532	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601533000	1533	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601534000	1534	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601535000	1535	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601536000	1536	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601537000	1537	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601538000	1538	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00166	Skyline_Trail stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4455MH0001660021601539000	1539	autofocus sub-frame for target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4455MH0001660021601540000	1540	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4455MH0001660021601541000	1541	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601542000	1542	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601543000	1543	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601544000	1544	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601545000	1545	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601546000	1546	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601547000	1547	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0001660021601548000	1548	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Lake_Arrowhead after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4455MH0001900021601549000	1549	autofocus sub-frame for target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4455MH0001900021601550000	1550	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Lake_Arrowhead after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4455MH0003360021601551000	1551	autofocus sub-frame for target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4455MH0003360021601552000	1552	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4455MH0003360021601553000	1553	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601554000	1554	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601555000	1555	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601556000	1556	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601557000	1557	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601558000	1558	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601559000	1559	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601560000	1560	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Lake_Arrowhead after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4455MH0003360021601561000	1561	autofocus sub-frame for target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4455MH0003360021601562000	1562	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4455MH0003360021601563000	1563	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601564000	1564	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601565000	1565	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601566000	1566	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601567000	1567	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601568000	1568	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601569000	1569	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4455MH0003360021601570000	1570	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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updated: 18_February_2025

Sol 4456 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	12
total focus merge products	24
total parent images + focus merge products	24

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4455 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100458	Focus Merges	4456MH0004580001601643900	1643	target Strawberry_Peak - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1639-1642 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601644500	1644	target Strawberry_Peak - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1639-1642 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601645900	1645	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1613-1620 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601646500	1646	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1613-1620 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601647900	1647	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1603-1610 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601648500	1648	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1603-1610 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601649900	1649	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1593-1600 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601650500	1650	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1593-1600 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601651900	1651	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1583-1590 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601652500	1652	target Strawberry_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1583-1590 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601653900	1653	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1573-1580 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601654500	1654	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1573-1580 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601655900	1655	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1563-1570 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601656500	1656	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1563-1570 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601657900	1657	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1553-1560 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601658500	1658	target Lake_Arrowhead - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1553-1560 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601659900	1659	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1541-1548 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601660500	1660	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1541-1548 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601661900	1661	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1531-1538 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601662500	1662	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1531-1538 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601663900	1663	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1521-1528 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601664500	1664	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1521-1528 - range map product
		4456MH0004580001601665900	1665	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1511-1518 - best focus image product
		4456MH0004580001601666500	1666	target Skyline_Trail - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4455 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1511-1518 - range map product

updated: 21_February_2025

Sol 4459 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	13

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4458 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4459MH001630001601731900	1731	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1723-1730 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601732500	1732	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1723-1730 - range map product
		4459MH001630001601732900	1733	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1713-1720 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601734500	1734	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1713-1720 - range map product
		4459MH001630001601735900	1735	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1703-1710 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601736500	1736	target Chumash_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1703-1710 - range map product
		4459MH001630001601737900	1737	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1691-1698 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601738500	1738	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1691-1698 - range map product
		4459MH001630001601739900	1739	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1681-1688 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601740500	1740	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1681-1688 - range map product
		4459MH001630001601741900	1741	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1671-1678 - best focus image product
		4459MH001630001601742500	1742	target Wheeler_Gorge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1671-1678 - range map product

updated: 24_February_2025

Sol 4461 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Feb-25
camera position	12
total parent images	55
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	55

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. MAHLI also imaged the targets Wellman_Divide and Salton_Sea.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	4461MH00037200116017430D	1743	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		4461MH00037200116017440D	1744	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
m1N00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	4461MH00037200116017450D	1745	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		4461MH00037200116017460D	1746	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
m1N00374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	4461MH00037400116017470D	1747	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4461MH00037400116017480D	1748	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		4461MH00037400116017490D	1749	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
m1N00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	4461MH00037300116017500D	1750	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		4461MH00037300116017510D	1751	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
m1N00390	Wellman_Divide ~24 cm standoff	4461MH00019000116017520D	1752	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - standoff near 24 cm
		4461MH00019000116017530D	1753	target Wellman_Divide - standoff near 24 cm
m1N00299	Wellman_Divide stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00029900116017540D	1754	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH00029900116017550D	1755	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH00029900116017560D	1756	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017570D	1757	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017580D	1758	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017590D	1759	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017600D	1760	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017610D	1761	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017620D	1762	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017630D	1763	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00299	Wellman_Divide stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00029900116017640D	1764	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH00029900116017650D	1765	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH00029900116017660D	1766	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017670D	1767	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017680D	1768	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017690D	1769	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017700D	1770	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017710D	1771	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017720D	1772	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH00029900116017730D	1773	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 3 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017740D	1774	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 3 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 4 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017750D	1775	target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 3 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 5 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017760D	1776	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 4 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 5 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017770D	1777	target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 4 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 5 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017780D	1778	autofocus sub-frame for target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 5 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00705	Wellman_Divide relief model position 5 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH00070500116017790D	1779	target Wellman_Divide - relief model position 5 - standoff near 4 cm
m1N00390	Salton_Sea ~24 cm standoff	4461MH00019000116017800D	1780	autofocus sub-frame for target Salton_Sea - standoff near 24 cm
		4461MH00019000116017810D	1781	target Salton_Sea - standoff near 24 cm
m1N00396	Salton_Sea stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH0003600116017820D	1782	autofocus sub-frame for target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH0003600116017830D	1783	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH0003600116017840D	1784	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017850D	1785	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017860D	1786	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017870D	1787	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017880D	1788	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017890D	1789	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017900D	1790	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017910D	1791	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00396	Salton_Sea stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4461MH0003600116017920D	1792	autofocus sub-frame for target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH0003600116017930D	1793	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4461MH0003600116017940D	1794	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017950D	1795	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017960D	1796	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017970D	1797	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017980D	1798	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116017990D	1799	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116018000D	1800	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4461MH0003600116018010D	1801	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 24_February_2025

Sol 4462 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Feb-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4462 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	4462MH001530001601802900	1802	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1784-1801 - best focus image product
		4462MH001530001601803500	1803	target Salton_Sea - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1794-1801 - range map product
		4462MH001530001601804900	1804	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1784-1791 - best focus image product
		4462MH001530001601805500	1805	target Salton_Sea - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1784-1791 - range map product
		4462MH001530001601806900	1806	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1766-1773 - best focus image product
		4462MH001530001601807500	1807	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1766-1773 - range map product
		4462MH001530001601808900	1808	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1756-1763 - best focus image product
		4462MH001530001601809500	1809	target Wellman_Divide - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4461 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1756-1763 - range map product

Sol 4464 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Feb-25
camera position	3
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Matliija_Poppy and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN000359	Matliija_Poppy ~25 cm standoff	4464MH0003590021601810C00	1810	autofocus sub-frame for target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm		
		4464MH0003590011601811C00	1811	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm		
		4464MH0003590021601812C00	1812	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590011601813C00	1813	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590021601814C00	1814	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590011601815C00	1815	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590021601816C00	1816	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590011601817C00	1817	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590021601818C00	1818	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0003590011601819C00	1819	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN000182	Matliija_Poppy stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4464MH0001820021601820C00	1820	autofocus sub-frame for target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4464MH0001820011601821C00	1821	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4464MH0001820021601822C00	1822	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4464MH0001820011601823C00	1823	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4464MH0001820021601824C00	1824	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4464MH0001820011601825C00	1825			target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4464MH0001820021601826C00	1826			target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4464MH0001820011601827C00	1827			target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4464MH0001820021601828C00	1828			target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4464MH0001820011601829C00	1829			target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN000182	Matliija_Poppy stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4464MH0001820021601830C00	1830	autofocus sub-frame for target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4464MH0001820011601831C00	1831	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4464MH0001820021601832C00	1832	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4464MH0001820011601833C00	1833	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4464MH0001820021601834C00	1834	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4464MH0001820011601835C00	1835	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0001820021601836C00	1836	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0001820011601837C00	1837	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0001820021601838C00	1838	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4464MH0001820011601839C00	1839	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN000189	Focus Merges	4464MH0001930021601840R00	1840	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1832-1839 - best focus image product
				4464MH0001930011601841S00	1841	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1832-1839 - range map product
				4464MH0001930021601842R00	1842	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1822-1829 - best focus image product
				4464MH0001930011601843S00	1843	target Matliija_Poppy - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1822-1829 - range map product
				4464MH0001930021601844R00	1844	target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1812-1819 - best focus image product
4464MH0001930011601845S00	1845			target Matliija_Poppy - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4464 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1812-1819 - range map product		

updated: 03_March_2025

Sol 4466 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	27-Feb-25	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Trippet_Ranch and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Trippet_Ranch after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4466MH001900011601846C0D	1846	autoFocus sub-frame for target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4466MH001900011601847C0D	1847	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002196	Trippet_Ranch after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4466MH002360021601849C0D	1848	autoFocus sub-frame for target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4466MH002360021601849C0D	1849	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4466MH002360021601850C0D	1850	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601851C0D	1851	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601852C0D	1852	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601853C0D	1853	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601854C0D	1854	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601855C0D	1855	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601856C0D	1856	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601857C0D	1857	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Trippet_Ranch after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4466MH002360021601858C0D	1858	autoFocus sub-frame for target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4466MH002360021601859C0D	1859	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4466MH002360021601860C0D	1860	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601861C0D	1861	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601862C0D	1862	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601863C0D	1863	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601864C0D	1864	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601865C0D	1865	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601866C0D	1866	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH002360021601867C0D	1867	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002196	Trippet_Ranch after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4466MH0020840021601868C0D	1868	autoFocus sub-frame for target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4466MH0020840021601869C0D	1869	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4466MH0020840021601870C0D	1870	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601871C0D	1871	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601872C0D	1872	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601873C0D	1873	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601874C0D	1874	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601875C0D	1875	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002199	Focus Merges	4466MH002360021601876C0D	1876	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH0020840021601877C0D	1877	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4466MH001930011601878C0D	1878	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1870-1877 - best focus image product
		4466MH001930011601879C0D	1879	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1870-1877 - range map product
		4466MH001930011601880C0D	1880	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1860-1867 - best focus image product
		4466MH001930011601881C0D	1881	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1860-1867 - range map product
		4466MH001930011601882C0D	1882	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1850-1857 - best focus image product
		4466MH001930011601883C0D	1883	target Trippet_Ranch - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1850-1857 - range map product

updated: 12_March_2025

Sol 4471 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-Mar-25
camera position	4
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	48

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Ramona_Trail and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00876	Ramona_Trail after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4471MH0008760021601884C0D	1884	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4471MH0008760021601885C0D	1885	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4471MH0008760021601886C0D	1886	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601887C0D	1887	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601888C0D	1888	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601889C0D	1889	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601890C0D	1890	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601891C0D	1891	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601892C0D	1892	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008760021601893C0D	1893	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ramona_Trail after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4471MH0001680021601894C0D	1894	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4471MH0001680021601895C0D	1895	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4471MH0001680021601896C0D	1896	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601897C0D	1897	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601898C0D	1898	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601899C0D	1899	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601900C0D	1900	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601901C0D	1901	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601902C0D	1902	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601903C0D	1903	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ramona_Trail after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4471MH0001680021601904C0D	1904	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4471MH0001680021601905C0D	1905	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4471MH0001680021601906C0D	1906	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601907C0D	1907	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601908C0D	1908	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601909C0D	1909	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601910C0D	1910	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601911C0D	1911	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601912C0D	1912	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0001680021601913C0D	1913	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Ramona_Trail after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4471MH0008640021601914C0D	1914	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4471MH0008640021601915C0D	1915	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4471MH0008640021601916C0D	1916	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601917C0D	1917	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601918C0D	1918	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601919C0D	1919	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601920C0D	1920	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601921C0D	1921	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601922C0D	1922	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4471MH0008640021601923C0D	1923	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	4471MH0001530016019240D	1924	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1916-1923 - best focus image product
		4471MH0001530016019250D	1925	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1916-1923 - range map product
		4471MH0001530016019260D	1926	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1906-1913 - best focus image product
		4471MH0001530016019270D	1927	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1906-1913 - range map product
		4471MH0001530016019280D	1928	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1896-1903 - best focus image product
		4471MH0001530016019290D	1929	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1896-1903 - range map product
		4471MH0001530016019300D	1930	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1886-1893 - best focus image product
4471MH00015300160193150D	1931	target Ramona_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1886-1893 - range map product		

updated: 12_March_2025

Sol 4478 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-Mar-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4477 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00789	Focus Merges	4478MH00789001601997900	1997	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1969-1996 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001601998500	1998	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1969-1996 - range map product
		4478MH00789001601999900	1999	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1979-1996 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001602000500	2000	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1979-1996 - range map product
		4478MH00789001602001900	2001	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1969-1976 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001602002500	2002	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1969-1976 - range map product
		4478MH00789001602003900	2003	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1959-1966 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001602004500	2004	target Millard_Canyon - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1959-1966 - range map product
		4478MH00789001602005900	2005	target Angeles_Crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1949-1956 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001602006500	2006	target Angeles_Crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1949-1956 - range map product
		4478MH00789001602007900	2007	target Angeles_Crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1938-1945 - best focus image product
		4478MH00789001602008500	2008	target Angeles_Crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4477 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1938-1945 - range map product

updated: 14_March_2025

Sol 4479 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-Mar-25
camera position	40
total parent images	100
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	100

MAHLI image of the target Stunt_Ranch and the target Pacifico_Mountain, which includes a 3x1 mosaic.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00855	Stunt_Ranch Stereo-1 ~26 cm standoff	4479MH0008550011602009C00	2009	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602010C00	2010	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602011C00	2011	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602012C00	2012	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602013C00	2013	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602014C00	2014	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602015C00	2015	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602016C00	2016	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602017C00	2017	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602018C00	2018	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Stunt_Ranch Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4479MH0002970011602019C00	2019	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4479MH0002970011602020C00	2020	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4479MH0002970011602021C00	2021	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602022C00	2022	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602023C00	2023	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602024C00	2024	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602025C00	2025	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602026C00	2026	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602027C00	2027	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602028C00	2028	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Stunt_Ranch Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4479MH0002970011602029C00	2029	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4479MH0002970011602030C00	2030	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4479MH0002970011602031C00	2031	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602032C00	2032	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602033C00	2033	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602034C00	2034	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602035C00	2035	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602036C00	2036	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602037C00	2037	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0002970011602038C00	2038	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00649	Stunt_Ranch ~1 cm standoff	4479MH0006490011602039C00	2039	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm
		4479MH0006490011602040C00	2040	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm
		4479MH0006490011602041C00	2041	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602042C00	2042	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602043C00	2043	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602044C00	2044	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602045C00	2045	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602046C00	2046	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602047C00	2047	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0006490011602048C00	2048	target Stunt_Ranch - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00855	Stunt_Ranch Stereo-2 ~26 cm standoff	4479MH0008550011602049C00	2049	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602050C00	2050	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602051C00	2051	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602052C00	2052	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602053C00	2053	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602054C00	2054	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602055C00	2055	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602056C00	2056	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602057C00	2057	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602058C00	2058	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00855	Stunt_Ranch Stereo-3 ~26 cm standoff	4479MH0008550011602059C00	2059	autofocus sub-frame for target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602060C00	2060	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm
		4479MH0008550011602061C00	2061	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602062C00	2062	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602063C00	2063	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602064C00	2064	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602065C00	2065	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602066C00	2066	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602067C00	2067	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4479MH0008550011602068C00	2068	target Stunt_Ranch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

updated: 14_March_2025

Sol 4480 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	14-Mar-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	10
total focus merge products	20
total parent images + focus merge products	20

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4479 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100369	Focus Merges	4480MH00369000160210900	2109	target Pacific_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2101-2108 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602110500	2110	target Pacific_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2101-2108 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602111900	2111	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2091-2098 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602112500	2112	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2091-2098 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602113900	2113	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 8 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2081-2088 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602114500	2114	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 8 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2081-2088 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602115900	2115	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 75 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2071-2078 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602116500	2116	target Pacific_Mountain - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 75 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2071-2078 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602117900	2117	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2061-2068 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602118500	2118	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-3 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2061-2068 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602119900	2119	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2051-2058 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602120500	2120	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-2 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2051-2058 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602121900	2121	target Stunt_Banch - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2041-2048 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602122500	2122	target Stunt_Banch - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2041-2048 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602123900	2123	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2031-2038 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602124500	2124	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2031-2038 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602125900	2125	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2021-2028 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602126500	2126	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2021-2028 - range map product
		4480MH003690001602127900	2127	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2011-2018 - best focus image product
		4480MH003690001602128500	2128	target Stunt_Banch - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4479 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2011-2018 - range map product

mH00673	Sepulveda_Pass stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4481MH000673001602259C00	2259	autofocus sub-frame for target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4481MH000673001602260C00	2260	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4481MH000673001602261C00	2261	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602262C00	2262	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602263C00	2263	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602264C00	2264	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602265C00	2265	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602266C00	2266	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602267C00	2267	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4481MH000673001602268C00	2268	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 18_March_2025

Sol 4483 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Mar-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	14
total focus merge products	28
total parent images + focus merge products	28

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 4483 were merged.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
m1N00728	Focus Merges	4483MH0072800160226900	2269	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2261-2268 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602270500	2270	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2261-2268 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602271900	2271	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2251-2258 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602272500	2272	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2251-2258 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602273900	2273	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602274500	2274	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602275900	2275	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2231-2238 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602276500	2276	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2231-2238 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602277900	2277	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2221-2228 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602278500	2278	target Sepulveda_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2221-2228 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602279900	2279	target South_Fork - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2211-2218 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602280500	2280	target South_Fork - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2211-2218 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602281900	2281	target South_Fork - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2201-2208 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602282500	2282	target South_Fork - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2201-2208 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602283900	2283	target South_Fork - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2191-2198 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602284500	2284	target South_Fork - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2191-2198 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602285900	2285	target South_Fork - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2181-2188 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602286500	2286	target South_Fork - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2181-2188 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602287900	2287	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 5 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2171-2178 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602288500	2288	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 5 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2171-2178 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602289900	2289	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2161-2168 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602290500	2290	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2161-2168 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602291900	2291	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2151-2158 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602292500	2292	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2151-2158 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602293900	2293	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2141-2148 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602294500	2294	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2141-2148 - range map product
		4483MH00728001602295900	2295	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2131-2138 - best focus image product
		4483MH00728001602296500	2296	target Yerba Buena_Ridge - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff between 12 cm and 21 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4481 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2131-2138 - range map product

updated: 21_March_2025

Sol 4487 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Mar-25
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	39
total focus merge products	40
total parent images + focus merge products	40

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities
 Focus stack images from Sol 4486 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
m1H00163	Focus Merges	4487MH000163000160249900	2499	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 16 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2491-2498 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160250000	2500	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 16 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2491-2498 - range map product		
		4487MH000163000160250100	2501	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 15 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2481-2488 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160250200	2502	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 15 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2481-2488 - range map product		
		4487MH000163000160250300	2503	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 14 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2471-2478 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160250400	2504	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 14 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2471-2478 - range map product		
		4487MH000163000160250500	2505	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 13 of 16 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2461-2468 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160250600	2506	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 13 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2461-2468 - range map product		
		4487MH000163000160250700	2507	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 12 of 16 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2451-2458 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160250800	2508	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 12 of 16 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2451-2458 - range map product		
		4487MH000163000160250900	2509	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 11 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2441-2448 - best focus image product		
		4487MH000163000160251000	2510	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 11 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2441-2448 - range map product		
		m1H00897	Focus Merges	4487MH000897000160251100	2511	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 10 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2431-2438 - best focus image product
				4487MH000897000160251200	2512	target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 10 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2431-2438 - range map product
4487MH000897000160251300	2513			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 9 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2421-2428 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160251400	2514			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 9 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2421-2428 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160251500	2515			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 8 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2411-2418 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160251600	2516			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 8 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2411-2418 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160251700	2517			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 7 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2401-2408 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160251800	2518			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 7 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2401-2408 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160251900	2519			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 6 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2391-2398 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160252000	2520			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 6 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2391-2398 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160252100	2521			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 5 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2381-2388 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160252200	2522			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 5 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2381-2388 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160252300	2523			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 4 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2371-2378 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160252400	2524			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 4 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2371-2378 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160252500	2525			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 3 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2361-2368 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160252600	2526			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 3 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2361-2368 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160252700	2527			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 2 of 16 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2351-2358 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160252800	2528			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 2 of 16 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2351-2358 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160252900	2529			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 1 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2341-2348 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160253000	2530			target Duna_Vista - mosaic position 1 of 16 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2341-2348 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160253100	2531			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2331-2338 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160253200	2532			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2331-2338 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160253300	2533			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2321-2328 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160253400	2534			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2321-2328 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160253500	2535			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2311-2318 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160253600	2536			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2311-2318 - range map product		
4487MH000897000160253700	2537			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2301-2308 - best focus image product		
4487MH000897000160253800	2538			target Palm_Grove - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4486 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2301-2308 - range map product		

mH00166	Black_Oak stereo-2 -3 cm standoff	448BMH00166001602601C00	2501	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		448BMH00166001602602C00	2502	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		448BMH00166001602603C00	2503	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602604C00	2504	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602605C00	2505	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602606C00	2506	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602607C00	2507	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602608C00	2508	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602609C00	2509	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		448BMH00166001602610C00	2510	target Black_Oak - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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